

Geotek Coring Inc. Report to
ASRC Consulting & Environmental Services, LLC

JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22

Pressure Coring and Core Analysis on Alaska North Slope

part of the
Extended Duration Scientific Reservoir Response Test at Site Kuparuk
State 7-11-12, Prudhoe Bay Unit

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GEOTEK Coring Inc.

3350 W Directors Row Ste # 600

Salt Lake City, UT 84104, USA

Tel: +1 385-528-2536

e-mail: info@geotek.co.uk

web site: www.geotekcoring.com

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JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22

Executive Summary

The Geotek “JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22” program of work provided by Geotek Coring Inc. (GCI) was designed to fulfil a component of the joint JOGMEC/DOE program for the “**Extended Duration Scientific Reservoir Response Test at Site Kuparuk State 7-11-12, Prudhoe Bay Unit**” on the Alaska North Slope (ANS). The whole coring and core analysis program was divided into two main phases: A) rig site operations, which included all the coring operations and the initial core analysis; and B) a secondary field laboratory operation at GCI’s Salt Lake City (SLC) headquarters which included all the final core analysis operations and the distribution of samples to client authorised laboratories. The Geotek contract was managed by ASRC Consulting & Environmental Services LLC over a period of many months through 2022 and 2023. Geotek’s involvement in this project was limited to coring operations in the first well drilled, Hydrate-02, also known as the Geoscience Data Well (GDW), with the technical program being defined by an external Project Owner Group.

The primary objective of the coring program was to provide a continuous physical record from the pressure cores, collected with the HPTC IV JOGMEC pressure coring tool designed and developed by Geotek Coring, through both of these known gas hydrate targets. This included some of the overlying “seal” stratigraphy as well as the fine detail within the gas hydrate reservoirs themselves. The core analysis program was designed to provide centimeter-scale resolution non-destructive analysis in PCATS to correlate with the relatively low resolution downhole logs. This was followed by strategic-degassing experiments to provide high-accuracy gas hydrate concentration measurements, as well as subsampling under pressure for more detailed physical, chemical and biological analysis within the Project Owner Group laboratories.

Continuous pressure coring plans were developed for the two rich gas hydrate zones of interest. The first zone cored lay in Units E and D and consisted of 11 back-to-back pressure cores each with a ~10ft stroke starting at 2369’ measured depth. The second zone cored lay in Units C and B and consisted of 13 back-to-back pressure cores each with a ~10ft stroke starting at 2873’ measured depth. Overall the pressure recovery in both zones was 100% and the overall physical recovery was 89%.

Coring in the upper E/D unit was very successful with all 11 cores recovered at high pressure, though Core HY02-06P had to be depressurized in PCATS after a full pressure X-ray image, due to a shattered liner during coring. Of the total cored interval (110.6’) the length of core recovered was 86.28’, a recovery of 78%. Core quality as shown by X-ray imaging was generally excellent and representative cores of all major lithologies were collected.

Coring in the lower C/B unit was even more successful with all 13 cores recovered at high pressure. Of the total cored interval (130’) the length of core recovered was 127.89’, a recovery of 98%. The entire section was recovered including the contact between the seal lithology and the top of gas hydrate (in Core HY02-15P) and the transition zone. Again the overall core quality as revealed by X-ray imaging was considered excellent for a rotary coring system.

Following recovery, all cores were handled and non-destructively analysed in PCATS (P-wave velocity, gamma density and X-ray imaging) before a cut plan was developed. Geotek Coring worked closely alongside personnel from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and Japan’s Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (AIST) during the operation to maintain close control over the core curation, sample handling and storage. The pressure cores were cut into sections for storage, quantitative

degassing and rapid degassing. 36 core sections of up to 1.2 m each were stored for later processing at the secondary field location at SLC. All other core material remaining in liners was frozen.

Once all the coring and initial core analysis was completed, the entire contents of the tent together with all the core samples were packed and road hauled to the secondary core analysis site at GCI in SLC, including samples taken by USGS and AIST personnel. Once all equipment had been remobilised at GCI a team from Geotek, USGS and AIST and the United States National Energy Technology Laboratory (NETL) resumed the process of core handling and analysis.

The 36 x 1.2 m storage chambers containing pressure core sections that were transported from ANS to SLC in PCATS₃₆ maintained temperature and pressure at all times, as recorded by the data loggers inside the chambers. Seven of these chambers were designated for onward transportation to AIST in Japan, five of the chambers were quantitatively degassed as a whole, and two sections were transferred directly into USGS pressure chambers. The remaining 22 core sections were transferred into PCATS and sectioned into 16 quantitative degassing samples, 34 samples for cryofreezing under pressure, six samples for transportation under pressure to USGS, two samples for transportation under pressure to NETL, seven samples for transfer under pressure into the AIST “Bio chamber”, seven samples for testing in PCATS Triaxial, and 14 subsamples which were rapidly degassed.

All conventionalized cores were split while frozen and non destructively logged on a Geotek BoxScan instrument. This provided high resolution line scan images, point sensor magnetic susceptibility and elemental XRF measurements, which will be used to enhance the sedimentological descriptions.

Five of the seven designated samples were tested in PCATS Triaxial after all other work had been completed. The final two samples are still at SLC and will likely be cryofrozen at a later convenient date. All other samples were distributed to USGS, AIST and NETL as appropriate and the archived core sections were frozen and released to USGS for transport to the core repository in Denver. The seven storage chambers designated for AIST were transferred from the 40' PTRANS₃₆ into the 20' PTRANS₁₀ and transported by road and ship to Japan whilst being maintained at low temperatures and high pressures. They were moved into the the AIST pressure core laboratory in April 2023.

Gas hydrate was detected via quantitative degassing experiments in 18 cores, with a maximum concentration of 65% methane hydrate as a percent of pore volume. Gas hydrate was undetectable in Unit E, the “seal” formation above Unit D (Cores HY02-1P & -2P). Gas hydrate concentration in Unit D ranged from 15-51% (Cores HY02-4P, -5P, -7P-9P), became undetectable in Cores HY02-9P & -10P, and appeared again at 3-5% in Core HY02-11P. Gas hydrate was present in Unit C samples (Cores HY02-12P, -13P, -15P) at concentrations of 2-12%. Gas hydrate concentrations increased in the upper portions of Unit B to 24-65% (Cores HY02-16P-19P), decreased to 18-34% as the cores became less sedimentologically uniform (Cores HY02-19P-21P), and was low but detectable (1-5%) in the remaining section (Cores HY02-21P-24P).

Pressure Coring, Core Handling & Core Analysis Report

Introduction & Project Overview

Geotek Coring Inc was contracted by ASRC Consulting & Environmental Services LLC to perform a comprehensive pressure coring and pressure core analysis program in parts of a single well on Alaska North Slope on behalf of the Japan Organization for Metals and Energy Security (JOGMEC) and the United States Department of Energy (US DOE). This program was part of a much larger program “**Extended Duration Scientific Reservoir Response Test at Site Kuparuk State 7-11-12, Prudhoe Bay Unit**” on the Alaska North Slope (ANS) which in essence had been designed to test the practicalities of effectively producing methane gas from gas hydrate reservoirs. Pressure core acquisition and analysis were a key part of the overall program, since pressure coring is the only effective way to fully characterize, test, and quantify gas hydrate in deep sediments.

The Nordic-Calista Rig 3 was used to drill the well and Geotek worked closely with the rig crew to ensure that the coring operations were conducted safely and efficiently. The well was named ‘Hydrate-02’, also known as the Geoscience Data Well (GDW). The technical program was defined by an external Project Owner Group. Geotek worked very closely with collaborating scientists from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and Japan’s Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (AIST) to ensure that that the technical and scientific goals were met safely, effectively and efficiently as practically possible.

Geotek’s program of work had two main phases. The first phase was the pressure coring, core handling and initial core analysis which was completed at the rig site on ANS. A subsequent second phase was conducted away from the rig site after all the equipment, samples and crew had relocated to the “secondary field location” at Geotek Coring’s facility in Salt Lake City, Utah. During this phase the pressure core samples were further subsampled, analysed and distributed to the various Project Owner Group laboratories.

Geotek Coring’s Overall Responsibilities & Services

Prior to the main coring operations all the Geotek equipment which was accommodated in 9 laboratory/container units. All units went via road and ferry from Salt Lake City via Seattle and Fairbanks to Deadhorse on Alaska’s North Slope (ANS). From Deadhorse they went to the rig site and were positioned inside the 100’ x 60’ heated tent to create the “Geotek village.”

During the initial coring, core handling and analysis phase of the JOGMEC/DOE Alaska ’22 expedition, Geotek Coring provided the following primary services:

- Collect pressure cores by deploying and retrieving JOGMEC’s HPTC IV (High Pressure Coring Tool) developed by Geotek Coring.
- Transfer the core from the HPTC IV autoclave into PCATS (Pressure Core Analysis and Transfer System).
- Assess the core recovery, core quality, and petrophysical nature of the core using measurements of gamma density, P-wave velocity together with X-ray imaging and X-ray computed tomographic (CT) imaging.

- Provide a detailed temperature and pressure record of each complete coring and handling process.
- Cut all cores under pressure into shorter sections, according to cut plans agreed with the AIST and USGS science teams, and transferring each subsample into shorter pressure chambers (0.35 m and 1.2 m).
- Provide equipment, supplies, support, and assistance for scientists in quantitative degassing of pressure core samples.
- Rapidly depressurize selected samples where no further handling or analysis under pressure was required.

Following the main coring operations, all the core samples and all the Geotek equipment was transported back to SLC via road. This demobilization operation created more logistical issues than had been anticipated resulting in some delays to the next phase of the operation at the secondary core analysis site at GCI in SLC. Thirty-six core samples in storage chambers were retained at full pressure and low temperature while be transported to SLC in PTRANS36. The remaining conventionalized cores were frozen while other subsamples were transported refrigerated.

During the secondary core handling and analysis phase of the JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22 expedition, Geotek Coring provided the following primary services:

- Reanalyze transported cores in PCATS as required.
- Present standard data from PCATS (X-ray images, P-wave and density profiles) to scientific representatives from DOE, JOGMEC, USGS, AIST and the United States National Energy Technology Laboratory (NETL) for sample planning.
- Cut pressure core samples from PTRANS36 according to sample plans agreed with the AIST and USGS science teams, and transferring each sample subsample into shorter pressure chambers as required. These shorter chambers included Geotek's 0.35 m storage chambers as well as pressure chambers from USGS, AIST and NETL.
- Provide equipment, supplies, support, and assistance for scientists in quantitative degassing of pressure core samples.
- Provide equipment, infrastructure and supplies to analyze 4 test samples in PCATS Triaxial.
- Freeze designated pressure core samples under pressure in liquid nitrogen, and store in liquid nitrogen until custody handover/shipping.
- Subsample and freeze conventionalized core.
- Rapidly depressurize selected samples where no further handling or analysis under pressure was required.
- Split all frozen conventionalized core longitudinally
- Image one half of each split core.
- Non-destructive analysis of all conventionalized cores, providing high resolution magnetic susceptibility, visible colour and elemental data sets (non-contractual).

During the secondary core handling and analysis phase Geotek Coring also provided the following secondary services which assisted project scientists with their own on site analysis:

- Provided equipment, supplies, and support for scientists to describe and sample frozen conventionalized core.
- Provided equipment, supplies, and support for scientists to extract pore water samples from conventionalized core.
- Provided suitable reefer space to enable AIST to use their microbiological sampling equipment.
- Packed and stored frozen core for shipment.

Following the secondary core handling and analysis phase Geotek Coring provided the following primary services:

- Transported seven core samples preserved under *in situ* pressure to AIST in Japan.
- Provided local assistance to USGS/NETL as part of their effort to ship all remaining samples (under pressure, cryo frozen, frozen and cold) to final destinations within the USA.
- Demobilized and decommissioned all equipment and facilities.
- Provided complete deep cleaning and overhaul of HPTC IV coring tools, BHA components, and the service van, readying all tools for long term storage.
- Provided complete inventory of equipment parts and spares following the field work.
- Provided recommendations for other servicing or modifications prior to the next field operation.

This report documents the pertinent operations associated with the above activities. It provides an account of the methods employed, how the cores and core samples were curated and provides tables and plots of pertinent information and data. A complete set of data is provided with this report for distribution to others in the Project Owner Group.

Figure 1. Location of Hydrate 02-Kuparuk 7-11-12 in Prudhoe Bay, ANS

Operations Overview

Mobilisation/Preparations

(30th August-26th October 2022)

All Geotek equipment was prepared at GCI facilities in SLC prior to shipping. The 9 service units left SLC on 30th August 2022 and were transported via road, ferry and train and road (Seattle, Fairbanks, Deadhorse) and were finally installed inside the Geotek village tent at the rig site on the 3rd October. Preparations continued until the rig was ready for coring operations to begin on the 27th October.

Coring operations in Hole Hydrate-02 Units E/D & Units C/B

(27th October-6th November 2022)

HY02-01P, the first pressure core in Hydrate-02, also known as the Geoscience Data Well (GDW), was recovered on the 28th October. The 24th and last pressure core, HY02-24P, was recovered on the 6th November. All 24 cores were recovered above *in situ* pressure (resulting from the pressure boost) ensuring that these cores remained well inside the gas hydrate stability zone. Core recovery was excellent. In the upper E/D unit, 11 cores progressed 110.6 ft down the hole and the length of core recovered was 86.28 ft, a recovery of 78%. In the lower C/B unit 13 cores progressed 130 ft down the hole and the length of core recovered was 127.89 ft, a recovery of 98%. Overall the recovery was 89%.

The overall core quality as shown by X-ray imaging in PCATS was considered excellent for rotary coring. One core, HY02-06P, was X-ray imaged at full pressure and then depressurised/conventionalized because the liner was broken during coring through a particularly hard interval and could not be processed under pressure after the X ray image.

Rig Site Core Processing

(7th-16th November 2022)

Both during and after the coring had been completed pressure core processing continued in PCATS where non destructive testing (gamma density, P-wave velocity and X ray imaging) enabled cut plans to be developed. The long core sections were cut in PCATS under pressure where subsections of cores were designated for storage (and subsequent transportation under pressure), quantitative degassing, or rapid degassing. This complete process was concluded on the 16th November prior to final demobilization in the tent.

Rig Site Demobilization

(17th-22nd November 2022)

Shutting down, securing, and packing some of the Geotek coring laboratories and work area had begun as soon as the coring had finished. However, the core analysis labs could not be shut down until all the PCATS and quantitative degassing work had been completed. All the Geotek equipment housed in the 9 service units were removed from the tent on the 22nd November 2022. Pressure core samples were shipped under pressure and cold (~6°C) temperatures in PTRANS36. Depressurised/conventionalized cores were shipped frozen (~-20°C). Most units were staged in Deadhorse until trucks became available for road transport to Fairbanks and beyond. On this return journey all equipment was road-hauled through Canada and onward to Salt Lake City in Utah.

Secondary Core Analysis Site Mobilization

(28th November-15th December 2022)

Remobilization at Geotek Coring facilities in SLC began on the 28th November but delays in shipping from ANS resulted in the last container (stores only) not arriving until the 23rd December. However,

enough of the facilities had been established for further core analysis work to resume with scientists from USGS, AIST and NETL by the 16th December.

Secondary Core Analysis at GCI

(16th-24th December 2022 and 3rd-27th January 2023)

The final part of the core analysis program was split into two periods that was significantly extended (compared with the initial plan) because of the Christmas/New year holidays and because Geotek offered additional core analysis capabilities. During this period, two core sections were transferred whole into USGS pressure chambers using PCATS, five sections were quantitatively degassed, and seven sections were prepared for transporting to AIST in Japan. The remaining 22 pressure core sections transported to SLC were transferred into PCATS for further sectioning into subsamples.

The total tally of subsamples cut at SLC were 16 for quantitatively degassing, 34 for cryofreezing under pressure, six for transportation under pressure to USGS, two for transportation under pressure to NETL, seven for transfer under pressure into the AIST 'Bio chamber', seven subsamples for Triax testing and 14 subsamples were rapidly degassed. Five of the seven PCATS Triaxial samples were transferred into PCATS Triaxial after all other work had been completed. All other samples have been distributed to USGS, AIST and NETL as appropriate and the archived core sections were frozen and released to USGS for transport to the USGS core repository in Denver.

All conventionalized cores were split frozen and non-destructively logged on a Geotek BoxScan instrument. This provided high resolution data line scan images, point sensor magnetic susceptibility and elemental X-ray fluorescence measurements. All samples (apart from the two untested PCATS Triaxial samples) were distributed to USGS, AIST and NETL as appropriate and the archived core sections were frozen and transported to USGS core repository in Denver.

PCATS Triaxial Testing

(14th January-17th February 2023)

Five of the seven samples collected for PCATS Triaxial were tested during this period. The other two PCATS Triaxial samples are still at SLC and will likely be cryofrozen at a later convenient date.

Pressure Core Shipping to AIST

(13th February-12th April 2023)

The seven SC120s containing the pressure cores designated for AIST were moved from the larger 40' PTRANS36 into the smaller 20' PTRANS 10 and transported by road and sea to Japan whilst being maintained at low temperatures and high pressures. They were moved into the the AIST pressure core laboratory on the 12th April 2023 after which PTRANS10 was shipped back to SLC. The high pressures on receipt and the temperature records from PTRANS10 & PTRANS36 confirmed that the samples had been maintained, for over 5 months, well inside the gas hydrate stability zone at all times from the cores first being cut at the rig site all the way through the analysis and transportation from ANS to SLC, and finally to AIST.

HPTC IV Servicing and Cleaning for Long-Term Storage

(16th-24th December 2022)

After completion of all coring operations, the HPTC IV tools and service unit were taken by truck from Prudhoe Bay to Geotek Coring headquarters in Salt Lake City, Utah. Here a complete refurbishment was undertaken and the equipment prepared for long-term storage. The objectives of this operation were threefold: first, to ensure that coring tools and equipment were cleaned and protected as best as possible

from rust and deterioration during storage; second, to assess the post-operational condition of the tools; and third, to provide an accurate inventory to allow for proper planning with regard to future operations.

Care was taken to completely clean all surfaces, using a heated high-pressure washing system. This is done to remove rust, scale, and drilling fluid from each part. After washing, water was displaced using compressed air, after which parts are left to dry in the low-humidity SLC air. After thorough drying, parts are coated using a non-toxic, lanolin-based, rust-preventive film. Particular attention was paid to long tubular parts to ensure that parts are completely dry before being packed in the coring van.

During the washing and coating process each item was visually and tactilely inspected and checked for fit, form, and function. Additionally, mating parts were joined together to ensure continued proper function of threads and connections. Coatings and inside- and outside-diameter surfaces were inspected for functional and cosmetic damage, including pitting, corrosion, burrs, and wear. Minor burrs and damage were repaired onsite whenever possible.

Items that had deteriorated significantly were marked and recommended for re-manufacture or removal from service. Finally, each item was counted and added to a final inventory. This information was assembled into a separate final report, which makes recommendations for upgrades, replacements, and the replenishment of consumable parts.

Table 1. Geotek Coring timeline : September 2022-April 2023

Key Dates	Principal Activities
30th Aug	Start of Geotek equipment transportation from SLC
17th Sept	First container unit arrives in Deadhorse
26th Sept	All 9 container units in Deadhorse
30th Sept	Geotek crew begin arriving at Kusko and Nabesca camp
3rd Oct	All 9 container units placed in rigside tent - 'Geotek Village' created
4th Oct	In tent' mobilization starts
15th Oct	Complete crew on site; 14 Geotek, 5 USGS and 1 AIST
27h Oct	Coring operations begin - deploy BHA
28th Oct	1st Pressure Core recovered HY-02-01P (Unit E/D)
29th Oct	Pressure Cores recovered HY-02-02P, 03P & 04P (Unit E/D)
30th Oct	Pressure Cores recovered HY-02-05P, 06P & 07P (Unit E/D)
31st Oct	Pressure Cores recovered HY-02-08P, 09P & 10P (Unit E/D)
1st Nov	Last Pressure Core recovered in unit E/D - HY-02-11P
3rd Nov	1st Pressure Cores recovered in Unit (C/B) HY-02-12P and 13P
4th Nov	Pressure Cores recovered in Unit (C/B) HY-02-14P, 15P, 16P & 17P
5th Nov	Pressure Cores recovered in Unit (C/B) HY-02-18P, 19P, 20P & 21P
6th Nov	Last Pressure Cores recovered in Unit (C/B) HY-02-22P, 23P & 24P
7th Nov	Continue core processing and start coring cleanup / demob activities
14th Nov	Core processing completed in PCATS
16th Nov	All core processing completed - demob continues
22nd Nov	Geotek Village vacated, PTRANS36 loaded and left Deadhorse.
28th Nov	Mobilization at SLC begins
6th Dec	Final container unit leaves Deadhorse
16th Dec	First core section processed in PCATS
23rd Dec	Final container (stores) arrives at SLC
24th Dec	Final day of core analysis prior to pause period.
3 Jan	Core analysis resumes
27 Jan	All core analysis completed (apart from TRIAX)
13 Feb	7 AIST samples shipped in PTRANS10
17 Feb	PCATS TRIAX testing completed
12 April	7 samples arrived at temperature and under pressure at AIST, Japan

Geotek Village Layout in the tent at rig site, ANS

Geotek mobilized the following major infrastructure for the JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22 operation: JOGMEC 20' HPTC IV tool service container - 'CORING', PCATS (40' and 20') DNV laboratory combination, a 20' DNV SERVICES frame, a 20' DNV refrigerated container for DEGASSING pressure cores, a 40' G26 LAB container for data processing and core curation and geochemistry, a 40' PTRANS container unit, a 20' STORES unit, and a 20' FREEZER sample container.

The positions of the laboratories in the 100' x 60' Geotek Village are shown in Figure 2. The containers were placed on top of plywood sheets that were themselves laid on top of rig mats, which covered the gravel pad. Electric power, water, and heat (at each corner of the tent) were provided by ASRC.

It should be noted that this tent/village arrangement worked exceptionally well for the complex work being undertaken the many people in the ANS environment.

Figure 2. Layout of all the working units/laboratories in the tented Geotek Village

HPTC IV Pressure Coring Equipment

Coring Tools

HPTC IV Pressure Coring Tools

The High Pressure/Temperature Corer, Mk IV (HPTC IV) is a wireline coring system designed to recover 53 mm diameter cores at lengths up to 3.5 meters and at full in-situ pressure (up to 35 MPa).

HPTC IV was developed and modified from a version of the Pressure Temperature Coring Sampler (PTCS) that was developed and used successfully to recover methane-hydrate-bearing cores during the Tokai-oki Kumana-nada operations offshore Japan in 2003-2004. One of the key developments was to ensure the new HPTC tools were fully compatible with the Geotek Coring Pressure Core Analysis and Transfer System (PCATS) enabling the cores to be analysed and sampled in detail at full *in situ* conditions.

The HPTC IV is a rotary coring system in a ‘face bit’ configuration which latches into the bottom-hole assembly (BHA). An internal bearing isolates the rotation of the core liner from the BHA as it spins in the borehole. Core material is cut during coring and passes through the central aperture in the main bit, through a protective core shoe on the HPTC IV and into a plastic core liner.

The only significant difference between the HPTC III last used in 2018 and the current HPTC IV are 1) a new bearing arrangement which provides a more freely rotating inner core barrel, decoupled from the BHA, that assists with improving core quality and 2) an improved, more robust unlatching spring mechanism which improves the reliability of the pressure boost mechanism.

At the end of each coring interval (normally 10 ft during this expedition) a wireline pulling tool was lowered and latched into the HPTC IV, actuating the mechanisms that pull the core sample into the sealed lower outer barrel. During this pulling process the ball valve closes, sealing the lower outer barrel from the bottom, and a pressure boost is triggered from a nitrogen-charged pressure control section above the sample.

Upon actuation, the HPTC IV unlatches from the BHA and is pulled to the rig floor, where it is transferred to a glycol-chilled vertical water-filled shuck for temperature stabilization. After a period of at least 30 minutes, the complete tool was moved to the coring service unit where the upper latching and pressure control section assemblies were removed. Autoclave pressure was recorded at this stage and the tool was prepared for transfer to PCATS. The sample was then stored in a glycol-chilled horizontal water bath if necessary until it was removed to PCATS for transfer and analysis.

Figure 3. HPTC IV pressure coring tool

Solid model cross section of HPTC inside the BHA (horizontally exaggerated) showing internal mechanisms

Ancillary Coring Equipment

HPTC IV Coring Service Van

This Alaskan operation was the first work performed using the new DNV-rated JOGMEC 20' ISO coring service van. It was located a short distance from the rig inside the tented Geotek Village. The unit contains all the necessary tools, test equipment and supplies for a continuous 24 hr operation. Most importantly it has an extending gantry that enables the heavy coring tools to be handled both inside and immediately outside the unit which minimises the need to use an external crane for small local movements.

Ergonomics, comfort, and durability of the new unit were excellent. Additionally, the previous wall-mounted bank of high pressure water and nitrogen pumps were replaced with a new manifold system, providing a greater degree of safety and ease of use for filling, testing, and troubleshooting HPTC components. Since 2019, Geotek Coring has discontinued use of the Honeywell pressure transducer system to check pressure of coring tools as they are brought up-hole. In place of the transducer system, digital pressure gauges are used to directly read the internal pressure of the autoclave. Comparison with the pressure-temperature data from the Star-Oddi DST recorders has shown this technique to be accurate, as well as inherently simpler and less error-prone than the transducer system used previously.

Figure 4. HPTC IV coring service van and outside preparation area

HPTC IV coring tool being handled using overhead crane gantry outside the coring service van.

BHA and Center Bit

The Bottom Hole Assembly (BHA) is a HPTC IIV custom built light weight system with a top landing shoulder and recess for the tool latching mechanism. It uses a custom face bit configured 10 5/8" polycrystalline diamond cutting bit. Prior to use each HPTC IV coring tool undergoes a fit test/space-out test on the rig floor. The space-out is adjusted as necessary to ensure that the nose of the tool sits correctly inside the main coring bit. A compatible center bit was used to drill out the hole when not coring. This center bit uses a top latch with a bit-driven drive.

Cold Shuck/Bath and Glycol Chillers

To ensure that the cores are kept in the proper temperature range after they are returned to the rig floor and during handling in the Geotek Village, glycol-chilled, water-filled constant-temperature baths are used. These are a significant improvement on the ice-filled containers that have been used previously. A vertical shuck is used on the rig floor for maintaining the temperature of the tool as soon as it is removed from the pipe and a horizontal bath is used for storage outside the coring service van.

Pressure Core Handling and Analysis Equipment

Pressure Core Analysis and Transfer System: PCATS

PCATS, the Pressure Core Analysis & Transfer System, is designed to manipulate and analyze pressure cores at *in situ* pressures. Pressure cores can be transferred into PCATS without releasing pressure, measurements made on the cores, and the cores can be cut into sections and moved into storage or analysis pressure vessels, all under *in situ* pressures and temperatures (Table 2). This fully containerised system is based on standard ISO containers with DNV 2.7-1 classification, enabling the system to be easily shipped to mobilization ports and lifted off and on offshore platforms and drilling vessel as required.

PCATS itself (Fig. 5 below) and much of the control infrastructure, is housed in the 40-foot air-conditioned laboratory container (PCATS11). The refrigerated right-hand container (PCATS8) enables the corer autoclave to be attached to PCATS through an opening between the central and right-hand containers. This right-hand unit is also used as temporary storage for cores recovered and held in long 3.5 m pressure storage chambers.

Figure 5. Schematic diagrams of PCATS

Above: Drawing to scale of PCATS inside the two laboratory containers. Below: Conceptual diagram of PCATS, showing corresponding parts on drawing (not to scale).

<i>Maximum core length accepted</i>	3.5 m
<i>Maximum core liner diameter accepted</i>	63 mm (OD)
<i>Temperature control</i>	4-18°C
<i>Pressure control</i>	0-35 MPa
<i>Minimum length of cut sample</i>	10 cm
<i>X-ray resolution</i>	100-150 µm pixel size
<i>Gamma density & P-wave velocity spatial resolution</i>	0.5 cm

Table 2. General PCATS specifications

PCATS Pressure & Temperature Control Systems

Pressure containment in PCATS is through the use of modular steel, titanium and high-tensile aluminum pressure vessels and components. These vessels are rated to a minimum working pressure of 350 bar and joined together at their end flanges with a quick-clamp system where frequent assembly and disassembly is required. Ball valves (65 mm ID) are incorporated into PCATS to isolate the different parts of the system while retaining space for the maximum size of core (63 mm OD).

Pressure is maintained inside PCATS hydraulically, using fresh water as the pressurizing fluid. During this expedition, cesium chloride was added to the PCATS water as a tracer for those scientists interested in quantifying the potential contamination of the samples from this water that surrounds the core in PCATS and during storage. High-pressure hoses connect to a number of points within the system, providing alternate pathways for fluid flow as core is moved within PCATS. The total volume of PCATS without a core is 60- 70 litres. The system is filled and drained with electric high flow, low pressure pumps and pressurised with compressed-air-driven high-pressure pumps. Pressure is monitored with a series of digital and analog pressure gauges.

Temperature control from 4°C to 18°C is provided through refrigeration and circulation of the pressurizing fluid. The two-stage refrigeration unit uses a chilled glycol chiller unit to cool the circulating, high-pressure water in a custom heat exchanger. Each pressure chamber of PCATS is insulated to allow the PCATS central control laboratory to be maintained at room temperature.

PCATS Core Motion Assemblies

Cores are moved inside PCATS using a linear manipulator and a rotator system. Both the manipulator and the rotator are computer-controlled, servo-motor-driven units that together provide precise linear (± 0.1 mm) and rotational ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) positional control for the core with a software interface (Fig. 6). The manipulator mechanism consists of a long ball-screw providing the rectilinear push and pull motion of the core along the length of the PCATS (over 4 metres of linear motion). Rotation of the core is provided by a motor-driven ring which grips the core while allowing the core to move freely along the linear axis using an assembly of rollers. The rotation provides the user with the ability to cut the cores at precisely defined intervals and enables X-ray CT scans to be performed by precision rotating of the core.

Figure 6. Interior of central PCATS main laboratory

This image shows the main thermally jacketed manipulator housing of PCATS, the central hydraulic manifold system, and the computer control screens.

At the interface with the core autoclave, the manipulator has a customized latching/pulling tool for the HPTC IV autoclave. This pulling tool connects to the mechanical assembly attached to the top of each core (the core plug); the core plug is then mechanically released from the autoclave, allowing the core to be retracted into PCATS. A custom grabber is attached to the manipulator to reach inside the storage chambers to grab and retract cores which have previously been cut and stored.

PCATS Core Cutting Assembly

The core can be cut at a precise location to create subsamples using a combination pipe cutter and guillotine tool. The operation of the core cutter on the core liner is similar to a pipe cutter with a rolling cutting disk. The cutter is pressure-balanced and advanced under manual control across the core, while the core is rotating, enabling the operator to feel the cutting wheel moving through the core liner. Additional information on the cutting process is provided by live graphs of torque data from the motor. Once the core liner has been parted, the thin stainless steel of the guillotine is used to slice through the sediment. The overall quality of the cuts through the liner are generally excellent, with little cracking or burring at the edges. However, the quality of cuts through the sediment depend on the sediment properties. Through competent, homogenous softer material the cuts are sharp, clean, and perpendicular to the liner, but in hard sands cleavage along bedding planes may occur.

PCATS Multi-Sensor Non-Destructive Measurements

The automated non-destructive analysis systems built into PCATS are similar to those on the Geotek Multi-Sensor Core Loggers (MSCL) and X-ray imaging systems (MSCL-XCT), consisting of a gamma density measurement system, a P-wave velocity measurement system, and an X-ray imaging system, all within or “looking through” a section of aluminum pressure chamber. All sensors are controlled from a central computer running a core data acquisition and analysis program.

Gamma density is calculated from the attenuation of a collimated beam of monochromatic photons from a nominal 10 mCi (370 MBq) ^{137}Cs source. The source is active enough to penetrate both the core and the aluminum pressure housing (wall thickness of 11 mm), and is shielded in lead with a rotating lead shutter (5mm diameter collimator). The Tl-doped NaI detector is calibrated to record only the primary energy emitted by the ^{137}Cs source (662 keV), which ensures that the beam attenuation through scattering is accurately reported. Calibration of gamma attenuation to gamma density, and from there to bulk density, relies on a set of standards of known average bulk density. The standards of choice for calibration of gamma attenuation to gamma density in standard sediments (water-saturated aluminosilicates) are aluminium and water of known thicknesses inside core liner. This results in similar electron density in the calibration pieces and the core, allowing gamma density and bulk density to track each other with high precision, though the resultant data are still technically reported as “gamma density” rather than “bulk density.” The source, detector, and calibration protocols are the same as are used with Multi-Sensor Core Logger (MSCL) systems in laboratories and on research vessels around the world.

Ultrasonic P-wave velocity is measured with a pulse transmission technique. The two 500 kHz acoustic transducers are mounted inside the aluminium pressure housing, perpendicular to the core axis. The transducers are also perpendicular to but co-located along the core with the gamma ray beam. The P-wave velocity is calculated from the pulse travel time across the core material and the internal diameter of the core liner ultrasonic velocity with a precision of $\pm 1.5 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and an accuracy of approximately $\pm 5 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The pulse travel time across the core material is calculated by subtracting the travel time offset, which is the time required for the pulse to transit the core liner as well as the pressurizing fluid between the transducers and the core liner at a given temperature. Temperature is monitored constantly in PCATS, so the appropriate travel time offset can always be applied.

X-ray images are collected using a variable intensity, microfocal X-ray source and a digital flat-panel detector. The source can provide energies up to 130 keV. The combination of microfocal source and high resolution flat-panel detector enables images to be collected with typical spatial resolutions of 100-150 microns. To collect linear X-rays of core larger than the detector, the core analysis program takes a continuous image of the entire core in a synchronised line-scan mode of operation. As the line scan data is collected, images can also be collected for X-ray computed laminography (CL) reconstruction. To collect data for X-ray CT reconstruction, the core analysis program rotates the core while collecting images at regular intervals along the core (typically 6cm). Reconstructions are generated using appropriate algorithms suitable for rotational scans in a cone beam. To help ensure that the core remains aligned with the axis of rotation, mechanical centralizers are used on either side of the X-ray detector when possible. Note that in all X-ray images provided by Geotek, dense objects which obscure the X-ray beam are dark.

Core Analysis Ancillary Equipment

Chambers for Core Storage Under Pressure

Pressure storage chambers compatible with PCATS allow cores to be stored, both short-term and long-term. These chambers are made using the same materials, large-diameter ball valves, and flanges as the main body of PCATS.

Geotek provided the following pressure storage vessels on the JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22 expedition:

- a) 14 x SC350 chambers, each of which accepts an entire 3.5-meter-long core. These chambers were used as logging chambers and temporary storage chambers during the coring part of the program.
- b) 7 x SC035 chambers, which accept up to 35 cm samples which were used as temporary storage for quantitative degassing samples and samples used for pressurized cryofreezing.
- c) 42 x SC125 chambers, which were used for quantitative degassing and shipping vessels from ANS back to SLC in PTRANS36.

Degassing Laboratory

Quantitative depressurization/degassing experiments allow gas evolved from pressure core sections when depressurized to be collected for the calculation of methane hydrate concentration from methane mass balance. Quantitative degassing experiments are an important component of pressure core analysis providing the most accurate method of estimating gas hydrate concentration within any given sample.

The Geotek Coring degassing reefer container laboratory houses four depressurization stations with manifolds and gas collections systems enabling multiple samples to be degassed simultaneously.

Each manifold and degassing station contains both a “bubbling chamber” and a “gas chamber” for collecting and measuring the volume of gas expelled. The bubbling chamber consists of an inverted graduated cylinder in a water column that can collect gas volumes of up to 2L. Gas chambers are constructed of a transparent polycarbonate cylinder that can collect gas samples up to 4 litres at pressures up to 1 MPa. In practice it is not normal to exceed 0.5 MPa and therefore the volume of gas from the gas chamber can be up to 20L at atmospheric pressure. The gas chamber was not used during the JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22 expedition.

Figure 7. Degassing / depressurization laboratory

Four 1.2 m chambers are shown occupying the locations on the four degassing stations where gasses are collected to determine the concentration of gas hydrate in core sections.

Pressure Cryofreeze Cell

As had been done on a number of previous expeditions, we used the Geotek pressure cryofreeze chamber, which cryofreezes the samples in liquid nitrogen while the pressure core samples are still at 10 MPa. Only after the sample is cryofrozen is the pressure released. With this technique the sample is much less disturbed and all the gas hydrate and gas is preserved for later analysis. This process was only conducted on samples cut in SLC.

This pressure cryofreezing technique involves cutting a suitable subsample (normally 20-25 cm in length) in PCATS and transferring it to a 0.35 m sample storage chamber in the same way as other pressure core subsamples are taken. To prevent the sample becoming stuck in the chamber a brass weight is inserted in the chamber above the sample, prior to sample transfer, to ensure the sample falls through the ball valve and into the liquid nitrogen. The water surrounding the sample is replaced with high pressure nitrogen (10 MPa) before the chamber is connected to the pressure cryofreeze cell containing liquid nitrogen. Once the lower chamber is filled with nitrogen gas at 10 MPa and equalized with the sample in the chamber, the main ball valve is opened allowing the sample to fall into the liquid nitrogen. As the liquid nitrogen boils off, the pressure is vented to maintain the pressure at 10 MPa. After about two minutes the sample is completely cryofrozen and the pressure is released. The frozen sample is removed from the liquid nitrogen and stored in liquid nitrogen dewars.

Conventionalized Core Analysis & Equipment

Core Splitter

A modified table saw with a diamond-tipped blade was used to laterally split all the frozen conventionalized core sections in their plastic liner, prior to description and measurement. The customized core guide mechanism enabled this process to be carried out safely and efficiently.

BoxScan Analysis Platform

A Geotek BoxScan system was used to image the core at a 50µm pixel resolution using a line-scan imaging system. The imaging took place on the archive half of each core section after it had been cleaned by USGS sedimentologists. The BoxScan instrument available on site also had other non-contractual sensors fitted, including an Olympus Vanta-M X-ray fluorescence spectrometer and a Bartington magnetic susceptibility point sensor and meter.

Figure 8. BoxScan Imaging and Measurement Platform

BoxScan shown with linescan camera, Vanta XRF, magnetic susceptibility sensor, 3D laser scanner, and visible/infrared spectrometer; close-up of BoxScan sensor assembly.

Pressure Core Handling / Testing Overview

The HPTC IV was the only pressure coring tool used on Expedition JOGMEC/DOE Alaska '22, with four autoclave assemblies available. PCATS was used to remove all the cores from the HPTC autoclave, perform non-destructive testing under pressure (X-ray imaging, P wave velocity and gamma density measurements), and cut samples for further work on the vessel (rapid and quantitative degassing and samples for storage and transportation to SLC).

All samples that were “conventionalized” by rapid or quantitative degassing were provided to the USGS and AIST scientists for any appropriate subsampling before being frozen and shipped back to SLC. Figure 9 provides a flow chart illustrating the generalised flow of cores and core samples during and after the expedition at the rig site.

Figure 9. Pressure core handling flow chart at the rig site

HPTC IV Pressure Coring Operations

HPTC IV Tool Preparation

Preparation of the HPTC IV required the inspection, re-assembly, resetting, and testing of three main segments: the latch assembly, the pressure control section, and the lower outer barrel (or autoclave)

assembly. Each segment must be completely inspected and tested prior to deployment to ensure proper function of the final assembly. Particular attention was given to consumable seals, which were changed prior to each coring run.

To ensure the correct downhole operation, the greatest care was exercised in the assembly of HPTC IV coring tools. To this end, Geotek Coring assembly teams built the tools to a strict standard using proprietary assembly animations, enabling the assembly of each tool with near 100% quality assurance. During preparation, the pressure control section was charged with nitrogen to 37-40 MPa. Boost applied to the core sample was controlled by a built-in pressure regulator which was set to a predetermined pressure decided in consultation with the customer and scientific advisors to ensure stability of hydrate-bearing samples. During this expedition a boost pressure of ~15 MPa was used.

The plastic core liner was prepared with a basket-style core catcher for the first few cores after which it was changed to a flapper style catcher to ensure that no core was lost during recovery. A pressure/temperature data logger (Star-Oddi Data Storage Tag: DST) was always used in the core plug and an additional one was used in a rabbit when the basket catchers were used.

Core Acquisition with the HPTC IV

The JOGMEC HPTC IV equipment included four lower autoclave sections, four pressure sections, and four upper (latch) assemblies. These quantities allowed for a continuous cycling of coring tools from points of service and operation at the service van, drill floor, and PCATS, but do not preclude delays due to core processing time.

Prior to drilling a coring interval, a fully-assembled HPTC IV was delivered to the rig floor and placed directly into the drill pipe at rig floor level. A wireline running tool was inserted into the upper latch, after which the chain-slung lifting clamp was removed and the tool deployed down the string to the BHA. After latching into the BHA, the running tool was released and returned to the surface, where it was changed out for the wireline pulling tool. The pulling tool was then lowered into the hole and held at a depth just above the BHA until core cutting was complete.

At this point, with the HPTC IV latched into the BHA and the pulling tool pre-positioned just above, weight on bit was applied and the core cutting process commenced. Drilling parameters were dependent on formation and well control factors and can be found in the HPTC run reports.

When the desired coring end depth was reached, the BHA (along with the HPTC IV) were lifted off the bottom in preparation for retrieval with the wireline coring tool. As the pulling tool was lifted it engaged the inner assemblies of the tool: retracting the core above the ball valve, closing the ball, and actuating the pressure control section as described above). The outer latch was then disengaged, releasing the entire HPTC IV assembly from the BHA. At this point, with the inner latch fully retracted, the tool was fully sealed and boosted to the regulator's set pressure.

The wireline trip from BHA to rig floor was made as quickly and as safely possible, in order to limit exposure of the sample to warmer temperatures higher in the water column. Upon arrival to the surface, the tool was removed from the drill string and immersed in a glycol-cooled vertical water shuck, where it is left for at least 30 minutes.

HPTC Autoclave Disconnection and Delivery to PCATS

After the HPTC IV was chilled in the vertical cold shuck (minimum time 30 mins), it was transferred to the coring service unit via the rig elevator and the loader. The pressure was measured, the pressure and latching sections were removed and the autoclave prepared for transfer to PCATS (which included installing a connector flange at the crossover sub). When these preparations were complete, the autoclave was placed in the horizontal cold bath immediately outside the service unit until it could be transferred to

PCATS. For the transfer, the autoclave was transferred to the PCATS laboratory using the fork lift, where it could be stored or connected directly to PCATS for analysis. Following transfer into PCATS the autoclave was returned to the Coring Service Van for redressing/preparations for the next core.

Figure 10. The HPTC IV between tent and rig

The HPTC IV autoclave was moved to and from the rig elevator into the tent and the core service van using a loading vehicle.

Pressure Boost After Coring

The pressure boost from the pressure section should ideally occur just before the tool is unlatched from the BHA. On previous expeditions the pressure data from downhole pressure-temperature recorders showed that this boost occurred after the core was lifted from the BHA and in some cases it occurred when the tool was significantly above the BHA on its wire line return to the surface. Consequently, in the past full sealing and pressure boost was *not* accomplished until the tool had travelled some distance up the drill string on its return trip to the surface. Modifications of the over-travel spring mechanism prior to this expedition resulted in an improved pressure boost performance, where the pressure boost occurred more often prior to unlatching.

Pressure & Temperature Monitoring of Cores During Coring and Core Handling

All 24 HPTC IV coring runs were fitted with a pressure-temperature sensor (Star-Oddi DST) to record the pressure-temperature history of each pressure core. This was housed in the core plug (“IT” plug) in the autoclave. A second pressure-temperature sensor was used as a back up in the core follower or “rabbit” which moves up the inside of the core liner as the core advances. The rabbit can only be deployed when a sprung finger catcher is used; however, for the bulk of the deployments used a flapper catcher, and no rabbit DST was available. The DST recorders were set to collect data every five seconds.

HY02-09P Plug PT record 31 Oct 2022

HY02-09P Plug P vs T

Figure 11. Illustrative pressure-temperature record

Above: the temperature and pressure for each core deployment was plotted vs time showing the different phases of the coring operation. Below: plot showing the temperature pressure loci with respect to the methane hydrate stability curve illustrating that the core remained inside methane hydrate stability.

PCATS Operations

Schematics of Overall PCATS Operations

Figure 12. Diagrams of PCATS operations: part 1

Diagrams of standard PCATS operations. PCATS is prepared for connection to corer autoclave, retrieves core from the corer autoclave and core is examined in X-ray. PCATS collects nondestructive data on core. PCATS cuts core free of corer plug and stores core.

Figure 13. Diagrams of PCATS operations: part 2

Diagrams of standard PCATS operations, continued. PCATS retrieves core from storage chamber, PCATS collects further nondestructive data on core (e.g., X-ray CT measurements), PCATS cuts samples from core, and documents samples with X-ray images. PCATS transfers samples into 0.35 or 1.2 m storage chambers for storage or further testing.

Core Transfer into PCATS and Preliminary Core Measurements

Prior to accepting an HPTC IV core, the core latching/pulling tool was attached to the PCATS manipulator rod. PCATS was filled with fresh water including a cesium chloride tracer, bled of air, and pressurized to 15 MPa. A temperature of between 6 °C and 8 °C was maintained in PCATS throughout the handling and analysis.

The autoclave was moved into PCATS 11 through the personnel door using the internal hoist. The top of the autoclave was checked for debris, aligned, and then pushed onto the sealing ring and clamped securely in place using the quick-clamp. The joint between PCATS and the autoclave was filled with water and bled of air before it was pressure equalized with PCATS. The port on the transfer barrel at the bottom of the autoclave was opened and pressurized from the main manifold. After equalizing the complete system and increasing the pressure to 15 MPa, the main PCATS ball valve was opened and latching commenced. The manipulator and latching tool were moved to the latch point where audible “clicks” indicated that the grabber was moving over the threaded plug. The pressures were then balanced and the hydraulic lock released before withdrawing the manipulator attached to the core into PCATS. Latching was confirmed by viewing the core plug in the live X-ray image and then the core liner itself. To ensure that measurements were orientated correctly the machined ‘dimples’ in the core liner were orientated away from the user, at the top edge of the X-ray image, and defined as 0°.

Once orientated and aligned, an X-ray radiograph was collected over the entire core as it was pulled from the autoclave into PCATS. This provided an X ray image and the curatorial length of the core. At this stage the core was isolated in PCATS and the autoclave depressurised, removed from PCATS and returned to the HPTC service van for redressing.

An empty 3.5 m storage chamber was connected to PCATS, filled with water, pressurized, and equalized with PCATS. This enabled the core to be cut from the HPTC IV core plug and transferred to the 3.5 m storage chamber. The core in the 3.5 m storage chamber was temporarily stored in PCATS8 while the core plug was removed from PCATS and the pressure-temperature sensor removed for reading. The core plug itself was returned with the autoclave to the HPTC service van for redressing.

Secondary Core Measurements

All but one of the 24 pressure cores retrieved during the expedition in PCATS were then returned to PCATS for secondary measurements which consisted of a secondary X-ray image at 90° to the first image and a detailed P-wave velocity and gamma density log at 1 cm intervals. The only core not scanned for a second time and subsampled was Core HY02-06P that had a badly cracked liner. This core had to be depressurised in PCATS and conventionalised.

X-ray CT data was collected for each of the cores. However, the quality of the CT reconstructions was adversely impacted by the dense, oil-based drilling mud, which moved and flowed as the core rotated, as well as by rotation of some of the core pieces within the liner. All the CT reconstructions have been provided, but in many cases the CL (computed laminography) data is superior in quality. A filter applied to the CL data set enhances the density contrasts.

Core Cutting into Sections

At the rig site following the initial X-ray radiography and the P-wave velocity and gamma density scans, the data was plotted for evaluation and cut plan generation, with the help and approval of the science team. In each cut plan it was decided where the cuts in PCATS should be made and how each cut section should be treated as follows:

- a) **Rapid degassing.** This was normally reserved for the bottom of the cores that were inside the core catcher (CC). These samples were sent directly to the science team for sampling and curation.

- b) **Quantitative degassing.** These samples were cut and held in either 1.2 m or 0.35 m SCs and degassed on one of the manifolds in the degassing laboratory container. These samples, once depressurized and removed from the chambers, were conventionalized and frozen ready for transport back to SLC.
- c) **Pressurized storage.** These samples were cut and put directly into 1.2 m storage chambers for subsequent shipping to SLC using PTRANS36.
- Once the pressure core sections had arrived at the Secondary Core Analysis location at GCI in SLC, 22 of those sections were further subsampled with the following categories:
- a) **Rapid degassing.** as above
- b) **Quantitative degassing.** as above
- c) **Pressurised storage.** These samples were cut and put directly into 1.2 m or 0.35 m storage chambers supplied by USGS and NETL.
- d) **Bio.** These samples were cut at 20cm and transferred directly into the pressurized AIST biosampling chamber.
- e) **Cryofreezing.** These samples were normally cut at 25 cm long and stored briefly in 0.35 m SCs before being cryofrozen 10 MPa.
- f) **PCATS Triaxial.** These samples were normally cut at 11 cm long and transferred into the dedicated transfer cells.

Figure 14. Pressure core and conventionalized core handling flow chart at SLC

HY02-14P, 2893.1ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

Figure 15. Illustrative PCATS cut plan

The cut plan for each core was based on the X-ray imaging and the P-wave velocity and gamma density scans. Once all the cut sections had been completed a final summary plot was made showing all cuts in PCATS.

Returning Stored Core to PCATS

Before retrieving a stored core, the liner grabbing tool was attached to the PCATS manipulator and PCATS was filled, bled of air, and brought to a working pressure of 20 MPa. A 3.5-meter-long storage chamber containing core was attached to PCATS and pressure-balanced as above before opening both ball valves. The manipulator with the liner grabbing tool was pushed onto the previously cut end of the liner.

Grabber control was achieved using a combination of positional ‘dead reckoning’ and by monitoring the torque on the translational motor. Once the grab position was reached, the core was gently retracted into PCATS. Successful core grabbing was confirmed physically in the storage chamber ball valve and visually in the live X-ray monitor.

Cutting and Transferring Samples to Storage Chambers

A subsample cutting plan for each core was developed either at the rig site or at SLC using the PCATS log data, allocating samples appropriately for the different subsequent experiments.

Using the nondestructive data, the subsample cutting plan was refined to the nearest centimeter. Cut positions were located precisely by comparing the live X-ray image with the original stored image, as well as using the live P-wave velocity measurement. Some small adjustments were made to the calculated cut depths when core material had moved inside the liner. The procedures used for each cut are similar to the previous description of PCATS cutting. Cuts were made sequentially from the bottom of the core. Cutting operations for each sample took about 1 hour. When PCATS was emptied after the core cutting was completed, a water sample was taken for sodium fluoride analysis.

Rapid Depressurization of Samples

Normally the core catcher or other short sections were rapidly depressurized between two ball valves in PCATS. This enabled the core catcher to be easily captured and the sediment sampled by the rig site science team. The rapid depressurization chamber or ball valve space was depressurized with no attempt to capture gas.

Quantitative Degassing for Gas Hydrate Saturation Calculations

Quantitative degassing samples were placed in either 0.35 m or 1.2 m storage chambers with cylindrical plastic spacers to minimize water volume. After bleeding and preparing the manifold and gas collection chambers, the storage chambers were connected to the depressurization station. All depressurizations started at ~20 MPa and measured the volume of liquid (water) as well as the volume of gas expelled throughout the experiment. Samples were initially quickly depressurized to just above methane hydrate stability, about 6 MPa at 6-8°C (temperature of the laboratory). Pressure was then slowly reduced in incremental steps allowing the hydrate to dissociate at each step to form gas in the chambers which was then released through the manifold. At the end of the experiment, the total amount of water forced from the chamber was added to the last gas increment as this was an accurate assessment of the gas remaining inside the chamber which could not escape.

Gas samples were collected throughout all degassing experiments in syringes. The GC analysis of these samples enabled the total amount of methane gas to be calculated and together with the physical measurements on the core the gas hydrate concentration was calculated.

HY02-17P-4

Figure 16. Illustrative plot of degassing data

The data for each degassing was plotted showing the evolution of gas (and water) with pressure. Note that most of the gas is released at 5 MPa and then subsequently expands.

The pore volume was calculated from gamma density and core volume. Thermodynamic equilibrium was assumed and the calculation was performed after Collett et al., 2008. The calculated concentration of methane was compared to predicted methane saturation for *in situ* conditions (Tishchenko et al., 2005); the *in situ* temperatures and salinities were provided by USGS and *in situ* pressures were assumed to be hydrostatic. Any methane present beyond dissolved methane saturation (excess methane) was assumed to be in a methane hydrate phase or a free methane gas phase, depending on the calculated thermodynamic phase boundaries. Structure I methane hydrate and full cage occupancy was assumed for these calculations.

Following the complete degassing process the core sections were carefully removed from the storage chambers in their liners, marked and labelled and transferred to the USGS and AIST science team as “conventionalized core” for curation and further routine analysis.

Collett et al. (Collett, T., Riedel, M., Cochran, J., Boswell, R., Presley, J., Kumar, P., Sathe, A., Sethi, A., Lall, M., Siball, V., the NGHP Expedition 01 Scientific Party, 2008. Indian National Gas Hydrate Program Expedition 01. Initial Report: Prepared by the U.S. Geological Survey. Directorate General of Hydrocarbons, Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas (India), 1 DVD).

Tishchenko, P., Hensen, C., Wallmann, K., Wong, C.S., 2005. Calculation of the stability and solubility of methane hydrate in seawater. *Chemical Geology* 219, 37-52.

LN₂ Cryofreezing of Gas Hydrate Cores at Pressure

The pressure cryofreeze cell described above was used to preserve 34 samples from this expedition. Operations took place in the GCI facilities where an air hoist was used to elevate the storage chamber while the liquid nitrogen was poured in the lower freeze chamber. Once the sample had been frozen and extracted it was oriented and given to USGS personnel for curation and storage in LN₂ dewars for transportation to USGS laboratories.

Figure 17. Preparing pressure core for cryofreezing

The water surrounding the sample is replaced by high pressure nitrogen gas prior to the transfer to LN₂. The operation took place inside the Geotek facility at SLC.

Core Splitting, Imaging, & Bonus Measurements

In SLC, all frozen conventionalized core was split into archive and working halves using the purpose-built rotary saw splitter. The archive half was cleaned by the USGS sedimentologists before being imaged using a line-scan camera on the Geotek BoxScan. ‘Bonus data’ (non-contractual) was collected on the archive half of the core. XRF elemental analyses and magnetic susceptibility point measurements were made at 1 cm intervals on all samples. Selected samples had the same measurements made at 0.2 cm intervals. XRF measurements used the “Geochem” profile and were 30 seconds each beam; magnetic susceptibility measurements integrated for 5 seconds.

Electronic Data

0. Report

Contains this report as a PDF, with and without the data appendixes.

1. Curation and summary

Contains the core summary sheets, showing all cuts in PCATS along with nondestructive data and gas hydrate concentration, as PDFs, as well as the inventory of cores and sections & pieces.

2. HPTC deployment

Contains logsheets for each coring tool run (PDF) and data from Star-Oddi DST pressure-temperature recorders. Pressure-temperature data is included as raw data (TXT) as well as graphically (PDF).

3. PCATS data

Contains gamma density & P-wave data and X-ray data collected in PCATS. Gamma density and P-wave data is presented in a spreadsheet (XLSX). The X-ray data consists of raw data (16-bit X-ray TIFFs with companion XML file), 8-bit X-ray images with a ruler added (JPG), and horizontally exaggerated core reports (PDF). X-ray radiographs of cut ends (TIFFs) are also provided. All X-ray images are “positive”; dense objects that obscure the X-ray are dark.

X-ray images include standard radiographs, CL slab images, and CT slab images. As mentioned in the text, the CL reconstructions are in many cases superior in quality to the CT reconstructions. The rulers applied to CT reconstructions may have some offsets compared to radiographs and CL images. Complete CT data is available on request (1 TB). As the CT data was impacted by artifacts, the raw rotational data is also provided as movies (AVI). Raw data is also available on request (1 TB).

4. Q degas data

Quantitative degassing and gas hydrate saturation data. Pressure vs. time records for each degassing (CSV), Q degas logsheet scans (PDF), tables for each Q degas experiment (PDF), graphs of pressure vs. volume for each Q degas experiment (PDF). A table of gas hydrate saturation and values required to calculate gas hydrate saturation is also included (XLSX).

5. Split-core data

Images of split-core archive half and data collected on archive half. Images are 16-bit TIFFs with companion XML file, 8-bit images with a ruler added (JPG), and horizontally exaggerated core reports (PDF). XRF elemental analysis and magnetic susceptibility measurements are in CSV files.

6. PCATS Triaxial reports

PDF reports containing plots of reconsolidation vs time, resonant column frequency response, pressure differential over time with fluid flow, and elastic parameters & permeability vs effective stress.

Explanation of Figures & Tables in Appendixes

Tables (Appendixes A & B)

List of cores with data pertinent to each core (**Appendix A**).

List of samples cut from cores in PCATS and distribution of samples (**Appendix B**).

Core Summary Diagrams (Appendix C)

The core samples and hydrate saturation data shown in table form elsewhere are presented in **Appendix C** with the PCATS nondestructive data as a diagram for each core. The methane hydrate saturation is presented as % pore volume.

Daily Progress Reports (Appendix D)

The daily progress reports provided via email to ASRC are collected in **Appendix D**.

Data for Each Core or Sample

HPTC Run Reports (Appendix E)

Reports on the tool deployment for each core.

HPTC Pressure-Temperature Diagrams (Appendix F)

There are two types of graph for each set of pressure-temperature data. The first is a record of pressure and temperature vs. time, showing the core history through time. The other graph shows sensor pressure vs. temperature, superimposed over methane hydrate stability curves. The red methane hydrate stability curve is for a pore fluid salinity of 0 ppt. Examining the data as a pressure-temperature trajectory allows quick identification of excursions outside methane hydrate stability. Data from the “rabbit” sensor is presented when possible.

PCATS X-ray Images (Appendix G)

The X-ray linear images for each core are presented in one-meter sections, with a 2x horizontal exaggeration for ease of viewing.

PCATS X-ray Computed Laminography (CL) Reconstructions (Appendix H)

Along-core orthogonal slabs (5mm thick) from the CL reconstructions for each core are presented in one-meter sections, with a 2x horizontal exaggeration for ease of viewing.

PCATS X-ray CT Reconstructions (Appendix I)

Along-core orthogonal slabs (5mm thick) from the CT reconstructions for each core are presented in one-meter sections, with a 2x horizontal exaggeration for ease of viewing. Note that many cores rotated within the liner during CT imaging, causing artifacts and “blurry” images. The CL images are free of these artifacts.

Quantitative Degassing Tables (Appendix J)

The volumes of gas and liquid evolved during each quantitative degassing experiment are shown, tabulated vs. pressure. Syringe samples and gas bag samples are noted, as well as methane concentration at each degassing stage. The final volume of methane used for gas hydrate calculations is in the lower right corner of each table.

Quantitative Degassing Pressure-Volume Diagrams (Appendix K)

The volumes of gas and liquid evolved during each quantitative degassing experiment are shown, displayed vs. pressure. The cumulative collected fluid (blue), multiplied by the pressure, plus the cumulative collected gas (green) at each stage is equal the total gas present in the system (red points and line on plots).

Gas Hydrate Saturation Table (Appendix L)

Gas hydrate saturation for each quantitatively degassed core (Q degas sample, BIO sample, PCATS Triaxial sample), and values required to calculate the gas hydrate saturation.

Linescan Images (Appendix M)

Images for each depressurized core section or piece which was split are presented individually. The number at the top of the image is the depth in core at the top of the section or piece, in centimeters.

PCATS Triaxial Reports (Appendix N)

The core samples tested in PCATS Triaxial are written up, with plots of reconsolidation vs time, resonant column frequency response, pressure differential over time with fluid flow, and elastic parameters & permeability vs effective stress.

Appendix A: List of Cores

List of Cores

core		depth		pressure			recovery		
Date	Core	Measured Depth (ft)	Vertical Depth (ft)	In situ Pressure (MPa)	Recovery Pressure (psi)	Recovery Pressure (MPa)	Cored Interval (ft)	Total cored length (m)	% Recovery
28-Oct-22	HY02-1P	2369.00	0.00	0.0	2220	153.1	10.00	2.46	81%
28-Oct-22	HY02-2P	2379.00	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	10.00	3.05	100%
29-Oct-22	HY02-3P	2389.00	0.00	0.0	2247	155.0	10.00	1.05	34%
29-Oct-22	HY02-4P	2399.00	0.00	0.0	2300	158.6	10.00	1.43	47%
30-Oct-22	HY02-5P	2409.00	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	10.00	3.08	101%
30-Oct-22	HY02-6P*	2419.00	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	10.00	3.48	114%
30-Oct-22	HY02-7P	2429.00	0.00	0.0	2210	152.4	10.30	3.54	113%
31-Oct-22	HY02-8P	2439.30	0.00	0.0	2090	144.1	10.20	1.42	46%
31-Oct-22	HY02-9P	2449.50	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	10.00	2.97	97%
31-Oct-22	HY02-10P	2459.50	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	10.00	2.55	84%
31-Oct-22	HY02-11P	2469.50	0.00	0.0	2100	144.8	10.10	2.81	91%
03-Nov-22	HY02-12P	2873.00	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	10.00	2.68	88%
03-Nov-22	HY02-13P	2883.00	0.00	0.0	2225	153.4	10.10	3.55	115%
03-Nov-22	HY02-14P	2893.10	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	9.90	3.20	106%
04-Nov-22	HY02-15P	2903.00	0.00	0.0	2090	144.1	9.80	3.25	109%
04-Nov-22	HY02-16P	2912.80	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	9.80	2.90	97%
04-Nov-22	HY02-17P**	2923.60	0.00	0.0	2300	158.6	9.90	2.99	99%
04-Nov-22	HY02-18P	2933.50	0.00	0.0	2170	149.7	10.00	2.05	67%
05-Nov-22	HY02-19P	2943.50	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	9.50	2.90	100%
05-Nov-22	HY02-20P	2953.00	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	10.00	3.07	101%
05-Nov-22	HY02-21P	2963.00	0.00	0.0	2150	148.3	10.00	3.23	106%
05-Nov-22	HY02-22P	2973.00	0.00	0.0	2000	137.9	10.00	3.12	102%
06-Nov-22	HY02-23P	2983.00	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	10.10	2.92	95%
06-Nov-22	HY02-24P	2993.10	0.00	0.0	2200	151.7	9.90	3.22	107%

*Core 6P had a shattered liner, and had to be depressurized in PCATS

**Drilling depth adjustment just before Core 17P from 2922.6 ft to 2923.6 ft

Appendix B: List of Sections

List of Sections & Pieces

Hole	Core	Core type	Section	Piece	Piece interval top (cm)	Piece interval bottom (cm)	Piece top (MD, ft)	Piece bottom (MD, ft)	Sample code
HY02	1	P	1	a	0	70	2369.00	2371.30	Q degas
HY02	1	P	1	b	70	90	2371.30	2371.95	Cryo
HY02	1	P	2		90	110	2371.95	2372.61	R DEGAS
HY02	1	P	3		110	130	2372.61	2373.27	R DEGAS
HY02	1	P	4		130	246	2373.27	2377.07	USGS
HY02	2	P	1		5	25	2379.16	2379.82	Q degas
HY02	2	P	2		25	65	2379.82	2381.13	R DEGAS
HY02	2	P	3	a	65	75	2381.13	2381.46	R DEGAS
HY02	2	P	3	b	75	90	2381.46	2381.95	Cryo
HY02	2	P	3	c	90	110	2381.95	2382.61	Cryo
HY02	2	P	3	d	110	130	2382.61	2383.27	Cryo
HY02	2	P	3	e	130	160	2383.27	2384.25	USGS
HY02	2	P	3	f	160	180	2384.25	2384.91	Bio
HY02	2	P	4		180	291.6	2384.91	2388.57	AIST
HY02	3	P	1		0	5.5	2389.00	2389.18	R DEGAS
HY02	3	P	2		5.5	105	2389.18	2392.44	AIST
HY02	4	P	1		0	32	2399.00	2400.05	R DEGAS
HY02	4	P	2	a	32	37	2400.05	2400.21	R DEGAS
HY02	4	P	2	b	37	52	2400.21	2400.71	USGS
HY02	4	P	2	c	52	63	2400.71	2401.07	Triax
HY02	4	P	2	d	63	74	2401.07	2401.43	Triax
HY02	4	P	2	e	74	95	2401.43	2402.12	NETL
HY02	4	P	2	f	95	110	2402.12	2402.61	Cryo
HY02	4	P	2	g	110	125	2402.61	2403.10	Cryo
HY02	4	P	2	h	125	140	2403.10	2403.59	Cryo
HY02	5	P	1		3.5	107	2409.11	2412.51	AIST
HY02	5	P	2		107	140	2412.51	2413.59	Q degas
HY02	5	P	3	a	140	150	2413.59	2413.92	R DEGAS
HY02	5	P	3	b	150	178	2413.92	2414.84	USGS
HY02	5	P	4	a	178	190	2414.84	2415.23	R DEGAS
HY02	5	P	4	b	190	210	2415.23	2415.89	Bio
HY02	5	P	4	c	210	230	2415.89	2416.55	Bio
HY02	5	P	4	d	230	260	2416.55	2417.53	NETL
HY02	5	P	4	e	260	280	2417.53	2418.19	Cryo
HY02	5	P	4	f	280	305	2418.19	2419.01	Cryo
HY02	6	P	1		0	98	2419.00	2422.22	R DEGAS
HY02	6	P	2		98	199	2422.22	2425.53	R DEGAS
HY02	6	P	3		199	302	2425.53	2428.91	R DEGAS
HY02	6	P	4		302	324	2428.91	2429.63	R DEGAS
HY02	6	P	5		324	348	2429.63	2430.42	R DEGAS
HY02	7	P	1	a	5	10	2429.16	2429.33	R DEGAS
HY02	7	P	1	b	10	30	2429.33	2429.98	Cryo
HY02	7	P	1	c	30	50	2429.98	2430.64	Q degas
HY02	7	P	1	d	50	70	2430.64	2431.30	Cryo
HY02	7	P	1	e	70	90	2431.30	2431.95	Cryo
HY02	7	P	1	f	90	110	2431.95	2432.61	Bio
HY02	7	P	1	g	110	125	2432.61	2433.10	Q degas
HY02	7	P	2	a	125	130	2433.10	2433.27	R DEGAS
HY02	7	P	2	b	130	150	2433.27	2433.92	Q degas
HY02	7	P	2	c	150	165	2433.92	2434.41	Cryo
HY02	7	P	2	d	165	195	2434.41	2435.40	USGS
HY02	7	P	2	e	195	245	2435.40	2437.04	Q degas
HY02	7	P	3		245	260	2437.04	2437.53	Q degas
HY02	7	P	4		260	280	2437.53	2438.19	R DEGAS
HY02	7	P	4		280	300	2438.19	2438.84	R DEGAS

List of Sections & Pieces

Hole	Core	Core type	Section	Piece	Piece interval top (cm)	Piece interval bottom (cm)	Piece top (MD, ft)	Piece bottom (MD, ft)	Sample code
HY02	7	P	4		300	320	2438.84	2439.50	R DEGAS
HY02	8	P	1	a	0	7	2439.30	2439.53	R DEGAS
HY02	8	P	1	b		25	2439.53	2440.12	Q degas
HY02	8	P	1	c	25	65	2440.12	2441.43	Q degas
HY02	8	P	1	d	65	85	2441.43	2442.09	Bio
HY02	8	P	1	e	85	100	2442.09	2442.58	R DEGAS
HY02	8	P	1	f	100	120.5	2442.58	2443.25	Cryo
HY02	8	P	2		120.5	140.5	2443.25	2443.91	R DEGAS
HY02	9	P	1		0	120	2449.50	2453.44	Q degas
HY02	9	P	2	a	120	125	2453.44	2453.60	R DEGAS
HY02	9	P	2	b	125	135	2453.60	2453.93	Q degas
HY02	9	P	2	c	135	165	2453.93	2454.91	USGS
HY02	9	P	2	d	165	180	2454.91	2455.41	Cryo
HY02	9	P	2	e	180	200	2455.41	2456.06	Bio
HY02	9	P	2	f	200	220	2456.06	2456.72	Bio
HY02	9	P	3		220	260	2456.72	2458.03	R DEGAS
HY02	9	P	4		260	297	2458.03	2459.24	R DEGAS
HY02	10	P	1		0	115	2459.50	2463.27	Q degas
HY02	10	P	2		115	180	2463.27	2465.41	Q degas
HY02	10	P	3	a	180	200	2465.41	2466.06	R DEGAS
HY02	10	P	3	b	200	220	2466.06	2466.72	R DEGAS
HY02	10	P	4		220	250	2466.72	2467.70	R DEGAS
HY02	11	P	1		0	117	2469.50	2473.34	Q degas
HY02	11	P	2		120	217	2473.44	2476.62	Q degas
HY02	11	P	3		217	251	2476.62	2477.73	R DEGAS
HY02	11	P	4		251	271	2477.73	2478.39	R DEGAS
HY02	12	P	1		0	106	2873.00	2876.48	Q degas
HY02	12	P	2		106	205	2876.48	2879.73	Q degas
HY02	12	P	3	a	205	226	2879.73	2880.41	R DEGAS
HY02	12	P	3	b	226	246	2880.41	2881.07	R DEGAS
HY02	12	P	4		246	268	2881.07	2881.79	R DEGAS
HY02	13	P	1		5	87	2883.16	2885.85	Q degas
HY02	13	P	2		87	175	2885.85	2888.74	Q degas
HY02	13	P	3		175	281	2888.74	2892.22	Q degas
HY02	13	P	4		281	301	2892.22	2892.88	R DEGAS
HY02	13	P	5		301	344	2892.88	2894.29	R DEGAS
HY02	14	P	1	a	0	26	2893.10	2893.95	R DEGAS
HY02	14	P	1	b	26	46	2893.95	2894.61	R DEGAS
HY02	14	P	2	a	46	51	2894.61	2894.77	R DEGAS
HY02	14	P	2	b	51	70	2894.77	2895.40	Cryo
HY02	14	P	2	c	70	90	2895.40	2896.05	Cryo
HY02	14	P	2	d	90	110	2896.05	2896.71	Cryo
HY02	14	P	2	e	110	140	2896.71	2897.69	USGS
HY02	14	P	2	f	140	155	2897.69	2898.19	Cryo
HY02	14	P	2	g	155	171	2898.19	2898.71	Cryo
HY02	14	P	3		171	296	2898.71	2902.81	AIST
HY02	14	P	4		296	320	2902.81	2903.60	R DEGAS
HY02	15	P	1	a	0	1	2903.00	2903.03	R DEGAS
HY02	15	P	1	b	1	21	2903.03	2903.69	Bio
HY02	15	P	1	c	21	41	2903.69	2904.35	Cryo
HY02	15	P	1	d	41	61	2904.35	2905.00	Q degas
HY02	15	P	2		61	180	2905.00	2908.91	USGS
HY02	15	P	3	a	180	185	2908.91	2909.07	R DEGAS
HY02	15	P	3	b	185	215	2909.07	2910.05	USGS
HY02	15	P	3	c	215	245	2910.05	2911.04	NETL

List of Sections & Pieces

Hole	Core	Core type	Section	Piece	Piece interval top (cm)	Piece interval bottom (cm)	Piece top (MD, ft)	Piece bottom (MD, ft)	Sample code
HY02	15	P	3	d	245	265	2911.04	2911.69	Cryo
HY02	15	P	3	e	265	280	2911.69	2912.19	Cryo
HY02	15	P	3	f	280	292.5	2912.19	2912.60	Cryo
HY02	15	P	4		292.5	316	2912.60	2913.37	R DEGAS
HY02	16	P	1	a	0	5	2912.80	2912.96	R DEGAS
HY02	16	P	1	b	5	18	2912.96	2913.39	Cryo
HY02	16	P	1	c	18	42	2913.39	2914.18	Cryo
HY02	16	P	1	d	42	53	2914.18	2914.54	Triax
HY02	16	P	1	e	53	70	2914.54	2915.10	Cryo
HY02	16	P	1	f	70	90	2915.10	2915.75	Cryo
HY02	16	P	1	g	90	120	2915.75	2916.74	NETL
HY02	16	P	2		120	150	2916.74	2917.72	Q degas
HY02	16	P	3		150	268	2917.72	2921.59	AIST
HY02	16	P	4		268	290	2921.59	2922.31	
HY02	17	P	1		0	48.5	2923.60	2925.19	R DEGAS
HY02	17	P	2		48.5	98.5	2925.19	2926.83	AIST
HY02	17	P	3	a	98.5	112	2926.83	2927.27	Bio
HY02	17	P	3	b	112	132	2927.27	2927.93	Bio
HY02	17	P	4		132	158	2927.93	2928.78	Q degas
HY02	17	P	5	a	158	162	2928.78	2928.91	R DEGAS
HY02	17	P	5	b	162	173	2928.91	2929.28	Triax
HY02	17	P	5	c	173	184	2929.28	2929.64	Triax
HY02	17	P	5	d	184	206	2929.64	2930.36	Cryo
HY02	17	P	5	e	206	228	2930.36	2931.08	Cryo
HY02	17	P	5	f	228	248	2931.08	2931.74	Cryo
HY02	17	P	5	g	248	263	2931.74	2932.23	Cryo
HY02	17	P	5	h	263	278	2932.23	2932.72	Cryo
HY02	17	P	6		278	299	2932.72	2933.41	R DEGAS
HY02	18	P	1	a	0	10	2933.50	2933.83	R DEGAS
HY02	18	P	1	b	10	30	2933.83	2934.48	Cryo
HY02	18	P	1	c	30	50	2934.48	2935.14	Bio
HY02	18	P	1	d	50	70	2935.14	2935.80	Cryo
HY02	18	P	1	e	70	90	2935.80	2936.45	Cryo
HY02	18	P	1	f	90	110	2936.45	2937.11	Cryo
HY02	18	P	2	a	110	113	2937.11	2937.21	R DEGAS
HY02	18	P	2	b	113	130	2937.21	2937.77	USGS
HY02	18	P	2	c	130	175	2937.77	2939.24	Q degas
HY02	18	P	2	d	175	205	2939.24	2940.23	R DEGAS
HY02	19	P	1		0	120	2943.50	2947.44	AIST
HY02	19	P	2	a	120	128	2947.44	2947.70	R DEGAS
HY02	19	P	2	b	128	139	2947.70	2948.06	Triax
HY02	19	P	2	c	139	150	2948.06	2948.42	Triax
HY02	19	P	2	d	150	170	2948.42	2949.08	Bio
HY02	19	P	2	e	170	190	2949.08	2949.73	Cryo
HY02	19	P	2	f	190	220	2949.73	2950.72	USGS
HY02	19	P	2	g	220	240	2950.72	2951.37	Cryo
HY02	19	P	3		240	290	2951.37	2953.01	R DEGAS
HY02	20	P	1	a	0	5	2953.00	2953.16	R DEGAS
HY02	20	P	1	b	5	20	2953.16	2953.66	Cryo
HY02	20	P	1	c	20	40	2953.66	2954.31	Bio
HY02	20	P	1	d	40	60	2954.31	2954.97	Cryo
HY02	20	P	1	e	60	77	2954.97	2955.53	Cryo
HY02	20	P	1	f	77	120	2955.53	2956.94	Q degas
HY02	20	P	2		120	170	2956.94	2958.58	R DEGAS
HY02	20	P	3		170	205	2958.58	2959.73	Q degas
HY02	20	P	4		205	286	2959.73	2962.38	Q degas
HY02	20	P	5		286	306	2962.38	2963.04	R DEGAS

List of Sections & Pieces

Hole	Core	Core type	Section	Piece	Piece interval top (cm)	Piece interval bottom (cm)	Piece top (MD, ft)	Piece bottom (MD, ft)	Sample code
HY02	21	P	1	a	0	30	2963.00	2963.98	Q degas
HY02	21	P	1	b	30	60	2963.98	2964.97	USGS
HY02	21	P	1	c	60	120	2964.97	2966.94	Q degas
HY02	21	P	2		120	155	2966.94	2968.09	Q degas
HY02	21	P	3		155	265	2968.09	2971.69	Q degas
HY02	21	P	4		265	320	2971.69	2973.50	R DEGAS
HY02	22	P	1	a	0	15	2973.00	2973.49	R DEGAS
HY02	22	P	1	b	15	30	2973.49	2973.98	Cryo
HY02	22	P	1	c	30	50	2973.98	2974.64	Cryo
HY02	22	P	1	d	50	120	2974.64	2976.94	Q degas
HY02	22	P	2		120	240	2976.94	2980.87	Q degas
HY02	22	P	3	a	240	260	2980.87	2981.53	R DEGAS
HY02	22	P	3	b	260	280	2981.53	2982.19	R DEGAS
HY02	22	P	4		280	303	2982.19	2982.94	R DEGAS
HY02	23	P	1	a	0	65	2983.00	2985.13	Q degas
HY02	23	P	1	b	65	80	2985.13	2985.62	Cryo
HY02	23	P	1	c	80	120	2985.62	2986.94	Q degas
HY02	23	P	2		120	220	2986.94	2990.22	Q degas
HY02	23	P	3	a	220	240	2990.22	2990.87	R DEGAS
HY02	23	P	3	b	240	265	2990.87	2991.69	R DEGAS
HY02	23	P	4		265	292	2991.69	2992.58	R DEGAS
HY02	24	P	1		2	122	2993.17	2997.10	Q degas
HY02	24	P	2		122	242	2997.10	3001.04	Q degas
HY02	24	P	3	a	242	252	3001.04	3001.37	R DEGAS
HY02	24	P	3	b	252	314	3001.37	3003.40	R DEGAS

Appendix C: Core Summary Diagrams

HY02-01P, 2369.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-02P, 2379.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-03P, 2389.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-04P, 2399.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-05P, 2409.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-06P, 2419.0 ft MD

AS CUT

HY02-07P, 2429.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-08P, 2439.3 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-09P, 2449.5 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-10P, 2459.5ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-11P, 2469.5ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-12P, 2873.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-13P, 2883.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-14P, 2893.1ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-15P, 2903.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-16P, 2912.8ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-17P, 2923.6ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-18P, 2993.5ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-19P, 2943.5ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-20P, 2953.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-21P, 2963.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-22P, 2973.0 ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-23P, 2983.0ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

HY02-24P, 2993.1ft MD

AS CUT IN PCATS

Appendix D: Daily Progress Reports

GEOTEK CORING Inc
 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
 +1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 1	2022-09-12
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GENERAL

Geotek equipment, 9 container units, are currently in Fairbanks en route to Deadhorse and we currently expect this equipment to be arriving over the next 3-5 days.

Mike Mimitz is now in in Fairbanks to install rubber dampeners/spacers on both Geotek units P11 and P8 to provide additional vibration protection during the road haul from Fairbanks to Deadhorse.

The schedule for main activities on site are firming up. We have the following confirmations from AES re immediate current planned timings:

- Sun 25th Sept.- Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
- Fri 30th Sept. - GDW well - SPUD date

FORWARD LOOK

Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers units prior to mobilization in the tent.

With this schedule in mind more detailed travel plans for all the 14 Geotek crew are now being made.

Geotek is also co ordinating travel and work plans with the USGS party of 6 who will be working closely alongside Geotek processing cores in the tent.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 2	Mon 12th Sept 22
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GENERAL

Geotek equipment, 9 container units, are still in Fairbanks at the Carlyle yard. Following discussions with Carlile we now expect the first units to arrive in Deadhorse around the end of this week but the schedule for all the units is more uncertain - hopefully by the middle of the following week 21st Sept.

Mike Mimitz installed the rubber dampeners/spacers on both Geotek units P11 and P8 which provide additional vibration protection during the road haul from Fairbanks to Deadhorse. Mike re-emphasised the need for these and other units to be transported on 'air-ride' trucks.

FORWARD LOOK

We are still working to the following near term schedule:

Sun 25th Sept.- Tent ready for Geotek mobilization

Fri 30th Sept. - GDW well - SPUD date

Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers when they first arrive prior to mobilization in the tent.

Further meetings with USGS and NETL scientists tomorrow (13th September 22) .

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 3	Tues 13th Sept 22
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GENERAL

Geotek equipment, 9 container units in Fairbanks.
Mike Mimitz - on standby in Anchorage ready for units to arrive in Deadhorse
VC meeting between Geotek, USGS and NETL coordinating logistics and detailed science activity planning.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 15th Sept - Matt Selman arrives Anchorage
~ Fri 16th Sept - 1st Geotek units in Deadhorse for inspection
Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers when they first arrive prior to mobilization in the tent.
Mon 24th Sept.- Quentin Huggett arrives Deadhorse
~ Sun 25th Sept.- Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
~ Fri 30th Sept. - GDW well - SPUD date

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 4	Wed 14th Sept 22
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GENERAL

Geotek equipment, 9 container units in Fairbanks.

Mike Mimitz - on standby in Anchorage ready for units to arrive in Deadhorse

Mike had confirmation today that first units would arrive in Deadhorse on Saturday 17th Sept.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 15th Sept - Matt Selman arrives Anchorage

Sat 17th Sept - 1st Geotek units arrive in Deadhorse for inspection

Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers when they first arrive prior to mobilization in the tent.

Mon 24th Sept.- Quentin Huggett arrives Deadhorse

~ Sun 25th Sept.- Tent ready for Geotek mobilization

~ Fri 30th Sept. - GDW well - SPUD date

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 5	Thurs 15th Sept 22
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GENERAL

Geotek equipment, 2 container units confirmed on route from Fairbanks to Deadhorse.
Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman - on standby in Anchorage ready for units to arrive in Deadhorse
First units to arrive Deadhorse on Saturday 17th Sept.

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 17th Sept - 1st Geotek units arrive in Deadhorse for inspection
Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers when they first arrive prior to mobilization in the tent.
Mon 24th Sept.- Quentin Huggett arrives Deadhorse
~ Sun 25th Sept.- Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
~ Fri 30th Sept. - GDW well - SPUD date

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 6	Fri 16th Sept 22
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GENERAL

AES informed Geotek that schedule has slipped about 7 days. Geotek will adjust plans accordingly.
2 container units on route from Fairbanks to Deadhorse.
Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman - on standby in Anchorage ready for units to arrive in Deadhorse

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 17th Sept - 1st Geotek units arrive in Deadhorse for inspection
Mike Mimitz and Matt Selman will travel to Deadhorse to meet and visually inspect the equipment inside the containers when they first arrive prior to mobilization in the tent.
~ Monday 3rd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
EstimatedMon 17th Oct. - Start coring ?

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 7	Sat 17th Sept 22
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GENERAL

PCATS container units arrived in Deadhorse.

2 Geotek crew arrived in Deadhorse

Initial visual inspection of PCATS units inside and out indicated no damage or shifting of equipment.

FORWARD LOOK

Geotek to make further detailed equipment inspections.

Geotek to visit pad site - especially to inspect rig mats for any handling issues that might be envisaged

Travel plans for remainder of Geotek crew being made based on following schedule:

~ Sunday 2nd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization

~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

EstimatedMon 17th Oct. - Start coring ?

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 8	Sun 18th Sept 22
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GENERAL

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Plans made to visit pad site tomorrow - primarily to inspect rig mats for any handling issues that might be envisaged

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 19th September - visit to pad site tomorrow

Further detailed equipment inspections as equipment becomes available.

Travel plans for remainder of Geotek crew being made based on following schedule:

~ Sunday 2nd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization

~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

EstimatedMon 17th Oct. - Start coring ?

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 9	Mon 19th Sept 22
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GENERAL

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Visit made to drill site on Z pad site - some minor rig mat concerns

- Rig mat in front of the northside of the tent is not level or flat
- Some trip hazards in the tent
- Rig mats need a ramp for the forklift to smoothly get from the rig to the tent for core transfer

Mike Mimitz in discussion with Mike Quick

Made visit to accomodation camp; now in contact with camp manager to make necessary arrangements for Geotek crew.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Further detailed equipment inspections as equipment becomes available.

Travel plans for remainder of Geotek crew being made based on following schedule:

~ Sunday 2nd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization

~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

EstimatedMon 17th Oct. - Start coring ?

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 10	Tues 20th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Mike Mimitz in discussion with Mike Quick about adjusting rig mats as needed

Detailed discussions with USGS re co ordinating arrival dates for different groups based on schedule below in Forward Look.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Further detailed inspections to be made as equipment becomes available.

Travel plans for remainder of Geotek and USGS crew being made based on following schedule:

- ~ Sunday 2nd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
- ~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Between Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 11	Wed 21st Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Detailed discussions with USGS re co ordinating arrival dates for different groups based on schedule below in Forward Look.

Arranging arrivals at camp for complete Geotek/USGS crew from 3rd Oct

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

22nd Sept - Visit Z-pad for on site discussion re mob plan into tent

Further detailed inspections to be made as equipment becomes available in Deadhorse.

Travel plans for remainder of Geotek and USGS crew being made based on following schedule:

- ~ Sunday 2nd October - Tent ready for Geotek mobilization
- ~ Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Between Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 12	Thurs 22nd Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Further inspections of Geotek units in Deadhorse. 5 container units opened and inspected. Nothing shifted; all equipment to be in good shape. Computer/electronics in PCATS tested briefly.

Further discussions with USGS re co ordinating arrival dates for different groups based on schedule below in Forward Look.

Visit to Z-pad - discussions with ACES personnel re detailed tent loading plan. Good communication between different groups.

Arranging arrivals at camp for complete Geotek/USGS crew from 3rd Oct

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Further detailed inspections to be made as equipment becomes available in Deadhorse.

Mon 3rd October - Start mobilization into tent

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 13	Fri 23rd Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Detailed personnel plan for Camp Kusco sent to camp manager for the 20 Geotek and USGS coring and core analysis crew arriving from 3rd October.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Further detailed inspections to be made as equipment becomes available in Deadhorse.

- Mon 3rd October - Main Geotek crew arrive and begin mobilization into tent
- Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 14	Sat 24th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel

Prelim discussions with ASRC SimOps Coordinator re tent mobilixation at the pad. Looking to set up Mob meeting between parties next week when tent construction nearing completion.

Core degassing container unit (R17) inspected on arrival - all in good shape inside.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Further detailed inspections to be made as equipment becomes available in Deadhorse.

- Mon 3rd October - Main Geotek crew arrive and begin mobilization into tent
- Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 15	Sun 25th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew on standby for travel.

Discussions with ACES company men on the pad today indicate that the tent will be complete by the 30th September and Geotek should start loading our units on 1st October. Official confirmation from AES required ASAP.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby - Final inspections of Geotek equipment to be made in Deadhorse prior to moving to pad.

Monday 26th Sept	Book flights for remainder of Geotek crew
Sat 1st October -	Main Geotek crew arrive and begin mobilization into tent
Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well -	SPUD date
Tues 11th Oct -	USGS crew arrive
Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. -	Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 16	Mon 26th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

All 9 Geotek units have been inspected in the Carlisle yard in Deadhorse and are ready to move to the pad.

AES reconfirmed 3rd Oct as start date for mob into tent

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Fri 30th Sept - Geotek crew start moving into camp

Mon 3rd Oct - Begin mobilization into tent

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 17	Tues 27th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

Inspected tent progress - see pictures. We understand this should be complete ~1st October

Power connectors supplied ready for electrical hook ups.

All 9 Geotek units are in the Carlisle trucking yard in Deadhorse ready to move to the pad on 1st day of Mobilization (currently 3rd October).

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Fri 30th Sept - Geotek crew start moving into camp

Sat 1st Oct - Tent 'ready' for mob

Mon 3rd Oct - Begin mobilization into tent

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 18	Wed 28th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

Checked on power connectors for electrical hook ups - all correct

All 9 Geotek units are in the Carlisle trucking yard in Deadhorse ready to move to the pad on 1st day of Mobilization (currently 3rd October).

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Assist with layout of power leads to ensure lengths are good

Fri 30th Sept - Geotek crew start moving into camp

Sat 1st Oct - Tent 'ready' for mob

Mon 3rd Oct - Begin mobilization into tent

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 19	Thurs 29th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

Laid our power lines at the pad to check lengths ready for connection of Geotek distribution unit to the generator.

All 9 Geotek units are in the Carlisle trucking yard in Deadhorse ready to move to the pad on 1st day of Mobilization (currently 3rd October).

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

Assist with layout of power leads to ensure lengths are good

Fri 30th Sept - 0700 Meet with construction manager / company man to finalise some 'move into tent' details.

Geotek crew start moving into camp

Sat 1st Oct - Tent 'ready' for mob

Mon 3rd Oct - Begin mobilization into tent

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 20	Fri 30th Sept 22
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MOBILIZATION

2 Geotek crew on Standby in Deadhorse - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

Tent loading plan confirmed with tent construction manager and company man. All 9 Geotek units are in the Carlisle trucking yard in Deadhorse ready to move to the tent on Monday 3rd October.

Geotek crew moved to camp

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

1st - 3rd Oct Geotek Mob crew arrive.

Mon 3rd Oct - Mobilization starts

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 21	Sat 1st Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION

3 Geotek crew on Standby at Camp - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

All 9 Geotek units + ancillary shipments are in the Carlisle trucking yard in Deadhorse ready to move to the tent on Monday 3rd October.

FORWARD LOOK

On standby	
2nd - 4th Oct	Geotek Mob crew arrive.
Mon 3rd Oct -	Mobilization starts
Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well -	SPUD date
Tues 11th Oct -	USGS crew arrive
Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. -	Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 22	Sun 2nd Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION

3 Geotek crew on Standby at Camp - remaining crew scheduled for travel.

Marked rig mats with paint for the Geotek unit layout ready for placement when the units arrive tomorrow

Firm plans in place with all parties for units to arrive at the tent starting at 7 am tomorrow Monday 3rd October to start mobilization

FORWARD LOOK

On standby

3rd - 4th Oct Geotek Mob crew arrive.

Mon 3rd Oct - Mobilization starts

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 23	Mon 3rd Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION

9 Geotek crew on site and at camp.

All 9 Geotek units were transferred from Deadhorse to the tent and placed in position.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue mobilization in tent with particular attention on getting power sistribution set up.

- Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 24	Tues 4th Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION Day #2

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp.

Power was run from the Generator Set to the Geotek distribution system.

Began connecting power to Geotek Units.

Started uppacking units.

An incident occurred that resulted in a minor hand injury to Geotek engineer when handling power connector to PCATS. This was deemed to be caused by a high heat arc inside the connector presumably from faulty wiring. No electrical shock occurred. Incident reported and medic consulted.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue mobilization in tent with particular attention on getting power distribution set up.

- Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date
- Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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Alaska 2022 - GDW WELL - GEOTEK DPR # 25	Wed 5th Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION Day #3

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp.

Power established to G26. Function testing on computers and electronics all good.

Service unit compressor and main chiller tested. Main airtank filled.

PCATS damaged connector repaired by rig electrician

ASRC directed Geotek to stop work at 1400 to enable overhead work on tent construction to be completed.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 6th Oct. - Electrical inspections - Pre spud meeting (1100) - 1200 Continue mobilization in tent with particular attention on getting power distribution set up and equipment tested.

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #4

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp - Mobilization of all equipment continued.

ASRC electrician inspections continued

Barrier erected to separate Geotek activities from tent construction/insulation activities to enable simultaneous activities.

Muster stations and sign in procedures established at pre spud meeting.

G26: Sterile network and internet network set up, awaiting internet service.

PCATS units powered up and testing of PCATS systems began. All functional to date.

R17: Gantry installed; storage chambers and other items removed; ready to power up.

Coring van emptied of parts and ready for power

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 7th Oct. 1200 resume mobilization in tent with particular attention on getting power and other service distribution set up to all units and all equipment tested.

Fri 7th Oct. - GDW well - SPUD date

Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #5

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp - Mobilization of all equipment continued.
 ASRC electrician inspections completed - no issues reported.
 ASRC crew continued with tent insulation.
 G26: Continued computer set ups - waiting for internet connection.
 PCATS Mechanical and software systems checks continue.
 R17: Powered - computer and electronics systems tested. All normal.
 Coring: Powered. Crane functions tested.
 Layout/catwalk area installed

FORWARD LOOK

SPUD ??
 Sat 8th Oct. Continue mobilization as per plan. Geotek crew start moving to shifts
 Mon 10th Oct - Geotek crew on shift pattern C
 Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
 Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #6

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp -
 Mobilization of all equipment continued.
 Crew now on normal 24 hr shift pattern.
 BHA staged ready for delivery to drill floor
 548 gallons water delivered to tent
 Internet delivered to tent - tested / working
 G26: Continued laboratory and computer set ups
 PCATS Mechanical and software systems checks continue. Chiller run up and on test.
 R17: Continue set up
 Continued construction of utility & containment systems and catwalk decking.

FORWARD LOOK

TBD - SPUD ??
 Sun 9th Oct. Continue mobilization as per plan
 Tues 11th Oct - USGS crew arrive
 Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. - Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #7

10 Geotek crew on site and at camp (Kusko & Nabesca)
 Mobilization of all equipment continued on schedule as planned.
 G26: Continued laboratory and computer set ups
 PCATS Mechanical and software systems checks continue.
 R17: Continue set up
 Catwalk decking completed
 Continued construction of utility & effluent capture systems.
 Dry run of HPTC autoclave to PCATS using forklift

1100 SPUD

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 10th Oct -	3 Geotek crew arrive. Continue mobilization as per plan
Tues 11th Oct -	USGS crew arrive
Wed 12th Oct -	1 Geotek crew arrive
Sat 15th Oct -	1 AIST crew arrive
Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. -	Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #8

13 Geotek crew on site and at camp (Kusko & Nabesca)

Mobilization of all equipment continued on schedule as planned.

Coring: Completed construction of effluent capture system

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Filled and pressure tested.

G26: Set up Geotek GC system

R17: Continue set up of degassing systems with pressure

FORWARD LOOK

Tues 11th Oct -

5 USGS crew arrive. Continue mobilization as per plan

Wed 12th Oct -

1 Geotek crew arrive

Sat 15th Oct -

1 AIST crew arrive

Mon 17th Oct - Wed 19th Oct. -

Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #9

- 18 crew on site (13 Geotek / 5 USGS) and at camp (Kusko & Nabesca)
- 2 Geotek crew moved into isolation at Brooks camp after testing COVID positive.
- Mobilization of all equipment continued on schedule as planned.
- ASRC reinforcing plywood floor in tent
- Coring: Continued setup. Commenced building coring tools for testing.
- PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Started calibration procedures.
- G26: Introduced USGS scientists to working spaces in G26
- R17: Continue set up of degassing systems and manifold testing

FORWARD LOOK

- Wed 12th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
Coring tool assembly - Core analysis preparations.
1 Geotek crew arrive
- Sat 15th Oct - 1 AIST crew arrive
- Sun 15th Oct - 2 Geotek crew back from isolation
- Tues 18th Oct - Start coring

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MOBILIZATION Day #10

19 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS) and at camp (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks)

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

Coring: Continued setup and tool building. Performed dry run of coring tool transfer between rig and tent using rig loader. Agreed correct procedure.

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - continued calibration procedures.

G26: USGS scientists waiting for equipment delivery.

R17: Continue set up of degassing systems and manifold testing

FORWARD LOOK

- Thurs 13th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
Coring tool assembly - Core analysis preparations. Autoclave transfer to PCATS
USGS equipment arrives ?
- Sat 15th Oct - 1 AIST crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - 2 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks
- Wed 19th Oct - Start coring

Coring tool transfer between rig and tent using rig loader.

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MOBILIZATION Day #11

19 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks)

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

Coring: Continued setup and tool building - Refined core delivery to/from PCATS

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - continued calibration procedures.

Checked/refined SC350 handling procedures.

G26: USGS equipment delivered to tent - Some missing items.

R17: Continue set up of degassing systems and manifold testing

FORWARD LOOK

- Fri 14th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
Coring tool assembly - Core analysis preparations. Autoclave transfer to PCATS
- Sat 15th Oct - 1 AIST crew arrive
- Mon 17th Oct - 2 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks
- Thurs 20th Oct - Start coring

Tented Geotek village.

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MOBILIZATION Day #12

19 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks)
 Supply run to Deadhorse and 'live check' on 2 crew isolating at Brooks.
 Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.
 Coring: Continued setup and tool preparation/building
 PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Test HPTC autoclave and SC350 transfers. Refine SC350m conveyor operations. Fabricated concrete test core.
 R17: Train USGS on operation of degassing systems.
 G26: USGS equipment preparations continue

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 15th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
 Coring tool assembly - Core analysis preparations
 1 AIST crew arrive
 Mon 17th Oct - 2 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks
 Thurs 20th Oct - Start coring

HPTC Autoclave anc Coring Van

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MOBILIZATION Day #13

Full complement of 20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks)

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

Rectified water line environment adjacent to main door to prevent freezing.

Coring: Continued setup and tool preparation/building

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Pressure testing all SCs.

PTRANS: Maintenance and pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: USGS familiarization of degassing systems.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue - Curatorial meeting.

FORWARD LOOK

- Sun 16th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
 Coring tool assembly - Pressure vessel testing and Core analysis preparations
 Confirm/refine wireline operational procedures
- Mon 17th Oct - 2 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks
- Sat 22nd Oct - 1st Core

USGS 'making stuff work' in G26 Laboratory

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MOBILIZATION Day #14

Full complement of 20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks)

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

CORING: Continued setup and tool preparation/building. Interface discussions with wireline contractors.

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Pressure testing all SCs. New water pump installed, concrete test core loaded for testing.

PTRANS: Maintenance and pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: Agreed with USGS procedures for handling depressurized cores from both rapid and quantitative degassing methods.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue. Repositioned USGS equipment

FORWARD LOOK

- Mon 17th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
 Coring tool assembly - Continue
 Pressure vessel testing. Set up
 detailed analysis on concrete core.
 2 Geotek crew back from isolation at
 Brooks if appropriate
- Sat 22nd Oct - 1st Core

The Nordic Calista Rig #3

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MOBILIZATION Day #15

Full complement of 20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks). 1 crew back from isolation.

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

CORING: Continued setup and tool preparation/building. 1 fully built HPTC autoclave pressurized and ready for trial transfer to PCATS

PCATS: Continue mechanical and software systems checks - Pressure testing all SCs. Testing artificial concrete test core.

PTRANS: Maintenance and pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Tues 18th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
Coring tool assembly - Test Core transfer procedure to PCATS
1 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks if appropriate
- Sat 22nd Oct - First Core
- Sat 1st Nov - Last Core

*PCATS Storage Chambers tested
 ready for 10' cores*

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MOBILIZATION Day #16

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca & Brooks).

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

CORING: Continued assembly of coring tools. HPTC autoclave pressurized and transferred to PCATS.

2nd interface meeting with Schlumberger wireline crew.

PCATS: Continue operational testing - including trial transfer of core from fully pressurized HPTC

PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Wed 19th Oct - Continue mobilization as per plan
 Further test core transfer procedure to PCATS.
 Continue pressure tests of all chambers.
 1 Geotek crew back from isolation at Brooks ?
- Sat 22nd Oct - Estimated date of first Core
- Tues 1st Nov - Estimated date last Core

HPTC on roller stand

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MOBILIZATION Day #17

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

1 crew released from 'Brooks' isolation to Kusko camp

Mobilization of all equipment continued as planned.

Met with ASRC environmental officer to discuss/agree containment procedures for core transfers.

CORING: Continued dressing and rebuilding coring tools with rehearsal transfer cycles into PCATS.

PCATS: Continue operational testing - further trial transfers of core from fully pressurized HPTC

PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue.

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 19th Oct - Further test core transfer procedure of HPTC core to PCATS. Continue pressure tests of all chambers.

Sun 23rd Oct - Estimated date of first Core

Tues 1st Nov - Estimated date of last Core

'Wait on Core' science activities.....w/snacks

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 40	Thurs 20th Oct 22
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MOBILIZATION Day #18

- 20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).
- Optimization of all procedures continues
- Testing back up generator - requested phase changing by ECE Services electrician
- CORING:** Dressing and rebuilding coring tools for optimizing procedures.
- PCATS:** Multiple transfer tests from HPTC - optimizing processes
- PTRANS:** Continue pressure testing overpacks
- R17 Degassing:** Ready for operations.
- G26 Laboratory:** USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Fri 21st Oct - Precautionary planned COVID testing prior to coring ops for complete team
 Optimizing all operational procedures and processes until rig ready for coring operational set up.
 Further testing of core transfer procedures in PCATS with HPTC and Storage Chambers
- Mon 24th Oct - Estimated date of first Core
- Wed 2nd Nov - Estimated date of last Core

Transfer HPTC into PCATS

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MOBILIZATION Day #19

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Backup generator was found to be phased incorrectly; a request has been made for an ICE Services electrician to rectify the issue.

Optimization of all procedures continues.

Conducted precautionary planned COVID test - all crew confirmed negative

Took sample of mineral based mud for testing especially when diluted with water - apart from heightened vigilance in handling and disposal should not cause Geotek any problems.

CORING: Optimizing procedures. Drafting initial coring parameters from available info.

PCATS: Multiple transfer tests and cutting from HPTC and Storage Chambers - optimizing processes

PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS equipment preparations/procedures continue.

Gas analysis of surface well completed

FORWARD LOOK

- Sat 22nd Oct - Optimizing all operational procedures and processes until rig ready for coring operational set up. Chill cold laboratory units ready for core handling operations. Testing of core transfer procedures in PCATS with HPTC & SCs
- Sunday 23rd Oct - Rig up for Coring operations
- Mon 24th Oct - Estimated date of first Core
- Wed 2nd Nov - Estimated date of last Core

USGS Gas Analysis

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MOBILIZATION Day #20

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).
Backup generator fixed by ICE Services electrician to rectify the phasing issue. Re-emphasized the importance of being notified about any work on generators that might cause power interruptions. Barrel of LVT oil delivered for tool cleaning purposes. Finalization of procedures continues. Late in day learnt there may be a delay in ops caused by mud chiller difficulties.
CORING: Optimizing procedures. Drafting initial coring parameters from available info.
PCATS: Testing oil based drilling mud in PCATS to determine physical properties. Optimizing processes.
PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks - all good.
R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.
G26 Laboratory: USGS preparations continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Mon 24th Oct - Rig up for Coring operations?
- Tues 25th Oct - Est. first Core
- Thurs 3rd Nov - Est. last Core

Coring bit ready for BHA assembly and tool space-out

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MOBILIZATION Day #21

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Finalization of procedures continues.

Cleaned and inspect DrillCool's heat exchanger plates which needed urgent servicing

CORING: Ready to begin rig up and coring operations.

PCATS: Optimizing processes especially X-ray CT scanning.

PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks - all good. Prepared/tested transport accumulators.

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS preparations continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Mon 24th Oct - Finish Drill cool cleaning operations
Rig up for Coring operations?
- Tues 25th Oct - Est. first Core
- Thurs 3rd Nov - Est. last Core

Mike Mimitz Jr. pressure washing 'zillions' of heat exchanger chiller plates

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Mobilization Day #22

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Finalization of procedures continues.

Finished cleaning and inspecting DrillCool's heat exchanger plates.

CORING: Cold shuck, chiller, wireline tools, rig floor tools, and BHA subs moved to rig floor and pipe shed. Cold shuck installed on rig floor. Chiller in place and ready for hook-up. Hand tools in place for coring operations.

PCATS: Optimizing processes especially X-ray CT scanning.

PTRANS: Continue pressure testing overpacks - all good. Prepared/tested transport accumulators.

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS preparations continue.

FORWARD LOOK

- Tues 25th Oct. Move BHA core barrel to pipe shed?
- Wed 26th Oct - RU for Coring - Space-out 4 coring tools in BHA
- Thurs 27th Oct Est. first Core Friday 4th Nov - Est. last Core

Moving equipment out of the Geotek tent to rig floor

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Mobilization Day #23

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Finalization of procedures continues. 'Stop the Job' - to review safety measures when handling tools in tent with Company Man.

CORING: Optimizing processes while waiting for coring ops to begin

PCATS: Optimizing processes.

PTRANS: Prepared/tested transport accumulators.

R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS preparations continue.

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 26th Oct - Move BHA core barrel to pipe shed?
 RU for Coring - Space-out 4 coring tools in BHA
 Thurs 27th Oct Est. first Core Fri 4th Nov - Est. last Core #24

Ptarmigan 'Alaskan Chickens'
(not wearing high vis jackets!)

The Alaskan town of Chicken was settled by [gold miners](#) in the late 19th century. In 1902 the local post office was established, requiring a community name. Due to the prevalence of [ptarmigan](#) in the area, that name was suggested as the official name for the new community. However, the spelling could not be agreed on, and "Chicken" was used to avoid embarrassment - from Wikipedia

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Mobilization Day #24

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).
 Finalization of procedures continues.
 Site wide 'Stop the Job' muster in Tent (~40 pax) - Company man reinforced safety culture and emergency procedures.
CORING: Outer core barrel removed from tent - placed in pipe shed ready for ops.
PCATS: Optimizing processes.
PTRANS: Prepared/tested transport accumulators.
R17 Degassing: Ready for operations.
G26 Laboratory: USGS preparations continue.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 27th Oct - RU for Coring - Space-out 4 coring tools in BHA
 Fri 28th Oct Est. first Core Sat 5th Nov - Est. last Core #24

'Pad wide' safety meeting in the primary muster location (tent) ~40pax.

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Coring Day #1

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Assisted DrillCool by lining baskets with finer mesh sizes. Start coring operations on the rig.

CORING: Coring BHA was made up to completion around 1100. Space-out tests of HPTC tools 1-4 completed by 1600. All tools are in proper space-out adjustment. All wireline tools (running, pulling, emergency) were tested in the BHA and fully functional. Vertical 'shuck' is half full of water and the chiller/heater unit is currently running and fully functional. Schlumberger wireline crew have the wireline rope socket adapter.

PCATS: Ready for Core.

PTRANS: Ready for Core

R17 Degassing: Ready for degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: USGS ready for further testing.

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 28th Oct Est. first Core Sat 5th Nov - Est. last Core #24

Basket weavers at work. Geotek Coring crew modifying Drill Cool filter baskets using finer mesh size to help eliminate blockages.

Basket-making in the Arctic region is a traditional practice that has been around for centuries. Baskets are made from the dried grass that grows in the Arctic tundra, which is very durable and water-resistant. Stainless steel basket weaving is a much more recent activity

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Coring Day #2

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Coring operations on the rig. Adjusted hole temperature criteria based on coring temperature records to prevent core freezing.

CORING: Rig up for coring with Schlumberger wire line. Drill Cool operational. Cut Core **HY02-01P**.

Next tool deployed ready for Core **HY02-02P**

PCATS: Fully operational - Core handling and core analysis.

PTRANS: Ready for Core storage

R17 Degassing: Ready for degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core #01 HY-02-01P - Advance 10ft, Recovery 2200 PSI / 8.06 ft - Unit E - Good quality

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 29th Oct Coring Core#2 Core#3 Core#4 Core#5
 Sun 6th Nov Core#24

Coring operations on the drill floor.

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Coring Day #3

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Continue coring operations. Core#4 left some 'stick up' material in the BHA which prevented Core#5 from landing/latching in the BHA. After multiple landing attempts POOH to clear BHA/bit of formation material that had prevented tool landing correctly.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 02P, 03P, 04P**

PCATS: Core handling/processing and core analysis.

PTRANS: Ready for Core storage

R17 Degassing: Ready for degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#2 - HY-02-02P - 2,379' Adv. 10ft, - Recovery 2150 PSI / 9.57 ft - Unit E - Good quality

Core#3 - HY-02-03P - 2,389' Adv. 10ft, - Recovery 2247 PSI / 3.44 ft - Unit E ? - Good quality

Core#4 - HY-02-04P - 2,399' Adv. 10ft, - Recovery 2300 PSI / 4.69ft - Unit D - Good quality

core material left in BHA - trip pipe

FORWARD LOOK

Sun 30th Oct Coring Core#5 Core#6 Core#7....
 Sun 6th Nov Core#24

Lifting strop and tag lines being attached to core autoclave after coring before being moved by loader from rig to tent.

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 50	Sun 30th Oct 22
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Coring Day #4

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Continue coring operations in upper target zone - Units E/D.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 05P, 06P, 07P** - good recoveries and all at high pressure.

PCATS: Core handling/processing and core analysis.

PTRANS: Ready for Core storage

R17 Degassing: Ready for degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#5- HY-02-05P - 2,408.8' Adv. 10.2ft, - Recovery 2200 PSI / 10.1 ft - Unit D1 - GH sand

Small piece below catcher cut and rapid depressurized. GH Sand

Core#6- HY-02-06P - 2,419.0' Adv. 10f.0t, - Recovery 2150 PSI / 7.61 ft - D1/D -

Liner broken, X-ray core at full pressure - depressurized in PCATS - Conventionalized

Core#7 - HY-02-07P - 2,428.7' Adv. 10.6ft, - Recovery 2210 PSI / 11.61ft - Unit D - Good quality

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 31st Oct Coring

Core#8, Core#9, Core#10, Core#11....

Sun 6th Nov Last Core - Core#24

USGS analyzing rapidly depressurized GH sample from bottom of Core#5

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 51	Mon 31st Oct 22
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Coring Day #5

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Continue coring operations in target zone - Units D.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 08P, 09P, 10P** - All cores recovered at high pressure and excellent quality.

PCATS: Core handling/processing and core analysis.

PTRANS: Ready for Core storage

R17 Degassing: Ready for degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#8- HY-02-08P - 2439.3' Adv. 10.2ft, - Recovery 2090 PSI / 4.66 ft - Unit D

Core#9 - HY-02-09P - 2449.5' Adv. 10ft, - Recovery 2150 PSI / 9.74 ft - Unit D -

Core#10 - HY-02-10P - 2459.5' Adv. 10ft, - Recovery 2150 PSI / 8.46 ft - Unit D

FORWARD LOOK

Tues 1st Nov

Coring .- last Core#11 in upper coring zone....

Sun 6th Nov

Last Core - Core#24

Halloween at the rig site

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 52	Tues 1st Nov 22
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Coring Day #6

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Finish coring upper target zone D and core processing acquired cores.

Summary upper coring zone: Recovered all 11 cores at high pressure. Total coring interval 110.6 ft.

Length of core recovered 78.22 ft. Recovery 71%. Core #06P X-ray image at full pressure then depressurized/conventionalized because of broken liner during coring v. hard interval. Core quality as shown by X-ray imaging is generally excellent. Representative cores of all major lithologies collected. Cores currently being further processed in PCATS to collect complete data sets before final cutting/storage etc. Coring tool configuration and coring parameters will be similar for the lower coring interval in the C/B units with subtle changes reflecting lessons learnt.

CORING: Cut Core: **HY02- 11P** - All cores recovered at high pressure and excellent quality.

PCATS: Core handling/processing and core analysis.

Finished PCATS processing: Core#11, Core#01

PTRANS: Core storage - @4°C

R17 Degassing: Degassing operations.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#11 - HY-02-11P - 2469.5' Adv. 10.1ft, - Recovery 2100 PSI / 9.22 ft - Unit D

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 1st Nov

Rebuilding coring tools and processing cores.

Sun 6th Nov

Last Core - Core#24

Extruding geochemistry sample from core catcher assembly (Core#11) after rapid depressurization in PCATS

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 53	Wed 2nd Nov 22
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Coring Day #7

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool refurbishment ready for coring and core processing acquired cores from upper target zone E/D

REVISED Summary upper coring zone: Recovered all 11 cores at high pressure. Total coring interval 110.6 ft. **Length of core recovered 86.28 ft. Recovery 78%.**

CORING: Cleaning, refurbishing/rebuilding coring tools ready for cutting 13 cores in the lower target zone C/B

PCATS: Core handling/processing and core analysis of core recovered to date.

Finished PCATS processing: Core#10

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Degassing operations of samples from Cores #10 & #11.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 3rd Nov

Make up coring BHA

Cut Cores #13, #14 & #15

Sun 6th Nov

Last Core - Core#24

Careful subsampling of depressurized core for geochemical and microbiological analysis. The core is coated with the dark brown oil based drilling mud.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 54	Thurs 3rd Nov 22
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Coring Day #8

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool refurbishment ready for coring. Core processing acquired cores from upper target zone E/D.

Started coring in lower target zone.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 12P & 13P**. All cores recovered at high pressure and excellent quality.

PCATS: Core handling/processing in real time and core analysis of cores recovered to date.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Degassing systems ready for more samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#12- HY-02-12P - 2873.0' Adv. 10.0ft, - Recovery 2200 PSI / 8.79 ft - Unit C?

Core#13- HY-02-13P - 2883.0' Adv. 10.1ft, - Recovery 2225 PSI / 11.09 ft - Unit C?

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 4th Nov

Cut Cores #14, #15, #16 & #17

Sun 6th Nov

Last Core - Core#24

'Teamwork in the Tent' - 14 good cores and counting.....(photo credit Jun Yoneda)

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 55	Fri 4th Nov 22
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Coring Day #9

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool refurbishment ready for coring. Continue coring in lower target zone.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 14P & 15P, 16P, 17P**. All cores recovered at high pressure and excellent quality. Captured interface between Unit C and Unit B (seal/GH) ~3 ft into Core#15.

PCATS: Core handling/processing in real time and core analysis of cores recovered to date.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Degassing systems ready for more samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#14- HY-02-14P - 2893.1' Adv. 9.9', - Recovery 2200 PSI / 10.50 ft - Unit C

Core#15- HY-02-15P - 2903.0' Adv. 9.8', - Recovery 2090 PSI / 10.66 ft - Unit C/B

Core#16- HY-02-16P - 2912.8' Adv. 9.8', - Recovery 2150 PSI / x9.51 ft - Unit B

Core#17- HY-02-17P - 2922.6' Adv. 9.9', - Recovery 2300 PSI / 9.81 ft - Unit B

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 5th Nov

Cut Cores #18, #19, #20 & #21

Sun 6th Nov

Last Core - Core#24

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 56	Sat 5th Nov 22
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Coring Day #10

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool refurbishment ready for coring. Continue coring in lower target zone.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 18P & 19P, 20P, 21P**. All cores recovered at high pressure. Corer #18 is currently stuck in coring autoclave. We will look to remove this at the end of coring operation. Other cores excellent quality through the GH zone and transition zone below.

PCATS: Core handling/processing in real time and core analysis of cores recovered to date.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#18- HY-02-18P - 2933.5' Adv. 10', - Recovery 2170 PSI / ?? ft - Unit B

Core#19- HY-02-19P - 2943.5' Adv. 9.5', - Recovery 2200 PSI / 9.51 ft - Unit B

Core#20- HY-02-20P - 2953.0' Adv. 10', - Recovery 2200 PSI / 10.27 ft - Unit B

Core#21- HY-02-21P - 2963.0' Adv. 10', - Recovery 2150 PSI / 10.59 ft - Unit B

FORWARD LOOK

Sun 6th Nov

Cut last 3 Cores #22, #23 & #24

Fri 18th Nov

Finish Core processing ?

*Remember, remember the fifth of November,
 The gunpowder, treason and plot,
 I know of no reason
 Why gunpowder treason
 Should ever be forgot*

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 57	Sun 6th Nov 22
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Coring Day #11

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool refurbishment ready for coring. Final cores cut in lower target zone.

CORING: Cut Cores : **HY02- 22P, 23P & 24P.**

Summary lower coring zone: Recovered all 13 cores at high pressure. Total coring interval 130 ft. Length of core recovered ~130 ft. Recovery ~100%. (Core #18 - still unknown) Core quality as shown by X-ray imaging is excellent. The whole section was likely recovered (caveat Core #18) including the main Seal/Top of GH contact (in Core#15) and the transition zone.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS to collect complete data sets before cutting/storage etc and transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#22- HY-02-22P - 2973.0' Adv. 10.0', - Recovery 2000 PSI / 10.27 ft - Unit B

Core#23- HY-02-23P - 2983.0' Adv. 10.1', - Recovery 2200 PSI / 9.58 ft - Unit B

Core#24- HY-02-24P - 2993.1' Adv. 9.9', - Recovery 2200 PSI / 10.59 ft - Unit B

FORWARD LOOK

Continue core processing

Clean up coring tools and core var

Fri 18th Nov

Finish Core processing ?

Sat 19th Nov

Start demob

activities.

The Geotek team, with the help of the whole project crew, acquired 24 x ten foot pressure cores, all recovered at full pressure. 240.6 ft cored with ~90% overall recovery in excellent condition.

CORE	CORE #	MD	HP	RECOVERY	RECOVERY	COMMENTS
HY-02	DATE	TIME	FE	FE	PER (IN)	FE (M)
01	2022/11/07	17:10	1000	1000	100	10.00
02	2022/11/07	17:15	1000	1000	100	10.00
03	2022/11/07	17:20	1000	1000	100	10.00
04	2022/11/07	17:25	1000	1000	100	10.00
05	2022/11/07	17:30	1000	1000	100	10.00
06	2022/11/07	17:35	1000	1000	100	10.00
07	2022/11/07	17:40	1000	1000	100	10.00
08	2022/11/07	17:45	1000	1000	100	10.00
09	2022/11/07	17:50	1000	1000	100	10.00
10	2022/11/07	17:55	1000	1000	100	10.00
11	2022/11/07	18:00	1000	1000	100	10.00
12	2022/11/07	18:05	1000	1000	100	10.00
13	2022/11/07	18:10	1000	1000	100	10.00
14	2022/11/07	18:15	1000	1000	100	10.00
15	2022/11/07	18:20	1000	1000	100	10.00
16	2022/11/07	18:25	1000	1000	100	10.00
17	2022/11/07	18:30	1000	1000	100	10.00
18	2022/11/07	18:35	1000	1000	100	10.00
19	2022/11/07	18:40	1000	1000	100	10.00
20	2022/11/07	18:45	1000	1000	100	10.00
21	2022/11/07	18:50	1000	1000	100	10.00
22	2022/11/07	18:55	1000	1000	100	10.00
23	2022/11/07	19:00	1000	1000	100	10.00
24	2022/11/07	19:05	1000	1000	100	10.00

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 58	Mon 7th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing Day #12

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Tool cleaning/maintenance and core processing.

CORING: Refurbishing and cleaning all coring tools.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be processed in PCATS:

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Continue core processing

Clean up coring tools and core van.

Thurs 17th Nov

Finish Core processing ?

Fri 18th Nov

Start demob activities.

The PCD (Polycrystalline Diamond Compact) bit that was used for the pressure coring. PDC core bits have numerous sintered polycrystalline diamond studs arranged on the bit which are very hard wearing. They work well in the formations encountered here (as evidenced by the length and quality of cores recovered) despite the relatively small core diameter.

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 59	Tues 8th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing Day #13

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Refurbishing and cleaning all coring tools.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be processed in PCATS: In Autoclave

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Continue core analysis / processing

Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure where possible.

Wed 16th Nov

Finish Core processing ?

Processing pressure cores in PCATS (Pressure Core Analysis and Transfer System).

Thurs 17th Nov

Cores, up to 11ft long and at pressures up to 5,000 psi, can be analyzed in detail (P-wave velocity, density and X-ray imaging, including CT) and cut into subsamples for further special analysis whilst maintaining in situ temperatures and pressures.

Start demob activities.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 60	Wed 9th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #14

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko & Nabesca).

Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Refurbishing and cleaning all coring tools.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be processed in PCATS: In Autoclave

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 10th Nov

8 Geotek crew moving to hotel in Deadhorse to make room at camp for new arrivals.

Continue core analysis / processing

Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure where possible.

Wed 16th Nov

Finish Core processing

Thurs 17th Nov

Demob activities.

Four cut pressure core samples standing vertically in storage chambers inside the 40' pressure core transport container unit PTRANS. They are being monitored to ensure pressure stability before being fitted with accumulators and secured into the white overpack cylinders for road transportation to Salt Lake City and beyond in the USA and Japan.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 61	Thurs 10th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #15

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

8 Geotek crew moved to hotel in Deadhorse at ASRC request. Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be completely processed in PCATS:

Core In Coring Autoclave

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 11th Nov Continue core analysis / processing
 Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure as available.

Wed 16th Nov Finish Core processing

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob activities.

Tues 22nd Nov Move container units from tent & load trucks

Dismantling the coring BHA, for inspection and cleaning, that was returned from the rig after having been used throughout the coring process.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 62	Fri 11th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #16

20 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS / 1 AIST) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of selected cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be completely processed in PCATS:

Core In Coring Autoclave

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 12th Nov Continue core analysis / processing
 Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure as available.

Wed 16th Nov Finish Core processing (degassing /analyzing last core samples)

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob activities.

Tues 22nd Nov Move container units from tent & load trucks

Syringe samples of gas from the quantitative degassing of core sections cut under pressure. The quantitative degassing process provides accurate gas hydrate concentrations as well as gas composition from gas chromatography analysis (methane, ethane, propane etc.).

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 63	Sat12th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #17

19 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS /) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: All cores are currently being further processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of selected cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Cores fully processed in PCATS: Cores remaining to be completely processed in PCATS:

Core In Coring Autoclave

01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P

12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P

FORWARD LOOK

Sun 13th Nov Continue core analysis / processing
 Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure as available.

Wed 16th Nov Finish Core processing (degassing /analyzing last core samples)

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob activities.

Tues 22nd Nov Move container units from tent & load trucks

VIP treatment for ASRC CEO Christine Resler and SVP Shelley Cordova: a live demonstration of a core being cut and manipulated in PCATS. John, Quentin, and Peter provided the entertainment.

(photo credit Bill Waite)

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 64	Sun13th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #18

19 crew on site (14 Geotek / 5 USGS /) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: Cores continue to be processed in PCATS collecting data sets and cutting as per cut plans ready for transportation to SLC for further detailed analysis and sample distribution.

Core 18P was extracted from the autoclave under pressure (it had previously got stuck) and continues to be analyzed and processed.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of selected cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

Core#18 - HY-02-18P - 2933.5.5' Adv. 10.0ft, - Recovery 2170 PSI / 6.63 ft - Unit B

Cores fully processed in PCATS: **Cores remaining to be fully processed in PCATS:**

- 01P, 02P, 03P, 04P, 05P, 06P, 07P, 08P, 09P, 10P, 11P**
- 12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 20P, 21P, 22P, 23P, 24P**

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 14th Nov Finish processing final core #18 in PCATS -

Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure as available.

Wed 16th Nov Finish Core processing (degassing /analyzing last core samples)

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob activities.

Tues 22nd Nov Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond..

Pressure core storage chambers, containing core samples, being monitored to ensure pressure integrity. Each of the 36 core samples (up to 4ft long) will then be safely and securely shut inside their individual gas tight overpacks (white). The whole DOT certified 40 ft PTRANS container unit will be kept at 6°C as it travels by road the 3354 miles through Canada to Geotek Coring in Salt Lake City.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 65	Mon14th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #19

16 crew on site (11 Geotek / 5 USGS /) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).
Core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance. Initial transfer of core data to USGS.

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: Final core (#18) finished processing in PCATS.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ 4°C

R17 Degassing: Quantitative degassing of selected cut core samples.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing / USGS Testing samples.

All Cores now fully processed in PCATS:

FORWARD LOOK

- Tues 15th Nov** Gas analysis from final degassing process
Clean up coring tools, core van and other infrastructure as available.
- Wed 16th Nov** Finish remaining core processing
- Thurs 17th Nov** ...Demob activities.
- Tues 22nd Nov** Remove N Wall of tent - Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond.

A selection of pressure core sections are depressurized slowly under controlled temperature conditions. The volume of gas is carefully measured at each stage of the process and the composition measured. With this data together with the measured volume and density of the core, the gas hydrate saturation is calculated. Once the process is complete the cores can be removed from the pressure chambers at atmospheric pressure in good condition, frozen and stored for subsequent sedimentological analysis.

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
 +1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 66	Tues 15th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #20

13 crew on site (11 Geotek / 2 USGS /) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

Final core processing and tool cleaning/maintenance. Further transfer of core data to USGS.

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: Finished processing cores. Began servicing and rebuild of high wear assemblies ready for operations in SLC.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ ~4°C - samples being loaded and mounted in position for monitoring.

R17 Degassing: Finished degassing - last chambers monitored before being moved to PTRANS

G26 Laboratory: Data processing

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 16th Nov Finish remaining core processing

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob activities.

Tues 22nd Nov Remove N. Wall of tent - Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond..

The Final HY-02 Core Board.

Days of coring activity	10 days
Measured Depth of Coring	2369 ft - 3003 ft
# of Cores taken	24 x (~10ft)
Cores recovered at high pressure	24 (100%)
Interval cored	240.6 ft
Good quality core recovered	214.17 ft
Overall % recovery	89%
# of core sections cut in PCATS	87
# of core sections retained at pressure for transport in PTRANS	36 (approx 126.7 ft)
Length of core sections retained at pressure for transport in PTRANS	126.7 ft ~60% of core recovered
Overall core quality	excellent

CORE	CORE AT RIG FLOOR	MD CORE	MD ADVANCE	RECOVERY PRESSURE	RECOVERY LENGTH	COMMENT
HY-02	DATE TIME	FE	FE	PSI (BAT)	FE (m)	
O1P	28 OCT/1817	2369.0	10.0	2200(152)	8.06 (2.458)	E
O2P	29 Oct/02:50	2377.0	10.0	2150(148)	10.00(3.05)	E
O3P	29 OCT/0816	2389.0	10.0	2247(155)	3.44(1.05)	DE?
O4P	29 OCT/1352	2399.0	10.0	2300(159)	4.69(1.43)	D ^{FORNATED}
O5P	30 OCT/1358	2409.0	10.0	2200(152)	10.10(3.08)	D ^{FORNATED}
O6P	30 OCT/1859	2419.0	10.0	2150(148)	7.61(2.32)	D ^{FORNATED}
O7P	30 OCT/2315	2429.0	10.3	2210(152)	10.30(3.14)	D
O8P	31 OCT/0553	2437.0	10.2	2090(144)	4.66(1.42)	D
O9P	31 Oct/1212	2449.0	10.0	2150(148)	9.74(2.97)	D
10P	31 Oct/1945	2459.0	10.0	2150(148)	8.46(2.58)	D
11P	01 Nov/0223	2469.0	10.1	2100(145)	9.22(2.81)	D
12P	03 Nov/1411	2873.0	10.0	2200(152)	8.79(2.68)	C
13P	03 Nov/1950	2883.0	10.1	2225(154)	11.07(3.38)	C
14P	04 Nov/0210	2893.1	9.9	2200(152)	10.50(3.20)	C
15P	04 Nov/0736	2903.0	9.8	2090(144)	10.66(3.25)	B1
16P	04 Nov/1410	2912.8	9.8	2150(148)	9.51(2.90)	B1
17P	04 Nov/2006	2922.6	9.9	2300(159)	9.81(2.99)	B1
18P	05 Nov/0140	2933.5	10	2170(150)	6.73(2.05)	B
19P	05 Nov/0617	2943.5	9.5	2200(152)	9.51(2.90)	B1
20P	05 Nov/1355	2953.0	10.0	2200(152)	10.27(3.13)	B1
21P	05 Nov/2035	2963.0	10.0	2150(148)	10.59(3.22)	B1/B2
22P	06 Nov/0119	2973.0	10.0	2000(138)	10.27(3.13)	B
23P	06 Nov/0537	2983.0	10.1	2200(152)	9.58(2.92)	B
24P	06 Nov/1038	2993.1	9.9	2200(152)	10.59(3.25)	B

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
 +1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 67	Wed16th Nov 22
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Coring/Core Processing - Day #21

12 crew on site (10 Geotek / 2 USGS /) and at camps (Kusko, Nabesca & Hotel Aurora).

Data backup - shut down systems ready for demob

CORING: Cleaning, inspecting, and packaging tool assemblies.

PCATS: Finished servicing - controlled shutdown ready for operations in SLC.

PTRANS: Core storage - @ ~4°C - all pressure core samples mounted in position and monitored prior to shipping.

R17 Degassing: Finished servicing and cleaning - controlled shutdown ready for demob and re use in SLC.

G26 Laboratory: Data processing completed. Data back up run and servers shut down.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 17th Nov ...Demob / packing activities in tent. 5 more crew leaving site

Tues 22nd Nov Remove N. Wall of tent overnight - Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond. Freezer unit left on power in Deadhorse waiting collection.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

The Geotek tented village.

This set up, adjacent to the rig, worked very well as a base for coring, core analysis and data processing.

We thank ASRC for the planning and for making it work so well.

Now we will vacate the tent so it can be repurposed for the rest of the project. Good luck.

Geotek will reestablish a similar village in SLC to finish off the core processing and sample distribution before Christmas.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 68	Thurs17th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #1

5 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).
Demob activities

Met with representatives of Carlile trucking and ASRC to confirm detailed plans to remove containers from site on 22 November.

PCATS: Begin fastening, packing, and loading; disconnect utilities and freeze-proof water system.

CORING: Packing, loading, and fastening of coring tools and equipment.

R17 DEGASSING: Packing, loading, and fastening storage chambers and equipment; drain and freeze-proof water system.

PTRANS: Packing and loading. Continue to monitoring core pressures prior to shipping.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue demob activities

Tues 22nd Nov Remove N. Wall of tent overnight - Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond.

Note: Core samples in PTRANS and Freezer unit will be trucked to SLC.

The Freezer unit will be left on power in Deadhorse waiting collection.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 69	Fri18th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #2

5 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).
Demob activities

PCATS: Complete packing; continue fastening; begin final removal of wastewater utilities.

CORING: Continue packing, loading, and fastening of coring tools and equipment.

R17 DEGASSING: Continue packing, loading, and fastening storage chambers and equipment; removal of wastewater utilities.

G26: Packing & Loading

PTRANS: Monitoring core pressure; begin sealing stable storage chambers into overpack system.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue demob activities

Tues 22nd Nov Remove N. Wall of tent overnight - Move container units from tent & load trucks for transportation to Deadhorse and beyond.

Note: Core samples in PTRANS and Freezer unit will be trucked to SLC.

The Freezer unit will be left on power in Deadhorse waiting collection.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 70	Sat19th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #3

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).
Demob activities

PCATS: Complete fastening; all utilities removed; final packing of light items.

CORING: BHA barrels and subs loaded; hand tools stowed; coring tools fastened for travel.

R17 DEGASSING: Storage chambers and equipment loaded and fastened, utilities removed.

G26: Packing & Loading

PTRANS: Monitoring core pressure; continued sealing stable storage chambers into overpack system; sealed overpack vessels monitored for airtightness.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Loaded and fastened for transit; arrangements made for powered storage on well pad while standing by for transport to SLC (breaker selected and compatible receptacle installed).

FORWARD LOOK

Continue and finish loading and fastening equipment in service containers.

Tues 22nd Nov Load service containers on trucks for Deadhorse. PTRANS to travel direct to SLC;

Freezer Core Store to remain under power onsite until PTRANS chassis return trip is complete.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 71	Sun20th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #4

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).

Demob activities

PCATS: Loading and fastening completed, ready to ship.

CORING: Loading and fastening completed, ready to ship.

R17 DEGASSING: Loading and fastening completed, ready to ship.

G26: Packing, loading, and fastening.

PTRANS: Monitoring core pressure; continued sealing stable storage chambers into overpack system; sealed overpack vessels monitored for airtightness.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Loading and fastening completed, ready to ship; will monitor on site until picked up for transport.

STORES CONTAINER: Loading and fastening completed, ready to ship.

SERVICES: Currently powering PTRANS and Core Store; will disconnect immediately prior to loading.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue and finish loading and fastening equipment in service containers.

Tues 22nd Nov Load service containers on trucks for Deadhorse. PTRANS to travel direct to SLC;

Freezer Core Store to remain under power onsite until PTRANS chassis return trip is complete.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 72	Mon 21st Nov 22
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Demob - Day #5

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).
 Everything completed ready for pickup tomorrow

PCATS: Ready to ship.

CORING: Ready to ship.

R17 DEGASSING: Ready to ship.

G26: Ready to ship.

PTRANS: All overpack vessels sealed, purged, and charged; ready for transport.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Ready to ship to ship; will monitor on site until picked up for transport.

STORES CONTAINER: Ready to ship.

SERVICES: Currently powering PTRANS and Core Store; will disconnect immediately prior to loading.

FORWARD LOOK

Tues 22nd Nov Load service containers on trucks for Deadhorse. PTRANS to travel direct to SLC;
 Freezer Core Store to remain under power onsite until PTRANS chassis return trip is complete.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

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 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 73	Mon 22nd Nov 22
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Demob - Day #6

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).

Remove all units from the tent

PTRANS: Sealed and loaded on trailer equipped with dual generators; left Deadhorse bound for Fairbanks ~1130; ETA Fairbanks 2330.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up on site and maintaining temperature.

All other units: Loaded on trailers and transported to Carlile yard in Deadhorse to await transport down the haul road.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse.

Monitor freezer core store until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~Wed 30th Nov Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~Mon 5th Dec Begin core processing operations in SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 74	Tues 23rd Nov 22
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Demob - Day #7

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora).

PTRANS: en route to SLC

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

R17, G26, Services and Stores Container units : On road to Fairbanks and beyond

PCATS11, PCATS08 & CORING units: in Carlile yard, Deadhorse, ready for transportation.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse.

Monitor freezer core store until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~**Fri 2nd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Mon 5th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

The Geotek 40ft PTRANS unit contains 36 ~4 ft sections of pressure core held at near in situ pressure and temperature. This DOT certified unit is shown being loaded on an air ride trailer in snowy conditions at the rig site (Tuesday) ready for the 3500 mile road trip to Salt Lake City for further detailed processing.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02

GEOTEK DPR # 75

Thurs 24th Nov 22

Demob - Day #8

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

PTRANS: en route to SLC

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

R17, G26, Services and Stores Container units : On road to Fairbanks and beyond

PCATS11, PCATS08 & CORING units: in Carlile yard, Deadhorse, ready for transportation.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse.

Monitor freezer core store daily until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~**Sat 3rd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Mon 5th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

HAPPY THANKSGIVING

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 76	Fri 25th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #9

3 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

2 crew left Deadhorse today

PTRANS: en route to SLC

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

R17, G26, Services and Stores Container units : On road to Fairbanks and beyond

PCATS11, PCATS08 & CORING units: in Carlile yard, Deadhorse, ready for transportation.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse.

Monitor freezer core store daily until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~**Sun 4th Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Mon 5th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 77	Sat 26th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #10

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

2 more units left Deadhorse

PTRANS: en route to SLC

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

R17, G26, Services, PCATS08, CORING and Stores Container units : On road to Fairbanks and SLC

PCATS11: in Carlile yard, Deadhorse, ready for transportation.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse. Monitor freezer core store daily until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Sun 27th Nov PTRANS arrives SLC

~Sun 4th Dec Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~Mon 5th Dec Begin core processing operations in SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 78	Sun 27th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #11

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

PTRANS: delivered to SLC and powered on site at Geotek Coring.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

R17, G26, Services, PCATS08, CORING and Stores Container units : On road to Fairbanks and onward to SLC

PCATS11: in Carlile yard, Deadhorse, ready for transportation.

FORWARD LOOK

Liaise with Carlile to ensure timely shipping of all units from Deadhorse. Monitor freezer core store daily until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~**Sun 4th Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Thurs 8th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

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 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 79	Mon 28th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #12

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressure chambers being monitored. All storage chambers were received at high pressure. (One chamber had dropped a little to 100bar, but has now been pumped up.

PCATS11, started journey from Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

ALL OTHER UNITS : On road to Fairbanks and onward to SLC

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily until PTRANS chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

~Sun 4th Dec Units begin arriving in SLC

~Sun 4th Dec Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~Thurs 8th Dec Begin core processing operations in SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02

GEOTEK DPR # 80

Tues 29th Nov 22

Demob - Day #13

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperature.

ALL OTHER UNITS : On road to Fairbanks and onward to SLC

SLC core processing mob - Day #2

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressure chambers being monitored.

Diesel generator: on site and tested.

Portable restrooms/shower: tested ready for use.

G10 40ft unit: Fitted for USGS office and curation.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Feed power and utilities to: **TRIAX, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units.

~**Sat 3rd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Sun 4th Dec** Further units begin arriving in SLC

~**Thurs 8th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 81	Wed 30th Nov 22
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Demob - Day #14

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Waiting for for generator chasis. Performed successful lift test to check and confirm lifting capability of onsite loader

ALL OTHER UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing mob - Day #3

Continue with preparations with all equipment and units for science party visitors and pressure core processing.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Feed power and utilities to: **TRIAx, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units.

~**Sat 3rd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Sun 4th Dec** Further units begin arriving in SLC

~**Thurs 8th Dec** Begin core processing operations in SLC

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 82	Thurs 1st Dec 22
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Demob - Day #15

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Waiting for generator chassis.

ALL OTHER UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing operations - Day #4

Continue with preparations with all equipment and units for science party visitors and pressure core processing.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Feed power and utilities to: **TRIAx, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units.

~**Sat 3rd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Sun 4th Dec** Further units begin arriving in SLC

~**Thurs 8th Dec** Begin PCATS operations

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 83	Fri 2nd Dec 22
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Demob - Day #16

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Waiting for for generator chassis (Dec 3rd?).

ALL OTHER UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing operations - Day #5

Continue with preparations with all equipment and units for science party visitors and pressure core processing.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored / all good.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Feed power and utilities to: **TRIAX, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units and prepare for operations.

~**Sat 3rd Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Sun 4th Dec** Further units begin arriving in SLC

~**Thurs 8th Dec** Begin PCATS operations

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Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 84	Sat 3rd Dec 22
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Demob - Day #17

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Waiting for generator chassis (Dec 5th?).

ALL OTHER UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing operations - Day #6

Continue with preparations with all equipment and units for science party visitors and pressure core processing.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored / all good.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Feed power and utilities to: **TRIAX, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units and prepare for operations.

~**Sun 4th Dec** Further units begin arriving in SLC

~**Mon 5th Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~**Fri 9th Dec** Begin PCATS operations

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 85	Sun 4th Dec 22
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Demob - Day #18

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Waiting for for generator chassis (Dec 5th?).

ALL OTHER UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing operations - Day #7

Continue with preparations with all equipment and units for science party visitors and pressure core processing.

PTRANS: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored / all good.

FORWARD LOOK

Monitor freezer core store daily on site until **PTRANS** chassis with dual generator returns for pick up.

Prepare: **TRIAx, CHEM, PTRANS10** and **G10** units for operations.

Mon 5th Dec R17, CORING & PCATS8 arriving in SLC

Arrival of other units is currently delayed because of trucking available.

~**Mon 5th Dec** Last unit (Freezer with samples) leaves Deadhorse for road transport to SLC

~~**Mon 12th Dec** Begin PCATS cutting operations

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 86	Mon 5th Dec 22
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Demob - Day #19

1 crew on site housed at Hotel Aurora, Deadhorse.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Powered up at rig site and maintaining temperate. Loading on generator chassis (Dec 6th).

R17, CORING & PCATS8 arrived in SLC

Remaining UNITS : Transiting to SLC

SLC core processing operations - Day #8

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored / all good.

USGS + science party installed in G10

Planning and preparing all equipment for core analysis

FORWARD LOOK

Prepare: **TRIAx, CHEM, PTRANS10, G10 & R17/DEGASSING** units for operations.

Arrival of other units is currently delayed because of trucking/barge availability.

Tues 6th Dec **FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples leaves Deadhorse; arrives SLC ~**Mon 12th Dec**

~**Wed 14th Dec** Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
+1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 87	Tues 6th Dec 22
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Demob - Day #20

1 crew en route to SLC in Anchorage.

FREEZER CORE STORE: Loaded in morning on generator chassis - en route to SLC at 2200

Remaining UNITS : Transiting to SLC

Demob activities on ANS complete

SLC core processing operations - Day #9

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored / all good.

Planning and preparing all equipment for core analysis

FORWARD LOOK

Prepare: **TRIAx, CHEM, PTRANS10, G10 & R17/DEGASSING** units for operations.

Arrival of other units is currently delayed because of trucking/barge availability.

Mon 12th Dec **FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

12th - 15th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

~Wed 14th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 88	Wed 7th Dec 22
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DEMOB - Day #21

Demob activities on ANS complete

All UNITS : In SLC or in transiting to SLC

SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #10

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powererd

R17 DEGASSING: Waiting for power

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10: Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: In preparation.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut planning in process

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 12th Dec **FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

12th - 15th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

~Wed 14th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #11

10 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment.

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: In preparation for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,
 Detailed core cut planning in process.

FORWARD LOOK

?? Fri 9th Dec **STORES** unit arrives SLC ??

Mon 12th Dec **FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

12th - 15th Dec .. **remaining units arrive SLC**

~Wed 14th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #12

10 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed

TRIAX: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: In preparation for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut planning in process.

Scientists testing subsampling equipment and pressure core storage chambers

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 12th Dec **STORES & FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

13th - 14th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

Thurs 15th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #12

10 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: In preparation for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut planning in process.

Scientists testing subsampling equipment and pressure core storage chambers

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 12th Dec STORES & FREEZER unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

13th - 14th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

Thurs 15th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

USGS and NETL pressure core chambers being made ready for accepting pressure core subsamples when that are cut in PCATS.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 92	Sun 11th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #13

11 Geotek crew + 6 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed

TRIAX: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: In preparation for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut planning in process.

Scientists testing subsampling equipment and pressure core storage chambers

FORWARD LOOK

Tues 13th Dec **STORES & FREEZER** unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

13th - 14th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

Thurs 15th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

Unit R17 made ready for degassing operations and bio subsampling on the inside and cryo-freezing operations on the outside. Empty pressure changes ready for operations sitting outside.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #14

11 Geotek crew + 6 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: Ready for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In Transit

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: In Transit

PCATS11: In Transit

SERVICES: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut planning in process.

Scientists testing subsampling equipment and pressure core storage chambers

FORWARD LOOK

Tue 13th Dec STORES & FREEZER unit with conventionalized samples arrives SLC

13th - 14th Dec .. remaining units arrive SLC

Thurs 15th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

Geotek Coring Units lining up ready for action.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #15

11 Geotek crew + 6 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: Ready for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: Arrived SLC, Unloaded and prepped ready for use.

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: Arrived late in day

SERVICES: Arrived late in day

PCATS11: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,
 Detailed core cut planning in process.

Scientists testing subsampling equipment and pressure core storage chambers

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 14th Dec Unload and prep G26 and SERVICES UNITS

Begin conventionalized core splitting and description

14th Dec .. PCATS 11 arrives SLC

Thurs 15th Dec Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

Geotek Coring SERVICES unit arrives late in day ready for unloading tomorrow..

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 95	Wed 14th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #16

12 Geotek crew + 8 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36: on power at Geotek Coring in SLC - Pressures and temperature being monitored.

PTRANS 10: Ready for core transfer ops when powered

R17 DEGASSING: Powered - Testing equipment. Bio sample transfer station installed - waiting for transfer chamber

TRIAx: Equipment testing in progress

G10 - 40': Visiting scientist office in use.

CHEMISTRY: Ready for pore water squeezing.

SAMPLE FREEZER: In use.

G26 ANALYSIS CURATION: Arrived late in day

SERVICES: Arrived late in day - unloaded - in use

PCATS11: In Transit

STORES: In Transit

Cryo Freezing, Core Splitting/Cutting, Imaging equipment in preparation,

Detailed core cut plan ready

Scientists - working on bag samples

FORWARD LOOK

Thursday 15th Dec

Begin conventionalized core splitting and description

Unload and set up **PCATS 11**

Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

Pressure core chamber .. Christmas Trees

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 96	Thurs 15th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #17

12 Geotek crew + 8 visiting scientists on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit

ALL OTHER UNITS - In use

PCATS11: Arrived - Unloaded - connected to power, air and water. The unit was very cold and took a long time to warm up to a safe working temperature. PCATS analysis, cutting and transfer operations to begin Fri 16th.

Bio transfer chamber delivered tested (including handling) ready for operations.

Began splitting cleaning and imaging conventionalized cores.

Bonus logging with Magnetic Susceptibility enabled/initiated

FORWARD LOOK

Friday 16th Dec

Begin 24/7 PCATS cutting operations early morning.

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

USGS Pressure Chambers ready for samples

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 97	Fri 16th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #18

9 Geotek crew + 9 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL & JAPAN) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Mon 19th Dec)

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

- Core# 01P-4 samples: USGS
- Core# 15P-2 samples: USGS
- Core# 02P-3 samples: 3 x CRYO, USGS, BIO
- Core# 05P-4 samples: 2 x CRYO, NETL, 2 x BIO, R degas
- Core# 22P-1 samples: Q degas, 2 x CRYO, R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Friday 16th Dec

Continue 24/7 core processing

~Wed 21st Dec Finish core processing operations.

The Japanese Bio transfer chamber connected to PCATS for sample transfer. The sample is subsequently connected to a nitrogen glove box in the R17 dewgassing van for clean subsampling

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #19

9 Geotek crew + 9 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL & JAPAN) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Mon 19th Dec ???)

Core processing going well and proceeding on all fronts. Some sampling and analysis operations waiting for some equipment in the delayed **STORES** unit.

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

- Core# 18P-2 samples:** Q degas, USGS, 2 x R degas
- Core# 17P-3 samples:** 2 x BIO, R degas
- Core# 21P-1 samples:** 2 x Q degas, USGS, R degas
- Core# 15P-3 samples:** 3 x CRYO, NETL, USGS, R degas
- Core# 15P-1 samples:** Q degas, CRYO, BIO, R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Continue 24/7 core processing
 ~Thurs 22nd Dec
 Finish core processing operations.

A selection of pressure core Chambers (USGS, NETL & Geotek) in cold storage either holding samples or ready for sample transfer.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 99	Sun18th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #20

11 Geotek crew + 9 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL & JAPAN) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery?)

Core processing went well and proceeding on all fronts. Some sampling and analysis operations waiting for some equipment in the delayed **STORES** unit.

Note: at the end of the day we had a problem with the X-Ray system in PCATS which is currently under investigation. PCATS processing paused.

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

- Core# 01P-1 samples: CRYO, Q degas, R degas**
- Core# 20P-1 samples: 3 x CRYO, BIO, Q degas, R degas**
- Core# 04P-2 samples: 3 x CRYO, NETL, USGS, 2 x TRIAX, R degas**
- Core# 07P-1 samples: 3 x CRYO, 2 x Q degas, BIO, 2 x R degas**

FORWARD LOOK

Look to resolve the PCATS X ray issues and then continue 24/7 core processing

~Thurs 22nd Dec

Finish core processing operations.

Cryo-Freeze training. Mike demonstrates to Junior the safety requirements when dealing with high pressure liquids and gases as well as how to handle the liquid nitrogen.

The PCATS cutting program calls for 40 cryo samples.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 100	Mon19th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #21

11 Geotek crew + 9 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL & JAPAN) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Friday 23rd Dec)

PCATS operations paused and serviced.

All other core processing proceeding on all fronts. Some sampling and analysis operations waiting for some equipment in the delayed **STORES** unit.

Visiting scientists unavailable after 21st Dec. This together with delays in equipment shipping have led to the decision today to pause the SLC Core Processing operation over the Christmas and New Year period. This will involve a controlled shutdown of operations this week. Geotek will resume operations on 3rd Jan with visiting scientists arriving from the 9th Jan.

FORWARD LOOK

~**Tues/Wed 20th/21st Dec:** Finish core processing operations on all cores cut to date.

~ **Thurs 22nd Dec:** partial demob activities

~ **Fri 23rd Dec:** Final STORES unit arrives at SLC - Unload/unpack critical items.

Tues 3rd Jan: partial remob and begin remaining core processing operations.

Mon 9th Jan: visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

1st Triax samples cut in PCATS and loaded into Triax transfer cells. The transfer cells contain the 'bottom cap' housing the porous disk enabling the sample to be extruded from the liner into the test cell before the triaxial stress and permeability tests are run.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02

GEOTEK DPR # 101

Tues 20th Dec 22

SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #22

10 Geotek crew + 7 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL & JAPAN) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Friday 23rd Dec)

PCATS operations paused and serviced.

All other core processing proceeding on all fronts. Some sampling and analysis operations waiting for equipment in the delayed STORES unit. All conventionalized cores to date are split. All cryo samples cut to date have been cryofrozen.

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 21st Dec: Finish core processing operations on all cores cut to date.

~ **Thurs 22nd Dec:** partial demob activities

~ **Fri 23rd Dec:** Final STORES unit arrives at SLC - Unload/unpack critical items and make ready.

Tues 3rd Jan: partial remob and begin remaining core processing operations.

Mon 9th Jan: visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

All remaining pressurized core samples are being stored in a single reefer van so they can be easily monitored during the core processing pause over the holidays.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02

GEOTEK DPR # 102

Wed 21st Dec 22

SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #23

9 Geotek crew + 4 visiting scientists (USGS, NETL) on site

PTRANS 36 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Friday 23rd Dec)

All other core processing completed as far as possible and all empty chambers made ready for the resumption of PCATS operation on the 3rd Jan.

Some sampling and analysis operations waiting for equipment in the delayed **STORES** unit.

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 22nd Dec: partial demob activities. Some further high resolution bonus core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF to be made on selected core sections.

Fri 23rd Dec: Final STORES unit arrives at SLC - Unload/unpack critical items and make ready. + some further high resolution bonus core logging

Sat 24th Dec: Conduct gas analysis on all samples collected to date + some further high resolution bonus core logging

Tues 3rd Jan: re-mob activities and begin remaining core processing operations in PCATS.

Mon 9th Jan: visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** visiting scientists finish all operations.

Bill topping up the dewars containing the cryofrozen samples.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 103	Thurs 22nd Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #24

3 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: In Transit (anticipated delivery Friday 23rd Dec)

Partial demob and preparations made for resumption of core processing in January.

High resolution core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF on selected core sections.

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 23rd Dec: Final STORES unit arrives at SLC - Unload/unpack critical items and make ready.

Further high resolution XRF and MS core logging on selected samples.

Sat 24th Dec: Conduct gas analysis on all samples collected to date + some further high resolution bonus core logging

Tues 3rd Jan: re-mob activities and begin remaining core processing operations in PCATS.

Mon 9th Jan: visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** visiting scientists finish all operations.

Conventionalized core sections being logged on the Geotek BoxScan. This instrument is used to obtain the high resolution images but can also be used to obtain other high resolution data including; XRF elemental data, infrared spectroscopy and magnetic susceptibility. Currently collecting XRF and MS data at a 2mm spatial resolution.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 104	Fri 23rd Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #25

5 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

STORES: The last container unit finally arrived in SLC. It was partially unloaded to retrieve the GC components required for the gas analysis.

GC set up, calibrated and gas analysis from the degassing experiments began.

Preparations made for resumption of core processing in January.

High resolution core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF on selected core sections.

FORWARD LOOK

Sat 24th Dec: Finish gas analysis on all samples collected to date + some further high resolution core logging

Tues 3rd Jan: re-mob activities and begin remaining core processing operations in PCATS.

Mon 9th Jan: visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ Fri 20th Jan: visiting scientists finish all operations.

The final STORES unit arrives and is unloaded at Geotek Coring in Salt Lake City .

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 105	Sat 24th Dec 22
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #26

2 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperature being monitored.

GC gas analysis from the degassing experiments to date completed..

High resolution core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF on selected core sections.

FORWARD LOOK

Sun 25th Dec - Mon 2nd Jan: Pressure and Conventionalized Cores will be monitored during the temporary shutdown of core processing operations. No DPRs will be issued during this period.

Tues 3rd Jan: re-mob activities and begin remaining core processing operations in PCATS for Geotek crew.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ Fri 20th Jan: Visiting scientists finish all operations.

**MERRY
 CHRISTMAS
 &
 HAPPY NEW YEAR**

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 106	Tues 3rd Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #27

6 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperatures of pressure were monitored over the holiday period - all good.

Remobilize/prepare for continuing the core analysis program. PCATS and other vans being prepared for start of cutting operations tomorrow.

Restart high resolution core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF on selected core sections (20P-4).

FORWARD LOOK

Wed Jan 23 Begin cutting pressure cores and preparing all other equipment for operations.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #28

6 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER on power - all pressures and temperatures of pressure were monitored over the holiday period - all good.

Cut 2 core sections - see below.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, using magnetic susceptibility and XRF on selected core sections **Finished core 20P-4.**

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 05P-3 samples: NETL, R degas

Core# 14P-2 samples: 5 x CRYO, USGS, R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Thurs 5th Jan. Continue high res core logging and preparing all other equipment for operations.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

~ Fri 20th Jan: Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #29

7 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all pressures and temperatures of samples monitored.

Cryo core sample 14P-2F lost pressure and will be conventionalised

Cut 1 core section in PCATS - see below.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, MS zero problem - rescan tomorrow.

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 08P-1 samples: CRYO, BIO, 2 x Q degas, 2 x R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Fri 6th Jan. Continue core cutting in PCATS (07P) and high res core logging and preparing all other equipment for operations next week.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing.

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 109	Fri 6th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #30

7 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all pressures and temperatures of samples monitored.

Cut 1 core section in PCATS - see below.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, started **Core 12P-1-2**

Prepared 6 Triax cones ready for PCATS transfer next week

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 07P-2 samples: CRYO, USGS, 2 x Q degas, R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Sat/Sun 7th/8th Jan. Continue with Box scan high res core logging and monitoring all core samples.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing. Resume PCATS operations.

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

GEOTEK CORING Inc
3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
+1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 110	Sat 7th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #31

2 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 12P-1-2** , started **Core 11P-1-2**

FORWARD LOOK

Sun 8th Jan. Continue with Box scan high res core logging and monitoring all core samples.

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing. Resume PCATS operations.

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 111	Sun 8th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #32

2 Geotek crew + 0 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 11P-1-2** , started **Core 10P-1-2**

FORWARD LOOK

Mon 9th Jan: Visiting scientists arrive to finish core processing. Resume PCATS operations and continue with Box scan high res core logging and monitoring all core samples..

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 112	Mon 9th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #33

7 Geotek crew + 3 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Cryofreezing, degassing and pore water squeezer all back up and running as required.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 10P-1-2**, started **Core 13P-1-2**

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 23P-1 samples: CRYO, 2 x Q degas

FORWARD LOOK

Tues 10th Jan: Continue with both PCATS processing and Box scan high res core logging and monitoring all core samples..

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 113	Tues 10th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #34

5 Geotek crew + 6 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Cryofreezing, degassing and pore water squeezer all working.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 13P-1-2**, started **Core 13P-3**

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 18P-1 samples: 4 x CRYO, BIO, R degas

Core# 16P-1 samples: NETL, 4 x CRYO, TRIAX, R degas

FORWARD LOOK

Wed 11th Jan: Continue with both PCATS processing and Box scan high res core logging and monitoring all core samples..

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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 3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
 Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
 +1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 114	Wed 11th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #35

5 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Other processes continue.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 13P-3**, started **Core 06P-1,2**

PRESSURE CORE SECTIONS PROCESSED:

Core# 19P-2 samples: 2 x CRYO, USGS, BIO, 2 x TRIAX, R degas

Core# 17P-5 samples: 2 x TRIAX, 5 x CRYO, R degas

Note: All pressure core samples destined to be processed in PCATS have been completed.

Note: All pressure core samples destined for Cryofreezing have now been processed.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue assisting visiting scientists with all aspects of core processing and monitoring all core samples..

?? Transfer and ship 7 AIST pressure core samples in PTRANS10

~ **Fri 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists finish all operations.

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 115	Thurs 12th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #36

3 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, completed **Core 06P-1-2**

Packaged all USGS & NETL pressure cores and cryo samples for transport Began shipping USGS equipment

FORWARD LOOK

Ship out all USGS AND NETL pressure cores and cryo samples as directed

Continue BoxScan and core splitting streams

Jan 18th ship Bio chamber and glove box out

~**Fri. 20th Jan**: Visiting scientists core processing complete

Continue monitoring Triax and AIST storage chambers Shipment to AIST

Core freezer hold for USGS

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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 116	Fri 13th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #37

3 Geotek crew + 5 visiting scientists on site

Reefer 17 & SAMPLE FREEZER all sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

PCATS Operations: Complete: We sub sampled 22 pressure cores in PCATS at SLC performing 98 successful cuts and sample transfers.

Boxscan High resolution core logging, continued.....

Loaded all NETL pressure cores and cryo samples in refrigerated truck.

Loaded all USGS pressure cores in refrigerated truck. Other samples were shipped via FedEx

Microbio samples shipped to Japan.

Although some operations continue next week this was the last day for most of the visiting scientists in SLC. It was fun - Thank you.

FORWARD LOOK

Continue BoxScan and core splitting streams

Jan 18th ship Bio chamber and glove box out

~**Fri. 20th Jan:** Visiting scientists core processing complete

Continue monitoring Triax and AIST storage chambers Shipment to AIST

Core freezer hold for USGS

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 117	14th - 20th Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #38-45

7 Geotek crew + 1 visiting scientist on site

Remaining sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Glove Box shipped

PCATS Triax - 19P-2b loaded and extruded into TRIAX and testing began

Boxscan High resolution core logging, core sections scanned...

09P-1, 20P-3, 07P-1c, 1g, 2e, 2b, 08P-1c, 23P-1a,1c, 01P-1a, 02P-1, 15P-1d, 16P-1, 17P-4, 05P-2.

FORWARD LOOK

Remaining Tasks

Ship out cryoport dewars as directed Jan 23

Continue BoxScan and core splitting streams

~Sun. 22nd Jan.: Processing complete

Continue monitoring and testing Triax samples

Ship AIST storage chambers

Core freezer hold for USGS until mid to late Feb

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
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ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 118	21 - 27 Jan 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING- Day #46-52

1 visiting scientist on site (departed 23rd Jan)

All visiting scientist have completed on site activities in SLC

Remaining sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

PCATS Triax - 19P-2b completed - 4P-2d in progress

Boxscan High resolution core logging, core sections scanned...

18P-1d, 2c, 20P-1f, 07P-2b, 08P-1b

FORWARD LOOK

Remaining Tasks

Continue Triax testing

Ship cryoport dewars as directed

Ship Bio Chamber to AIST

Ship AIST storage chambers

Core freezer hold for USGS until mid to late Feb

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3350 West Directors Row, Ste. 600
Salt Lake City, Utah 84104 USA
+1 385-528-2536 | geotekcoring.com | info@geotekcoring.com

ACES - GDW - HYDRATE-02	GEOTEK DPR # 119	28 Jan -4 - 17 Feb 23
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SLC CORE PROCESSING

Remaining sample pressures and temperatures monitored.

Cryoport dewars shipped

Bio chamber shipped

Core freezer loaded

PCATS Triax - completed 17th Feb - A separate data report will be issued.

AIST storage chambers (7) - Shipped in PTRANS10 from SLC on 13/02/23

FORWARD LOOK

Remaining Tasks

Core freezer hold for USGS until mid to late Feb

Water samples to be shipped to USGS

AIST cores - depart on container vessel from Tacoma 22nd Feb - delivery to AIST estimated early April.

FINAL DPR

Appendix E: HPTC Run Reports

GEOTEK CORING Inc

3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

+1 385-528-2536 | info@geotekcoring.com | geotekcoring.com

CORE NO.: HY02-01P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-28		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		13:30	
START DEPTH:		2,369 ft		END DEPTH:		2,379 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:		16:24		CORING END TIME:		16:39	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	63 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 2,990 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	2.0 tons	80	SPEED: 150 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	18:45	TIME OUT:	17:15
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				4:47		TIME ON DECK: 18:17	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				40.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:15	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-10-28		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,220 psi	
		TIME: 17:45					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED			
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>					
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-10-28	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 20:05	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		TOTAL CORE RECOVERY: 8.06 ft	
						RECOVERY PERCENTAGE: 81%	
NOTES:							

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3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

+1 385-528-2536 | info@geotekcoring.com | geotekcoring.com

CORE NO.: HY02-02P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-28		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		22:45	
START DEPTH:		2,379.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,389.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				01:10		CORING END TIME:	
						01:34	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	60 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	3.0 tons	60	SPEED:		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	03:13	TIME OUT:	03:23
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				5:48		TIME ON DECK:	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				25.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:24	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-29	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,150 psi
	TIME:	03:43		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	N/A	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:
	TIME:	N/A		2022-10-29
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	10.00 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	100%	
NOTES:				

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CORE NO.: HY02-03P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-29		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		04:24	
START DEPTH:		2,389.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,399.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				06:23		CORING END TIME:	
						06:38	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	60 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	3.0 tons	60	SPEED:		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	08:36	TIME OUT:	08:46
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:52		TIME ON DECK:	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				40.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:15	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-29	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,247 psi
	TIME:	09:01		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-10-29	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:
	TIME:	09:30		TIME:
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	3.44 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	34%	
NOTES:				

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3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-04P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-29		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		10:05	
START DEPTH:		2,399.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,409.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				12:24		CORING END TIME:	
						12:36	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 3,200 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	6.0 tons	60	SPEED: 320 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	14:16	TIME OUT:	14:35
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:47		TIME ON DECK: 13:52	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				50.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:12	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-29	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,300 psi
	TIME:	15:09		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-10-29	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE: 2022-10-29
	TIME:	15:21		TIME: 17:00
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	4.69 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	47%	
NOTES:				

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CORE NO.: HY02-05P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-30		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		10:36		
START DEPTH:		2,409.0 ft	END DEPTH:		2,419.0 ft	BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft
CORING START TIME:				12:25		CORING END TIME:		12:37
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL			
	CORING:	17 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:			2,800 lbs
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.7 tons	60	SPEED:			225 ft/min
	P.O.O.H.:	2 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	N/A	TIME OUT:		N/A
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:22		TIME ON DECK:		13:58
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				50.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:		0:12
NOTES: Picked up WOB 0.2 ft. prior to recorded start depth								

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-30	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,200 psi	
	TIME:	14:43			
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-10-30	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:	2022-10-30
	TIME:	15:59		TIME:	1111
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.10 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		101%	
NOTES:					

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-06P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-30		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		15:41	
START DEPTH:		2,419.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,429.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				17:04		CORING END TIME:	
				17:04		17:27	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	22 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 3,416 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	10.0 tons	60	SPEED: 220 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	2 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:18		TIME ON DECK: 18:59	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				26.1 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:23	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-10-30		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,150 psi	
		TIME: 17:40					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-10-30	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 19:55	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		7.61 ft	
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		76%	
NOTES:							

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-07P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-30		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		20:31	
START DEPTH:		2,429.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,439.3 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.30 ft	
CORING START TIME:				21:59		CORING END TIME:	
						22:05	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	15 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	10.0 tons	60 rpm	4,100 lbs		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	23:45	TIME OUT:	01:55
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				2:44		TIME ON DECK:	
						23:15	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				103.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:06	
NOTES: Picked up WOB 0.3 ft. prior to recorded start depth							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-31	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,210 psi
	TIME:	02:19		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	N/A	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:
	TIME:	N/A		10/31/2022
			TIME:	02:40
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	10.3 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	100%	
NOTES:				

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-08P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-31		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		02:27	
START DEPTH:		2,439.3 ft		END DEPTH:		2,449.5 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.2 ft	
CORING START TIME:				04:24		CORING END TIME:	
						04:39	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 4,044 lbs		
	PULLING:	21 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 245 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	06:22	TIME OUT:	07:37
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:26		TIME ON DECK:	
						05:53	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				40.8 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:15	
NOTES: 7:57 Power to rig went down; Picked up WOB 0.2 ft. prior to recorded start depth							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-31	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,090 psi
	TIME:	08:20		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	N/A	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE: 2022-10-31
	TIME:	N/A		TIME: 08:32
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	4.60 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	45%	
NOTES:				

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3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-09P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-31		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		08:06		
START DEPTH:		2,449.5 ft	END DEPTH:		2,459.5 ft	BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft
CORING START TIME:				10:36		CORING END TIME:		10:47
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL			
	CORING:	49 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:			3,900 lbs
	PULLING:	21 gpm	3.5 tons	60	SPEED:			250 ft/min
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	12:55	TIME OUT:	14:30	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				4:16		TIME ON DECK:		12:22
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				54.5 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:		0:11
NOTES:								

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE:		2022-10-31		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,150 psi			
		TIME:		15:01							
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE:		N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE:		2022-10-31	
		TIME:		N/A				TIME:		15:20	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		9.74 ft	
								RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		97%	
NOTES:											

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-10P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-31		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		16:29	
START DEPTH:		2,459.5 ft		END DEPTH:		2,469.5 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.0 ft	
CORING START TIME:				18:05		CORING END TIME:	
				18:05		18:30	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 7,000 lbs		
	PULLING:	21 gpm	6.0 tons	60	SPEED: 220 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	20:11	TIME OUT:	21:57
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:16		TIME ON DECK:	
						19:45	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				24.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:25	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-10-31	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,150 psi
	TIME:	22:20		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-10-31	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE: 2022-11-01
	TIME:	22:37		TIME: 01:08
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	8.46 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	85%	
NOTES:				

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CORE NO.: HY02-11P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-10-31		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		22:50	
START DEPTH:		2,469.5 ft		END DEPTH:		2,479.6 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.1 ft	
CORING START TIME:				00:36		CORING END TIME:	
						00:50	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	46 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,800 lbs		
	PULLING:	21 gpm	3.0 tons	60	SPEED: 245 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	03:00	TIME OUT:	03:19
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				4:29		TIME ON DECK:	
						02:23	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				43.3 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:14	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-01		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,100 psi	
		TIME: 03:49					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-01	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 04:03	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		9.22 ft	
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		91%	
NOTES:							

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CORE NO.: HY02-12P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-03		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		08:51	
START DEPTH:		2,873.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,883.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				11:42		CORING END TIME:	
						11:53	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	60 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:		
	PULLING:	21 gpm	5 tons	60	SPEED:		
	P.O.O.H.:	0 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	N/A	TIME OUT:	
						N/A	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				5:20		TIME ON DECK:	
						14:11	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				54.5 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:11	
NOTES: Mud out temperature was approximately 50°F prior to cutting the core. Company man D. Hammons made the decision to core ahead.							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-03		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,200 psi	
		TIME: 14:59					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-03	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 15:14	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		8.79 ft	
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		88%	
NOTES:							

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CORE NO.: HY02-13P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-03		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		16:06	
START DEPTH:		2,883.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,893.1 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.10 ft	
CORING START TIME:				17:58		CORING END TIME:	
				18:08			
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	12 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 6,000 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:44		TIME ON DECK: 19:50	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				60.6 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:10	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-03		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,225 psi	
		TIME: 20:45					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-03	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 20:47	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		11.09 ft	
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		110%	
NOTES:							

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-14P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-03		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		21:39	
START DEPTH:		2,893.1 ft		END DEPTH:		2,903.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		9.90 ft	
CORING START TIME:				23:40		CORING END TIME:	
						23:56	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 12,000 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	50	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				4:31		TIME ON DECK:	
						02:10	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				37.1 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:16	
NOTES: Significant overpull. Several attempts were made to pull the tool smoothly; tool released with a slight upward jar							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-04		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,200 psi	
		TIME: 03:00					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: 2022-11-04		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-04	
		TIME: 03:12				TIME: 04:15	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.50 ft		
			RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		106%		
NOTES:							

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-15P

REVISION NO.: 1

**CORING RUN REPORT
ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT**

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-04		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		03:53	
START DEPTH:		2,903.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,912.8 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		9.80 ft	
CORING START TIME:				5:35		CORING END TIME:	
						05:50	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	52 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,800 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	4 tons	60	SPEED: 250 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	0	TIME OUT: 0	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:43		TIME ON DECK:	
						07:36	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				39.2 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:15	
NOTES: Smooth coring run. Tagged the formation at 2902.7ft. Cored 10ft.							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-11-04	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,090 psi
	TIME:	08:26		
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-11-04	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:
	TIME:	08:49		2022-11-05
			TIME:	12:00
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	10.66 ft	
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	109%	
NOTES:				

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-16P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-04		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		09:17	
START DEPTH:		2,912.8 ft		END DEPTH:		2,922.6 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		9.80 ft	
CORING START TIME:				11:45		CORING END TIME:	
						12:04	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,800 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	4.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	35 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				19:00		TIME ON DECK: 14:10	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				30.9 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:19	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-04		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,150 psi	
		TIME: 14:57					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-04	
		TIME: N/A				TIME: 15:13	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		9.51 ft	
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		97%	
NOTES:							

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CORE NO.: HY02-17P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-04		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		16:17	
START DEPTH:		2,923.6 ft		END DEPTH:		2,933.5 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		9.90 ft	
CORING START TIME:				18:09		CORING END TIME:	
				18:09		18:23	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm		DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL	
	CORING:	56 gpm		W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:	
	PULLING:	0 gpm		5.0 tons		3,500 lbs	
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm		COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	TIME OUT:	200 ft/min
				N/A		N/A	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:49		TIME ON DECK:	
						20:06	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				42.4 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING:	
						0:14	
NOTES: Immediately prior to coring, pumps were taken to 500 gpm by mistake; a decision was made to attempt to run the core with the understanding that it would be aborted in case of low ROP. Top drive stopped rotating at 2928.1, weight on bit was maintained and rotation was restarted but at a lower rate (50 rpm).							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE:		2022-11-04		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,300 psi	
		TIME:		21:03					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE:		2022-11-04		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE:	
		TIME:		21:24				2022-11-04	
						TIME:		11:21	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		9.81 ft	
						RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		99%	
NOTES:									

POST-CORING TOOL ANALYSIS & REBUILD (AS REQUIRED)

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CORE NO.: HY02-18P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-04		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		22:03	
START DEPTH:		2,933.5 ft		END DEPTH:		2,943.5 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				12:01		CORING END TIME:	
						12:16	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm		DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL	
	CORING:	56 gpm		W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,850 lbs	
	PULLING:	0 gpm		5.0 tons		SPEED: 220 ft/min	
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm		COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				-20:23		TIME ON DECK: 01:40	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				40.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:15	
NOTES: Stiffer drilling at 2940 ft; ROP decreased to 19 ft/min for 1-2 minutes.							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-11-05		GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,170 psi			
	TIME:	02:20						
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-11-05		TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:	2022-11-05		
	TIME:	02:34			TIME:	04:45		
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:				6.73 ft		
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:				67%
NOTES: Difficulty pulling into PCATS initially. Waited until all other core had been processed to attempt again; this time pulled without issue.								

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CORE NO.:	HY02-19P	REVISION NO.:	1
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CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:	2022-11-05	TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:	03:05			
START DEPTH:	2,943.5 ft	END DEPTH:	2,953.0 ft			
		BIT ADVANCEMENT:	9.50 ft			
CORING START TIME:	04:35	CORING END TIME:	04:41			
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS	WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	32 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL:	5,400 lbs
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED:	220 ft/min
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	N/A	TIME OUT:
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:			3:12	TIME ON DECK:	06:17	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):			95.0 ft/min	TOTAL TIME CORING:	0:06	
NOTES:	Tagged formation at 2943.1. Ended core run .1 early at 2953.0 based on company man approval.					

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE:	2022-11-05	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,200 psi	
	TIME:	07:01			
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE:	2022-11-05	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE:	2022-11-05
	TIME:	07:14		TIME:	10:29
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:	9.51 ft		
		RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:	100%		
NOTES:					

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CORE NO.: HY02-20P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-05		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		08:17	
START DEPTH:		2,953.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,963.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				11:44		CORING END TIME:	
						11:54	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	32 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 6,300 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	42 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	14:27	TIME OUT:	15:14
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				5:38		TIME ON DECK: 13:55	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				60.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:10	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-05		GAUGE PRESSURE: 2,200 psi	
		TIME: 15:52			
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: N/A		TRANSFERED TO PCATS DATE: 2022-11-05	
		TIME: N/A		TIME: 16:08	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.27 ft
			RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		103%
NOTES:					

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CORE NO.: HY02-21P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-05		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		16:51	
START DEPTH:		2,963.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,973.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				18:52		CORING END TIME:	
				19:00			
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	56 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 6,000 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:42		TIME ON DECK: 20:33	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				75.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:08	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-05		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,150 psi	
		TIME: 21:26					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: 2022-11-05		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-05	
		TIME: 21:37				TIME: 2243	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.59 ft		
			RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		106%		
NOTES:							

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3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

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CORE NO.: HY02-22P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-05		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		22:10	
START DEPTH:		2,973.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,983.0 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.00 ft	
CORING START TIME:				23:40		CORING END TIME:	
				23:48			
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	46 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,900 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A		
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:09		TIME ON DECK: 01:19	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				75.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:08	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE:	2022-11-06	GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,000 psi	
		TIME:	01:02				
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE:	2022-11-06	TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE:	2022-11-06
		TIME:	01:13			TIME:	05:40
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.27 ft		
				RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		103%	
NOTES:							

GEOTEK CORING Inc

3350 West Directors Row, Suite 600
Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

+1 385-528-2536 | info@geotekcoring.com | geotekcoring.com

CORE NO.: HY02-23P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-06		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		01:38	
START DEPTH:		2,983.0 ft		END DEPTH:		2,993.1 ft	
				BIT ADVANCEMENT:		10.10 ft	
CORING START TIME:				03:46		CORING END TIME:	
						03:57	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm		DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL	
	CORING:	42 gpm		W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,700 lbs	
	PULLING:	0 gpm		5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 200 ft/min	
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm		COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN: N/A	TIME OUT: N/A	
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:59		TIME ON DECK: 05:37	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				55.1 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:11	
NOTES: Stiffer drilling at ~2983.5 ROP decreased to 19. WOB briefly up to ~12,000.							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR		DATE: 2022-11-06		GAUGE PRESSURE:		2,200 psi	
		TIME: 06:03					
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				
PLACED IN ICE BATH		DATE: 2022-11-06		TRANSFERED TO PCATS		DATE: 2022-11-06	
		TIME: 06:18				TIME: 15:25	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		9.58 ft		
			RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		95%		
NOTES:							

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Salt Lake City, Utah, 84104 USA

+1 385-528-2536 | info@geotekcoring.com | geotekcoring.com

CORE NO.: HY02-24P

REVISION NO.: 1

CORING RUN REPORT ALASKA 2022 METHANE HYDRATE PROJECT

CORING RUN

DATE:		2022-11-06		TOOL DEPLOYMENT TIME:		07:21	
START DEPTH:	2,993.1 ft	END DEPTH:	3,003.0 ft	BIT ADVANCEMENT:		9.90 ft	
CORING START TIME:		09:02		CORING END TIME:		09:11	
FLOW RATES	RUNNING IN:	126 gpm	DRILL PARAMETERS		WIRELINE PULL		
	CORING:	53 gpm	W.O.B.:	R.P.M.:	MAX OVERPULL: 5,900 lbs		
	PULLING:	0 gpm	5.0 tons	60	SPEED: 250 ft/min		
	P.O.O.H.:	21 gpm	COLD SHUCK:	TIME IN:	10:58	TIME OUT:	15:50
TOTAL TIME IN HOLE:				3:17		TIME ON DECK: 10:38	
R.O.P. (CALCULATED):				66.0 ft/min		TOTAL TIME CORING: 0:09	
NOTES:							

CORE TRANSFER & RECOVERY

RECEIVED FROM RIG FLOOR	DATE: 2022-11-06	GAUGE PRESSURE:	2,200 psi	
	TIME: 16:32			
SHUTOFF VALVE CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PRESSURE DRAINED; DRAIN VALVE AND PORT CLOSED <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			
PLACED IN ICE BATH	DATE: 2022-11-06	TRANSFERED TO PCATS	DATE: 2022-11-06	
	TIME: 16:43		TIME: 12:32	
SUCCESSFUL PRESSURIZED TRANSFER? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TOTAL CORE RECOVERY:		10.59 ft	
	RECOVERY PERCENTAGE:		107%	
NOTES:				

Appendix F: HPTC Pressure-Temperature Diagrams

HY02-01P Plug PT record 28 Oct 2022

HY02-01P Plug P vs T

HY02-01P Rabbit PT record 28 Oct-1 Nov 2022

HY02-01P Rabbit P vs T

HY02-02P Plug PT record 28-29 Oct 2022

HY02-02P Plug P vs T

HY02-02P Rabbit PT record 28 Oct-1 Nov 2022

HY02-02P Rabbit P vs T

HY02-03P Plug PT record 29 Oct 2022

HY02-03P Plug P vs T

HY02-04P Plug PT record 29 Oct 2022

HY02-04P Plug P vs T

HY02-04P Rabbit PT record 29 Oct 2022

HY02-04P Rabbit P vs T

HY02-05P Plug PT record 30 Oct 2022

HY02-05P Plug P vs T

HY02-06P Plug PT record 30 Oct 2022

HY02-06P Plug P vs T

HY02-07P Plug PT record 30-31 Oct 2022

HY02-07P Plug P vs T

HY02-08P Plug PT record 31 Oct 2022

HY02-08P Plug P vs T

HY02-09P Plug PT record 31 Oct 2022

HY02-09P Plug P vs T

HY02-10P Plug PT record 31 Oct 2022

HY02-10P Plug P vs T

HY02-11P Plug PT record 31 Oct-1 Nov 2022

HY02-11P Plug P vs T

HY02-12P Plug PT record 3 Nov 2022

HY02-12P Plug P vs T

HY02-13P Plug PT record 04 Nov 2022

HY02-13P Plug P vs T

HY02-14P Plug PT record 3-4 Nov 2022

HY02-14P Plug P vs T

HY02-15P Plug PT record 04 Nov 2022

HY02-15P Plug P vs T

HY02-16P Plug PT record 04 Nov 2022

HY02-16P Plug P vs T

HY02-17P Plug PT record 05 Nov 2022

HY02-17P Plug P vs T

HY02-18P Plug PT record 05-06 Nov 2022

HY02-18P Plug P vs T

HY02-18P Plug PT record 05-06 Nov 2022

HY02-18P Plug P vs T

HY02-19P Plug PT record 05 Nov 2022

HY02-19P Plug P vs T

HY02-20P Plug PT record 5 Nov 2022

HY02-20P Plug P vs T

HY02-21P Plug PT record 05-06 Nov 2022

HY02-21P Plug P vs T

HY02-22P Plug PT record 06 Nov 2022

HY02-22P Plug P vs T

HY02-23P Plug PT record 06 Nov 2022

HY02-23P Plug P vs T

HY02-24P Plug PT record 6-7 Nov 2022

HY02-24P Plug P vs T

Appendix G: X-ray Images

HY02-01P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-01P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-06P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P X-Radiograph 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P X-Radiograph 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

Appendix H: X-ray CL Images

HY02-01P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-01P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-06P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P Laminography 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P Laminography 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

Appendix I: X-ray CT Images

HY02-01P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-01P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-03P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-04P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-14P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P-Rescan CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-19P-Rescan CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P CT 0deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P CT 90deg

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

Appendix J: Q-Degas Tables

HY02-01P-1a Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.6	17.6	0.00	82		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.6	12.7	0.00	82		0.01	0%	0.38
3	12.7	6.8	0.00	82		0.02	0%	0.34
4	6.8	2.2	0.00	82		0.03	0%	0.18
5	2.2	0.3	0.00	82		0.04	0%	0.04
6	0.5	0.1	0.70	82	1 + BAG	0.51	100%	0.96

HY02-2P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.4	14.4	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.4	4.5	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.00
3	4.5	2.5	0.00	61		0.01	0%	0.00
4	2.5	1.6	0.00	61		0.01	0%	0.00
5	1.7	1.0	0.00	61		0.01	0%	0.00
6	1.0	0.5	0.00	61		0.01	0%	0.01
7	0.5	0.3	0.00	61		0.02	0%	0.01
8	0.3	0.1	0.00	61		0.05	0%	0.02
9	0.1	0.1	0.07	61	1 + BAG	0.08	100%	0.09

HY02-02P-3 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	21.4	21.4	0.00	95		0.00	n/a	0.00
2	21.4	12.8	0.00	95		0.01	n/a	0.00
3	12.9	11.0	0.00	95		0.01	n/a	0.00
4	11.3	9.9	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
5	10.0	7.7	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
6	7.7	6.4	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
7	6.5	5.0	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
8	5.1	4.1	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
9	4.2	3.1	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
10	3.1	2.3	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.00
11	2.3	1.1	0.00	95		0.03	n/a	0.00
12	1.2	0.6	0.00	95		0.04	n/a	0.00
13	0.9	0.2	0.00	95		0.15	n/a	0.18
14	0.1	0.1	0.00	95		0.15	n/a	0.09

HY02-04P-2d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	8.3	8.3	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.00
2	8.3	7.1	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.01
3	7.1	6.4	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.04
4	6.4	6.5	0.00	61		0.00	0%	0.06
5	5.5	4.6	0.00	61		0.01	0%	0.08
6	4.6	3.4	0.00	61		0.02	0%	0.30
7	3.7	3.1	0.00	61		0.04	0%	0.68
8	3.3	2.7	0.00	61		0.07	0%	1.05
9	2.9	2.9	0.04	61		0.10	1%	1.71
10	3.0	2.9	0.18	61	1	0.11	3%	1.91
11	3.1	3.0	0.26	61		0.11	4%	2.08
12	3.2	3.1	0.37	61	2	0.11	6%	2.22
13	3.2	3.1	0.54	61		0.18	8%	3.61
14	3.2	2.9	0.83	61		0.19	13%	3.74
15	3.7	3.4	1.09	61		0.19	17%	4.43
16	3.8	3.6	1.30	92	3	0.19	20%	6.88
17	4.0	3.9	1.49	92		0.19	23%	7.44
18	4.0	3.8	1.73	92		0.19	27%	7.63
19	4.0	3.8	1.95	92		0.19	30%	7.75
20	3.9	3.7	2.20	92		0.19	34%	7.75
21	3.7	3.5	2.42	92	4	0.19	37%	7.68
22	3.5	3.3	2.66	92		0.19	41%	7.56
23	3.3	3.1	2.90	92		0.19	45%	7.45
24	3.1	2.9	3.09	92		0.19	48%	7.37
25	2.9	2.7	3.33	92		0.19	52%	7.23
26	2.7	2.4	3.66	97	5	0.19	57%	7.27
27	2.4	2.2	3.93	97		0.19	61%	7.15
28	2.2	2.0	4.20	97		0.19	65%	7.02
29	2.0	1.7	4.45	97		0.19	69%	6.85
30	1.8	1.5	4.75	97	6	0.19	74%	6.70
31	1.5	1.3	4.99	97		0.19	77%	6.53
32	1.3	1.0	5.24	97		0.19	81%	6.39
33	1.1	0.8	5.47	97		0.19	85%	6.23
34	0.9	0.6	5.70	96	7	0.19	88%	6.09
35	0.6	0.4	5.97	96		0.19	92%	5.94
36	0.4	0.2	6.20	96		0.19	96%	5.85
37	0.2	0.1	6.35	96		0.20	98%	5.83
38	0.5	0.1	6.45	79	8	0.48	100%	6.10

HY02-05P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.3	15.3	0.00	6		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.3	15.1	0.00	6		0.00	0%	0.02
3	15.1	14.8	0.00	6		0.00	0%	0.02
4	14.8	14.4	0.00	6		0.00	0%	0.02
5	14.4	13.8	0.00	6		0.01	0%	0.03
6	13.8	12.7	0.00	6		0.01	0%	0.03
7	12.8	11.6	0.00	6		0.01	0%	0.03
8	11.7	11.1	0.00	6		0.01	0%	0.04
9	11.1	9.8	0.00	6		0.01	0%	0.04
10	9.8	8.2	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
11	8.9	7.0	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
12	7.0	6.6	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
13	6.6	6.5	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
14	6.5	6.3	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
15	6.3	6.2	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.05
16	6.2	6.0	0.00	6		0.02	0%	0.04
17	6.0	5.8	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.04
18	5.9	5.8	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.05
19	5.8	5.7	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.05
20	5.7	5.5	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.04
21	5.6	5.1	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.04
22	5.6	5.0	0.00	6		0.03	0%	0.05
23	5.5	4.5	0.00	6		0.05	0%	0.11
24	5.4	4.1	0.00	6		0.09	0%	0.19
25	5.3	4.3	0.05	6	1 + BAG	0.13	0%	0.30
26	5.4	4.3	1.17	65	2 + BAG	0.18	6%	5.26
27	4.9	4.5	2.26	97	3 + BAG	0.19	11%	9.27
28	4.9	4.3	3.76	98	4 + BAG	0.20	18%	10.93
29	4.8	4.2	5.31	99	5 + BAG	0.21	26%	12.79
30	4.7	4.0	6.53	99	6 + BAG	0.23	32%	14.15
31	4.6	3.4	8.45	99	7 + BAG	0.26	41%	15.77
32	3.6	2.8	10.09	99	8 + BAG	0.29	49%	16.88
33	2.9	2.3	11.54	99	9 + BAG	0.31	56%	17.39
34	2.3	1.7	12.93	98	10 + BAG	0.36	63%	17.82
35	1.7	1.3	14.63	99	11 + BAG	0.36	71%	18.32
36	1.3	0.8	16.31	99	12 + BAG	0.43	79%	18.83
37	0.8	0.4	18.12	99	13 + BAG	0.48	88%	19.21
38	0.5	0.1	19.92	99	14 + BAG	0.53	97%	19.73
39	0.2	0.1	20.59	97	15 + BAG	0.53	100%	20.37

HY02-05P-4b&c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.9	15.9	0.00	95		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.9	9.3	0.00	95		0.01	0%	0.05
3	9.4	8.2	0.00	95		0.01	0%	0.50
4	8.2	7.1	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.58
5	7.2	6.0	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.60
6	6.1	5.0	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.53
7	5.6	3.4	0.00	95		0.11	0%	3.23
8	3.6	2.7	0.03	95		0.29	0%	6.95
9	2.9	2.5	0.22	95	1 + BAG	0.34	1%	7.89
10	2.8	2.5	1.75	95	2	0.36	6%	9.73
11	2.7	2.4	3.36	95	3	0.37	12%	11.09
12	2.5	2.3	5.01	95	4 + BAG	0.37	18%	12.42
13	2.6	2.4	6.67	95	5	0.37	24%	14.39
14	2.5	2.3	8.37	95	6	0.38	30%	15.76
15	2.5	2.3	10.07	95	7	0.38	36%	17.46
16	2.5	2.2	11.77	95	8	0.39	42%	18.79
17	2.5	2.2	13.46	95	9	0.39	49%	20.40
18	2.4	2.1	15.11	95	10	0.39	54%	21.62
19	2.3	2.0	16.81	95	11	0.39	61%	22.88
20	2.0	1.6	18.46	95	12	0.39	67%	23.13
21	1.7	1.3	20.14	95	13	0.39	73%	23.68
22	1.4	1.0	21.82	95	14	0.40	79%	24.31
23	1.1	0.7	23.48	95	15	0.41	85%	24.85
24	0.7	0.3	25.15	95	16	0.45	91%	25.11
25	0.5	0.2	26.81	95	17	0.47	97%	26.32
26	0.2	0.1	27.74	95	18 + BAG	0.48	100%	26.79

gas not analyzed; used 95% methane for draft calculations

HY02-07P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.4	15.4	0.00	89		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.4	11.8	0.00	89		0.01	0%	0.73
3	11.8	7.3	0.00	89		0.02	0%	0.85
4	7.3	5.7	0.00	89		0.03	0%	1.01
5	4.7	3.3	0.00	89		0.04	0%	0.78
6	3.4	2.4	0.00	89		0.06	0%	1.10
7	2.8	1.8	0.00	89		0.13	0%	1.80
8	2.5	1.7	0.00	89		0.13	0%	1.69
9	2.0	1.2	1.17	89	1	0.24	27%	3.41
10	1.3	0.6	2.55	97	2 + BAG	0.28	60%	3.91
11	0.7	0.2	3.71	97	3 + BAG	0.32	87%	4.08
12	0.2	0.1	4.27	96	15	0.33	100%	4.34

HY02-07P-1f Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.4	18.4	0.00	97		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.4	5.4	0.00	97		0.01	0%	0.00
3	5.4	4.8	0.00	97		0.02	0%	0.32
4	4.8	4.4	0.00	97		0.03	0%	0.69
5	4.4	4.1	0.00	97		0.04	0%	1.02
6	4.1	4.0	0.00	97		0.05	0%	1.37
7	4.0	2.5	0.00	97		0.05	0%	0.82
8	2.5	2.0	0.04	97		0.44	0%	8.12
9	2.3	1.8	1.66	97	1 + BAG	0.58	11%	11.12
10	2.0	1.6	3.35	97		0.59	22%	11.90
11	1.6	1.4	5.05	97	2	0.59	33%	12.45
12	1.4	1.2	6.70	97		0.59	44%	12.98
13	1.2	1.0	8.31	97		0.59	54%	13.46
14	1.0	0.8	9.92	97		0.60	65%	14.01
15	0.8	0.5	11.61	97	3	0.60	76%	14.00
16	0.6	0.3	13.30	97		0.60	87%	14.54
17	0.3	0.1	14.99	97		0.61	98%	15.10
18	0.1	0.1	15.31	97	4 + BAG	0.67	100%	15.47

HY02-07P-1g Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.7	17.7	0.00	96		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.7	12.7	0.00	96		0.01	0%	0.64
3	12.7	8.0	0.00	96		0.02	0%	0.83
4	8.0	4.5	0.00	96		0.03	0%	0.77
5	4.9	3.7	0.00	96		0.07	0%	1.83
6	4.7	3.2	0.00	96		0.14	0%	3.77
7	4.8	3.2	1.57	96	1 + BAG	0.18	18%	6.58
8	3.6	2.4	3.11	96		0.22	36%	7.48
9	2.4	1.6	4.36	96		0.25	50%	7.62
10	1.7	1.1	5.81	96		0.25	66%	7.99
11	1.1	0.4	7.23	96		0.32	83%	8.07
12	0.4	0.1	8.75	97	2 + BAG	0.36	100%	8.75

HY02-07P-2b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.6	19.6	0.00	88		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.6	14.5	0.00	88		0.01	0%	0.69
3	14.5	9.2	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.86
4	9.2	4.6	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.67
5	4.6	4.1	0.00	88		0.04	0%	0.93
6	4.1	3.7	0.00	88		0.05	0%	1.15
7	3.7	3.6	0.00	88		0.06	0%	1.42
8	3.6	3.3	0.00	88		0.07	0%	1.58
9	3.3	3.2	0.00	88		0.08	0%	1.81
10	3.4	1.7	0.39	88	1	0.22	5%	3.40
11	2.6	1.8	1.90	88		0.25	23%	5.33
12	2.1	1.5	3.36	91	2 + BAG	0.27	41%	6.36
13	1.7	1.1	4.88	91		0.27	59%	6.90
14	1.2	0.5	6.40	91	3 + BAG	0.29	78%	6.98
15	0.6	0.2	7.51	91	4	0.32	91%	7.32
16	0.2	0.1	8.21	90	5	0.38	100%	7.72

HY02-07P-2e Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.5	18.5	0.00	81		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.5	12.9	0.00	81		0.01	0%	0.44
3	12.9	7.9	0.00	81		0.02	0%	0.58
4	7.9	4.3	0.00	81		0.03	0%	0.53
5	4.3	4.3	0.00	81		0.04	0%	0.87
6	4.3	4.1	0.00	81		0.05	0%	1.15
7	4.1	4.0	0.00	81		0.06	0%	1.43
8	4.0	3.9	0.00	81		0.07	0%	1.70
9	3.9	3.9	0.00	81		0.08	0%	2.01
10	4.0	3.1	0.00	81		0.16	0%	3.61
11	3.4	2.2	0.60	81	1	0.40	3%	7.15
12	2.7	2.3	2.00	81		0.44	9%	9.22
13	2.6	2.3	3.56	90	2	0.44	15%	11.63
14	3.3	3.0	5.05	90		0.45	22%	15.67
15	3.2	2.9	6.54	91	3 + BAG	0.45	28%	16.76
16	3.2	2.9	8.07	91		0.45	34%	18.33
17	2.9	2.6	9.50	90	4	0.46	41%	18.41
18	2.7	2.3	11.11	90		0.46	47%	18.74
19	2.4	2.0	12.65	90	5	0.46	54%	18.98
20	2.1	1.7	14.24	90		0.46	61%	19.26
21	1.8	1.4	15.85	91	6	0.46	68%	19.62
22	1.5	1.1	17.54	91		0.46	75%	20.01
23	1.1	0.8	19.19	91	7 + BAG	0.46	82%	20.33
24	0.8	0.5	20.72	91	8	0.47	89%	20.57
25	0.5	0.3	21.84	91	9	0.50	93%	20.85
26	0.3	0.1	23.41	91	10	0.54	100%	21.47

HY02-07P-3 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.6	15.6	0.00	20		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.6	10.3	0.00	20		0.01	0%	0.00
3	10.3	9.4	0.00	20		0.01	0%	0.08
4	9.5	7.9	0.00	20		0.01	0%	0.09
5	8.0	7.5	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
6	7.5	7.1	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
7	7.1	6.9	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.12
8	6.9	6.2	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
9	6.2	5.7	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
10	5.8	5.3	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
11	5.8	5.0	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
12	5.8	4.9	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.12
13	5.7	5.0	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.14
14	5.7	4.5	0.00	20		0.03	0%	0.16
15	5.6	4.2	0.00	20		0.04	0%	0.26
16	5.4	4.4	0.00	20		0.06	0%	0.47
17	5.3	4.4	0.00	20		0.08	0%	0.62
18	5.3	4.3	0.00	20		0.10	0%	0.79
19	5.4	4.3	0.00	20		0.14	0%	1.09
20	4.8	3.8	0.00	97		0.19	0%	6.45
21	4.2	3.2	0.45	97	1	0.24	5%	7.21
22	3.4	2.3	1.88	99	2	0.29	22%	7.90
23	2.4	1.8	3.52	99	3	0.33	42%	8.97
24	1.6	1.0	5.20	99	4	0.35	62%	8.33
25	1.0	0.5	6.76	99	5	0.39	80%	8.51
26	0.5	0.1	8.40	99	6	0.47	100%	8.74

HY02-08P-1b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	20.9	20.9	0.00	90		0.00	0%	0.00
2	20.9	15.3	0.00	90		0.01	0%	0.86
3	15.3	10.3	0.00	90		0.02	0%	1.03
4	10.3	5.0	0.00	90		0.03	0%	0.75
5	5.0	4.1	0.00	90		0.04	0%	0.95
6	4.1	3.8	0.00	90		0.05	0%	1.20
7	3.8	3.6	0.00	90		0.06	0%	1.45
8	3.6	3.5	0.00	90		0.07	0%	1.71
9	3.5	3.3	0.00	90		0.08	0%	1.91
10	3.5	2.5	0.00	90		0.14	0%	2.77
11	2.8	2.0	0.91	90	1	0.20	8%	4.12
12	2.7	2.1	2.32	90		0.22	21%	5.88
13	2.5	2.0	3.59	92	2	0.24	32%	7.27
14	3.2	2.5	4.86	92		0.25	44%	9.67
15	2.5	1.9	6.33	92	3 + BAG	0.26	57%	9.91
16	1.9	1.2	7.78	92	4	0.27	70%	9.84
17	1.3	0.6	9.03	91	5	0.30	81%	9.74
18	0.7	0.3	10.04	92	6 + BAG	0.34	90%	10.03
19	0.3	0.1	11.10	92	7	0.38	100%	10.48

HY02-08P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	20.8	20.8	0.00	34		0.00	0%	0.00
2	20.8	15.0	0.00	34		0.01	0%	0.22
3	15.0	9.2	0.00	34		0.02	0%	0.27
4	9.2	3.7	0.00	34		0.03	0%	0.17
5	3.7	3.7	0.00	34		0.04	0%	0.29
6	3.7	3.3	0.00	34		0.05	0%	0.36
7	3.3	3.3	0.00	34		0.06	0%	0.48
8	3.8	2.8	0.00	34		0.09	0%	0.69
9	3.5	2.8	0.00	34		0.12	0%	0.96
10	3.2	2.8	0.00	34		0.14	0%	1.16
11	2.9	2.3	0.00	34		0.21	0%	1.44
12	2.6	1.9	0.46	34	1	0.22	7%	1.43
13	2.2	1.4	1.40	34	2 + BAG	0.30	20%	1.76
14	1.6	1.1	2.53	34	3	0.34	37%	2.02
15	1.1	0.6	3.76	99	4 + BAG	0.48	55%	4.71
16	0.7	0.2	5.04	99	5	0.59	73%	4.45
17	0.3	0.1	6.57	99	6	0.69	96%	5.51
18	0.1	0.1	6.86	99	7	0.69	100%	5.79

HY02-08P-1d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.2	18.2	0.00	89		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.2	8.0	0.00	89		0.01	0%	0.02
3	8.0	4.2	0.00	89		0.02	0%	0.24
4	4.2	3.8	0.00	89		0.03	0%	0.53
5	3.8	3.5	0.00	89		0.04	0%	0.79
6	3.5	3.3	0.00	89		0.05	0%	1.02
7	3.3	3.2	0.00	89		0.06	0%	1.26
8	3.2	3.1	0.00	89		0.07	0%	1.49
9	3.1	3.1	0.00	89		0.08	0%	1.76
10	3.1	2.9	0.00	89		0.09	0%	1.89
11	2.9	2.9	0.00	89		0.10	0%	2.14
12	2.9	2.9	0.00	89		0.11	0%	2.40
13	3.1	2.1	0.00	89		0.19	0%	3.20
14	2.6	2.0	1.15	89	1	0.22	10%	4.65
15	2.9	2.2	2.55	89		0.24	21%	6.48
16	2.6	2.0	4.11	91	2	0.24	35%	7.64
17	2.5	1.9	5.64	91		0.24	47%	8.88
18	2.3	1.6	7.15	92	3 + BAG	0.25	60%	9.84
19	1.8	1.1	8.66	92		0.25	73%	10.17
20	1.3	0.6	10.08	92	4 + BAG	0.25	85%	10.42
21	0.7	0.3	11.11	92		0.27	93%	10.79
22	0.3	0.1	11.91	91	5	0.33	100%	11.12

HY02-09P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.6	14.6	0.00	85		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.6	8.7	0.00	85		0.01	0%	0.00
3	8.7	3.5	0.00	85		0.02	0%	0.00
4	5.2	3.7	0.00	85		0.03	0%	0.31
5	5.0	3.5	0.00	85		0.06	0%	0.98
6	4.5	3.5	0.00	85		0.10	0%	2.14
7	4.5	3.6	0.00	85		0.14	0%	3.30
8	4.0	2.8	0.00	85		0.18	0%	3.57
9	4.2	2.8	0.00	85		0.24	0%	4.84
10	3.4	2.5	0.00	85		0.28	0%	5.32
11	3.1	2.3	1.03	85	1	0.29	10%	5.86
12	2.5	1.8	2.35	96	2	0.30	22%	6.65
13	2.1	1.4	3.92	97	3 + BAG	0.30	37%	7.28
14	1.7	0.9	5.34	96	4	0.31	51%	7.34
15	1.4	0.6	6.51	94	5	0.33	62%	7.77
16	1.0	0.2	7.69	95	6 + BAG	0.34	73%	7.82
17	0.6	0.1	8.79	95	7	0.42	84%	8.65
18	0.3	0.1	10.50	96	8	0.42	100%	10.29

HY02-09P-2b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.0	14.0	0.00	95		0.00	n/a	0.00
2	14.0	1.3	0.00	95		0.01	n/a	0.00
3	1.3	0.4	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.03
4	0.4	0.1	0.07	95		0.08	n/a	0.13

HY02-09P-2e&f Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	13.4	13.4	0.00	95		0.00	n/a	0.00
2	13.4	2.7	0.00	95		0.01	n/a	0.04
3	2.7	0.5	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.04
4	0.6	0.1	0.02	95		0.16	n/a	0.16

HY02-10P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	13.9	13.9	0.00	55		0.00	0%	0.00
2	13.9	8.4	0.00	55		0.01	0%	0.07
3	8.4	4.5	0.00	55		0.02	0%	0.13
4	4.5	0.1	0.41	55	1 + BAG	0.29	44%	0.37
5	0.1	0.1	0.94	91	2 + BAG	0.30	100%	0.96

HY02-10P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	12.0	12.0	0.00	11		0.00	0%	0.00
2	12.0	8.0	0.00	11		0.01	0%	0.02
3	8.0	4.6	0.00	11		0.02	0%	0.03
4	4.6	2.5	0.00	11		0.03	0%	0.03
5	2.5	1.5	0.00	11		0.04	0%	0.03
6	1.5	1.0	0.00	11		0.05	0%	0.03
7	1.0	0.8	0.00	11		0.06	0%	0.03
8	0.8	0.6	0.00	11		0.07	0%	0.03
9	0.6	0.6	0.00	11		0.08	0%	0.04
10	0.6	0.5	0.00	11		0.10	1%	0.04
11	0.5	0.1	0.28	11	1 + BAG	0.21	64%	0.05
12	0.1	0.1	0.44	76	2	0.22	100%	0.30

HY02-11P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.7	15.7	0.00	20		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.7	10.9	0.00	20		0.01	0%	0.05
3	10.9	7.6	0.00	20		0.02	0%	0.11
4	7.6	6.7	0.00	20		0.03	0%	0.20
5	6.7	6.1	0.00	20		0.04	0%	0.29
6	6.1	5.4	0.00	20		0.05	0%	0.35
7	5.4	5.0	0.00	20		0.06	0%	0.41
8	5.0	4.7	0.00	20		0.07	0%	0.47
9	4.7	4.3	0.00	20		0.08	0%	0.51
10	4.6	3.1	0.00	20		0.14	0%	0.69
11	3.3	2.3	0.91	34	1 + BAG	0.18	15%	1.45
12	2.4	1.4	2.06	95	2 + BAG	0.19	34%	3.52
13	1.6	0.6	3.56	95	3	0.26	59%	4.12
14	0.7	0.1	5.41	96	4 + BAG	0.42	90%	4.96
15	0.2	0.1	5.85	92	5	0.43	98%	5.36
16	0.1	0.1	5.99	92		0.43	100%	5.49

HY02-11P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.8	14.8	0.00	65		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.8	8.4	0.00	65		0.01	0%	0.00
3	8.4	7.1	0.00	65		0.02	0%	0.31
4	7.1	6.6	0.00	65		0.03	0%	0.66
5	6.6	5.8	0.00	65		0.04	0%	0.89
6	5.8	5.1	0.00	65		0.05	0%	1.06
7	5.1	4.8	0.00	65		0.06	0%	1.28
8	4.8	4.5	0.00	65		0.07	0%	1.46
9	4.5	4.2	0.00	65		0.08	0%	1.62
10	4.3	3.1	0.00	65		0.12	0%	2.00
11	3.3	2.3	0.67	65	1 + BAG	0.17	10%	2.59
12	2.9	2.0	1.65	97	2	0.21	25%	4.78
13	2.1	1.3	2.79	98	3	0.24	42%	5.17
14	1.4	0.9	3.83	98	4	0.26	58%	5.51
15	0.9	0.6	4.77	98	5 + BAG	0.28	72%	5.85
16	0.6	0.3	5.52	97	6	0.32	83%	5.99
17	0.3	0.1	6.38	92	7 + BAG	0.39	96%	6.28
18	0.1	0.1	6.65	92	8	0.39	100%	6.53

HY02-12P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.0	14.0	0.00	74		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.0	6.2	0.00	74		0.02	0%	0.34
3	6.2	5.1	0.00	74		0.03	0%	0.76
4	6.3	5.1	0.00	74		0.05	0%	1.19
5	6.0	5.0	0.00	74		0.06	0%	1.61
6	5.6	4.5	0.00	74		0.08	0%	1.95
7	4.8	3.7	0.00	74		0.10	0%	2.18
8	3.9	2.7	0.48	74	1 + BAG	0.13	6%	2.56
9	2.9	1.9	1.95	97	2	0.16	24%	4.38
10	2.1	1.2	3.28	99	3	0.19	41%	5.03
11	1.4	0.7	4.66	99	4	0.22	58%	5.78
12	0.9	0.5	5.49	99	5 + BAG	0.23	69%	6.30
13	0.7	0.3	6.60	99	6	0.27	83%	7.10
14	0.4	0.2	7.22	98	7 + BAG	0.29	90%	7.51
15	0.2	0.1	7.98	98	8	0.35	100%	8.05

HY02-12P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.1	15.1	0.00	68		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.1	9.7	0.00	68		0.01	0%	0.08
3	9.8	9.1	0.00	68		0.01	0%	0.07
4	9.1	7.6	0.00	68		0.01	0%	0.01
5	7.6	6.4	0.00	68		0.01	0%	0.00
6	6.4	5.4	0.00	68		0.02	0%	0.10
7	6.4	6.0	0.00	68		0.02	0%	0.19
8	6.4	5.4	0.00	68		0.02	0%	0.34
9	6.2	5.0	0.00	68		0.04	0%	0.83
10	6.0	5.0	0.00	68		0.06	0%	1.52
11	5.9	4.7	0.00	68		0.08	0%	2.10
12	5.7	3.8	0.90	68	1 + BAG	0.14	7%	3.65
13	4.7	3.7	2.50	98	2	0.15	18%	6.71
14	4.0	2.9	4.21	99	3	0.16	31%	7.69
15	3.0	2.0	5.78	99	4	0.18	42%	8.48
16	2.2	1.2	7.42	99	5 + BAG	0.22	54%	9.33
17	1.5	0.9	8.98	99	6	0.26	66%	10.67
18	1.1	0.6	10.53	99	7	0.28	77%	11.60
19	0.7	0.2	12.17	99	8	0.36	89%	12.39
20	0.3	0.1	13.69	98	9 + BAG	0.39	100%	13.58

HY02-13P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	12.7	12.7	0.00	60		0.00	0%	0.00
2	12.7	3.6	0.00	60		0.07	0%	1.21
3	3.8	2.0	0.02	60	1	0.17	0%	1.84
4	2.0	1.8	0.74	93	2 + BAG	0.24	9%	4.37
5	2.0	1.4	2.30	98	3	0.25	29%	5.26
6	1.5	0.8	3.82	99	4	0.25	48%	5.48
7	1.0	0.5	5.41	98	5 + BAG	0.30	68%	6.61
8	0.6	0.2	6.95	98	6	0.33	87%	7.38
9	0.2	0.1	7.94	98	7 + BAG	0.39	100%	8.11

HY02-13P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.8	14.8	0.00	86		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.8	5.0	0.01	86		0.02	0%	0.45
3	5.2	3.9	0.01	86		0.04	0%	0.88
4	5.3	4.1	0.01	86		0.05	0%	1.42
5	4.9	3.9	0.01	86		0.07	0%	1.99
6	4.6	3.6	0.01	86		0.10	0%	2.64
7	3.6	2.3	0.87	86	1 + BAG	0.13	12%	2.92
8	2.5	1.5	1.83	98	2	0.15	24%	3.61
9	1.7	1.0	2.91	99	3 + BAG	0.17	39%	4.26
10	1.3	0.7	3.87	98	4	0.21	51%	5.00
11	0.9	0.4	5.21	98	5	0.26	69%	5.92
12	0.5	0.1	6.63	98	6 + BAG	0.33	88%	6.70
13	0.2	0.1	7.54	97	7	0.34	100%	7.59

HY02-13P-3 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.1	15.1	0.00	89		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.1	5.9	0.00	89		0.02	0%	0.35
3	6.0	5.0	0.00	89		0.04	0%	0.93
4	5.8	4.6	0.00	89		0.05	0%	1.41
5	5.7	4.6	0.00	89		0.07	0%	2.08
6	5.6	4.6	0.00	89		0.09	0%	2.98
7	5.3	4.2	0.00	89	1 + BAG	0.12	0%	3.82
8	4.9	3.5	0.96	98	2	0.16	8%	5.70
9	4.0	3.0	2.22	99	3	0.17	18%	6.62
10	3.2	2.2	3.84	99	4	0.18	32%	7.23
11	2.4	1.4	5.53	99	5	0.20	45%	7.84
12	1.8	1.0	7.11	98	6	0.22	58%	8.94
13	1.2	0.6	8.55	98	7	0.26	70%	9.78
14	0.7	0.3	10.02	98	8	0.26	82%	10.55
15	0.4	0.2	11.14	97	9	0.26	92%	11.40
16	0.4	0.1	11.98	97		0.26	98%	11.99
17	0.1	0.1	12.16	97		0.26	100%	12.17

HY02-15P-1b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.0	17.0	0.00	95		0.00	n/a	0.00
2	17.0	7.6	0.00	95		0.01	n/a	0.08
3	7.6	2.1	0.00	95		0.02	n/a	0.12
4	2.1	1.0	0.00	95		0.03	n/a	0.14
5	1.2	0.1	0.00	95		0.36	n/a	0.32
6	0.2	0.1	0.00	95		0.59	n/a	0.53
7	0.1	0.1	0.00	95		0.67	n/a	0.61

HY02-15P-1d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	16.9	16.9	0.00	85		0.00	0%	0.00
2	16.9	11.7	0.00	85		0.01	0%	0.57
3	11.7	7.8	0.00	85		0.02	0%	0.83
4	7.8	4.0	0.00	85		0.03	0%	0.66
5	4.0	2.9	0.00	85		0.04	0%	0.69
6	2.9	2.3	0.00	85		0.05	0%	0.73
7	2.3	1.8	0.00	85		0.06	0%	0.72
8	1.8	0.5	0.53	85	1	0.14	26%	0.95
9	0.7	0.1	2.03	79	2 + BAG	0.25	100%	1.82

HY02-16P-1d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	8.9	8.9	0.00	94		0.00	0%	0.00
2	8.9	7.9	0.00	94		0.00	0%	0.25
3	8.0	7.0	0.00	94		0.01	0%	0.51
4	7.1	6.0	0.00	94		0.01	0%	0.49
5	7.1	6.0	0.00	94		0.01	0%	0.63
6	6.3	5.2	0.00	94		0.01	0%	0.58
7	5.8	4.6	0.00	94		0.02	0%	0.73
8	5.8	4.8	0.00	94		0.02	0%	0.97
9	5.6	4.5	0.00	94		0.03	0%	1.24
10	5.3	4.4	0.00	94		0.07	0%	2.62
11	5.1	3.8	0.04	94		0.08	1%	2.75
12	4.5	3.0	0.68	94		0.09	14%	2.92
13	4.2	3.5	1.14	94	1	0.09	24%	3.78
14	3.9	3.4	1.45	94		0.09	30%	3.96
15	3.6	3.2	1.67	94		0.09	35%	4.09
16	3.4	2.9	1.92	94		0.09	40%	4.07
17	3.1	2.8	2.14	84	2	0.09	45%	3.92
18	2.9	2.5	2.41	84		0.09	50%	3.97
19	2.7	2.2	2.69	84		0.09	56%	3.98
20	2.4	2.0	2.95	84		0.09	62%	4.05
21	2.1	1.7	3.22	84		0.09	67%	4.06
22	1.9	1.4	3.50	86	3	0.09	73%	4.11
23	1.6	1.2	3.72	86		0.09	78%	4.15
24	1.3	0.8	4.04	86		0.09	85%	4.16
25	1.1	0.5	4.37	86		0.09	91%	4.24
26	0.7	0.1	4.66	62	4	0.15	98%	4.16
27	0.3	0.1	4.78	62		0.36	100%	4.35

HY02-16P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.1	17.1	0.00	88		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.1	11.8	0.00	88		0.01	0%	0.30
3	11.9	10.9	0.00	88		0.01	0%	0.35
4	11.0	10.6	0.00	88		0.01	0%	0.47
5	10.6	9.9	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.59
6	10.0	9.3	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.60
7	9.7	8.9	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.57
8	8.9	8.3	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.56
9	8.5	8.2	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.60
10	8.2	7.9	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.62
11	8.0	7.7	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.61
12	7.7	7.4	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.63
13	7.4	7.2	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.62
14	7.2	6.9	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.64
15	7.0	6.8	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.65
16	6.8	6.6	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.65
17	6.7	6.5	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.65
18	6.5	6.3	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.64
19	6.3	6.1	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.66
20	6.1	5.3	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.58
21	5.8	5.5	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.62
22	5.8	5.7	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.67
23	5.8	5.5	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.67
24	5.8	5.6	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.71
25	5.8	5.6	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.70
26	5.7	5.0	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.64
27	5.6	4.4	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.60
28	5.6	4.5	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.69
29	5.5	4.4	0.00	88		0.04	0%	0.86
30	5.5	4.5	0.00	88		0.05	0%	1.33
31	5.4	4.4	0.00	88		0.06	0%	1.75
32	5.4	4.3	0.00	88		0.08	0%	2.52
33	5.4	4.3	0.00	88		0.08	0%	2.52
34	5.3	4.5	0.72	88	1 + BAG	0.12	2%	4.69
35	5.5	4.6	2.37	95	2 + BAG	0.12	7%	6.74
36	5.6	4.7	3.48	97	3 + BAG	0.13	11%	8.15
37	5.7	4.9	5.08	96	4 + BAG	0.13	16%	9.87
38	5.5	4.7	6.45	99	5 + BAG	0.13	20%	11.22
39	5.5	4.6	8.07	99	6 + BAG	0.13	25%	12.70
40	5.3	4.4	9.54	99	7 + BAG	0.13	30%	14.03
41	5.3	4.3	11.05	99	8 + BAG	0.13	34%	15.61
42	5.0	4.1	12.70	96	9 + BAG	0.14	39%	16.97
43	4.9	4.0	14.22	96	10 + BAG	0.14	44%	18.51
44	4.9	4.1	15.88	99	11 + BAG	0.15	49%	20.57
45	4.8	4.1	17.48	99	12 + BAG	0.15	54%	22.22
46	4.6	3.7	19.18	99	13 + BAG	0.15	59%	23.46
47	4.4	3.7	20.82	99	14 + BAG	0.15	65%	25.14
48	4.1	3.4	22.49	99	15 + BAG	0.16	70%	26.45
49	3.8	3.2	23.75	99	16 + BAG	0.16	74%	27.57
50	3.4	2.8	25.07	99	17 + BAG	0.16	78%	28.36
51	2.8	2.2	26.52	99	18 + BAG	0.17	82%	29.06
52	2.3	1.6	27.91	99	19 + BAG	0.18	87%	29.70
53	1.7	0.8	29.55	99	20 + BAG	0.21	92%	30.36
54	0.9	0.4	31.04	99	21 + BAG	0.27	96%	31.36
55	0.4	0.1	32.15	99	22 + BAG	0.34	100%	31.82
56	0.1	0.1	32.24	95	23	0.34	100%	31.90

HY02-17P-3a&b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	12.5	12.5	0.00	95		0.00	0%	0.00
2	12.5	5.7	0.00	95		0.01	0%	0.22
3	5.7	5.0	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.63
4	5.1	3.3	0.00	95		0.11	0%	3.02
5	3.6	2.4	0.34	95	1	0.30	1%	6.71
6	2.6	2.4	1.55	95	2 + BAG	0.30	5%	7.86
7	2.6	2.5	3.09	95	3	0.30	11%	9.59
8	2.6	2.4	4.38	95	4	0.31	15%	10.73
9	2.5	2.3	5.85	95	5	0.31	20%	11.85
10	2.5	2.2	7.47	95	6	0.31	26%	13.11
11	2.5	2.3	9.12	95	7	0.31	31%	14.95
12	2.4	2.2	10.76	95	8	0.31	37%	16.23
13	2.3	2.2	12.41	95	9	0.31	42%	17.82
14	2.9	2.8	12.87	95	10	0.31	44%	19.91
15	3.1	2.9	13.48	95	11	0.31	46%	20.77
16	3.0	2.8	14.17	95	12	0.31	49%	21.14
17	2.9	2.8	14.66	95	13	0.31	50%	21.62
18	2.8	2.4	16.31	95	14 + BAG	0.31	56%	22.09
19	2.5	2.3	17.00	95	15	0.32	58%	22.77
20	2.3	2.2	17.93	95	16	0.32	61%	23.42
21	2.2	2.0	18.55	95	17	0.32	64%	23.42
22	2.1	1.9	19.23	95	18	0.32	66%	23.80
23	1.9	1.8	20.08	95	19	0.32	69%	24.32
24	1.8	1.6	20.85	95	20	0.32	71%	24.46
25	1.7	1.5	21.56	95	21	0.32	74%	24.85
26	1.5	1.3	22.28	95	22	0.33	76%	24.97
27	1.4	1.1	23.49	95	23	0.33	80%	25.57
28	1.1	0.9	24.60	95	24	0.33	84%	26.03
29	0.9	0.7	25.71	95	25	0.33	88%	26.52
30	0.7	0.5	27.07	95	26	0.34	93%	27.25
31	0.5	0.3	28.01	95		0.35	96%	27.54
32	0.3	0.1	29.20	95	27	0.36	100%	28.06

gas not analyzed; used 95% methane for draft calculations

HY02-17P-4 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.5	14.5	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.5	8.1	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
3	8.2	7.9	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
4	7.9	7.6	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
5	7.6	7.3	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
6	7.3	7.1	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
7	7.1	6.8	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
8	6.9	6.6	0.00	83		0.00	0%	0.00
9	6.6	6.3	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.00
10	6.3	6.1	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.00
11	6.1	5.9	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.05
12	6.1	6.0	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.06
13	6.0	5.8	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.08
14	5.9	5.6	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.10
15	5.9	5.6	0.00	83		0.01	0%	0.12
16	5.8	5.6	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.14
17	5.8	5.7	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.16
18	5.8	5.7	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.19
19	5.8	5.7	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.21
20	5.8	5.4	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.21
21	5.7	4.8	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.25
22	5.8	4.9	0.00	83		0.02	0%	0.40
23	5.8	4.7	0.00	83		0.03	0%	0.80
24	5.8	4.8	0.00	83		0.04	0%	1.24
25	5.9	5.2	0.00	83		0.06	0%	1.97
26	5.7	4.7	0.00	83		0.08	0%	2.56
27	5.5	4.5	0.00	83		0.12	0%	3.89
28	5.3	4.6	0.73	83	1 + BAG	0.14	3%	5.40
29	5.3	4.4	1.83	98	2 + BAG	0.15	8%	7.60
30	5.1	4.2	3.06	99	3 + BAG	0.17	13%	9.04
31	5.1	4.2	4.33	99	4 + BAG	0.17	19%	10.56
32	5.4	4.4	5.87	99	5 + BAG	0.18	25%	12.75
33	5.3	4.6	7.46	99	6 + BAG	0.18	32%	14.78
34	5.1	4.4	8.83	99	7 + BAG	0.19	38%	15.93
35	4.8	4.0	10.51	99	8 + BAG	0.19	45%	16.93
36	4.4	3.6	12.21	99	9 + BAG	0.19	52%	17.98
37	4.1	3.3	13.82	99	10 + BAG	0.19	59%	19.05
38	3.4	2.6	15.52	99	11 + BAG	0.20	67%	19.81
39	2.6	2.2	16.49	99	12 + BAG	0.20	71%	20.16
40	2.2	1.6	17.72	99	13 + BAG	0.21	76%	20.42
41	1.6	1.0	19.04	99	14 + BAG	0.24	82%	20.87
42	1.1	0.5	20.47	99	15 + BAG	0.27	88%	21.36
43	0.7	0.3	21.97	99	16 + BAG	0.37	94%	22.63
44	0.3	0.1	22.92	99	17 + BAG	0.44	98%	22.97
45	0.1	0.1	23.30	99	18 + BAG	0.45	100%	23.35

HY02-17P-5c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	6.4	6.4	0.00	1		0.00	0%	0.00
2	6.4	6.4	0.85	1	1	0.03	0%	0.03
3	6.4	6.4	1.70	1		0.06	1%	0.05
4	6.4	6.3	2.56	1		0.07	1%	0.07
5	6.3	6.3	3.41	1		0.07	1%	0.08
6	6.3	6.3	4.26	1		0.08	2%	0.09
7	6.3	6.3	5.11	1		0.08	2%	0.10
8	6.3	6.3	5.96	1		0.08	3%	0.11
9	6.3	6.2	6.81	1		0.08	3%	0.11
10	6.2	6.0	10.14	1		0.08	4%	0.15
11	6.0	4.9	15.40	1		0.08	7%	0.19
12	5.7	5.0	22.26	1		0.08	9%	0.26
13	5.5	5.2	26.06	1		0.08	11%	0.30
14	5.4	5.3	29.36	1		0.08	12%	0.33
15	5.3	4.8	33.08	1		0.08	14%	0.37
16	5.2	4.6	37.65	6	2	0.08	16%	0.81
17	5.1	4.6	42.01	6		0.08	18%	1.07
18	5.0	3.9	46.54	6		0.08	20%	1.31
19	4.9	4.8	50.25	6		0.08	21%	1.57
20	4.8	4.7	53.76	6		0.08	23%	1.78
21	4.8	4.6	58.24	6		0.08	25%	2.04
22	4.7	4.4	62.72	6		0.08	27%	2.30
23	4.6	4.3	67.60	7	3	0.08	29%	2.67
24	4.4	4.2	72.35	7		0.08	31%	3.00
25	4.3	4.0	77.99	7		0.08	33%	3.38
26	4.2	3.9	83.01	7		0.08	35%	3.73
27	4.1	3.8	89.30	7	4	0.08	38%	4.16
28	3.9	3.7	94.54	7		0.08	40%	4.52
29	3.8	3.5	100.00	7		0.08	43%	4.90
30	3.7	3.3	104.32	7		0.08	44%	5.19
31	3.6	3.2	110.80	7		0.08	47%	5.64
32	3.4	3.1	116.58	7		0.08	50%	6.04
33	3.3	3.0	121.22	7		0.08	52%	6.36
34	3.2	2.8	126.50	7		0.08	54%	6.72
35	3.0	2.7	133.25	4	5	0.08	57%	6.92
36	2.9	2.7	137.18	4		0.08	58%	7.08
37	2.8	2.5	142.77	4		0.08	61%	7.30
38	2.6	1.6	147.81	4		0.08	63%	7.47
39	2.5	1.8	154.83	4		0.08	66%	7.76
40	2.2	1.4	161.37	4		0.08	69%	8.01
41	2.0	1.2	166.57	4		0.08	71%	8.21
42	1.9	1.3	171.15	4		0.08	73%	8.40
43	1.8	1.3	175.14	4		0.08	74%	8.56
44	1.7	1.0	178.50	4		0.08	76%	8.68
45	1.6	1.0	184.59	2	6	0.08	78%	8.79
46	1.5	0.8	188.16	2		0.08	80%	8.86
47	1.4	0.8	192.92	2		0.08	82%	8.95
48	1.3	0.7	198.13	2		0.08	84%	9.06
49	1.1	0.7	201.85	2		0.08	86%	9.13
50	1.1	0.6	206.06	2		0.08	88%	9.21
51	1.0	0.6	210.56	2		0.08	90%	9.30
52	0.8	0.5	215.98	2		0.08	92%	9.41
53	0.7	0.4	222.16	2		0.08	94%	9.53
54	0.5	0.3	227.64	2		0.08	97%	9.64
55	0.4	0.2	231.58	2		0.08	98%	9.72
56	0.2	0.1	232.45	2		0.10	99%	9.74
57	0.2	0.1	233.35	2		0.12	99%	9.75
58	0.1	0.1	234.20	2		0.13	100%	9.77
59	0.1	0.1	235.06	2		0.18	100%	9.79
60	0.1	0.1	235.15	2		0.40	100%	9.79

HY02-18P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.3	18.3	0.00	96		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.3	8.7	0.00	96		0.01	0%	0.07
3	8.7	4.8	0.00	96		0.02	0%	0.32
4	4.8	4.4	0.00	96		0.03	0%	0.69
5	4.4	4.1	0.00	96		0.04	0%	1.01
6	4.1	3.9	0.00	96		0.05	0%	1.32
7	3.9	3.7	0.00	96		0.06	0%	1.59
8	3.7	3.5	0.00	96		0.07	0%	1.83
9	3.5	3.4	0.00	96		0.08	0%	2.09
10	3.4	3.3	0.00	96		0.09	0%	2.33
11	3.3	3.2	0.00	96		0.10	0%	2.56
12	3.3	2.2	1.00	96	1	0.21	6%	4.97
13	2.7	2.3	2.55	96		0.24	14%	7.17
14	2.6	2.2	4.04	98	2	0.24	23%	8.63
15	2.6	2.2	5.55	98		0.24	31%	10.17
16	2.6	2.3	7.00	98	3 + BAG	0.25	39%	12.02
17	2.6	2.2	8.62	98		0.26	49%	13.51
18	2.5	2.0	10.20	99	4	0.26	58%	14.70
19	2.5	1.9	11.73	99		0.26	66%	16.03
20	2.2	1.5	13.35	99	5	0.27	75%	16.71
21	1.6	1.0	14.95	99		0.28	84%	17.15
22	1.1	0.4	16.57	99	6	0.28	93%	17.28
23	0.5	0.2	17.22	98	7	0.29	97%	17.42
24	0.3	0.1	17.73	97	8	0.32	100%	17.69

HY02-18P-2c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.2	14.2	0.00	95		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.2	8.3	0.00	95		0.01	0%	0.32
3	8.3	5.4	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.56
4	5.4	5.1	0.00	95		0.03	0%	0.99
5	5.1	4.9	0.00	95		0.04	0%	1.39
6	4.9	4.8	0.00	95		0.05	0%	1.80
7	4.8	4.7	0.00	95		0.06	0%	2.20
8	4.7	4.6	0.00	95		0.07	0%	2.59
9	5.1	4.2	0.00	95		0.13	0%	4.78
10	4.4	3.6	1.13	95	1	0.20	3%	7.36
11	5.3	4.9	2.44	95	2	0.21	6%	11.20
12	5.3	4.9	3.67	95	3	0.21	9%	12.63
13	5.3	4.9	5.19	95	4	0.22	12%	14.26
14	5.3	4.9	6.71	95	5	0.22	16%	15.75
15	5.3	4.9	8.26	95	6	0.22	19%	17.26
16	5.3	4.8	9.64	95	7	0.22	23%	18.42
17	5.0	4.5	11.21	95	8	0.22	26%	19.40
18	4.7	4.3	12.58	95	9	0.22	30%	20.48
19	4.9	4.5	13.83	95	10	0.23	33%	22.18
20	4.7	4.2	15.33	95	11	0.23	36%	23.15
21	4.5	4.0	16.90	95	12	0.24	40%	24.43
22	4.8	4.3	18.43	95	13	0.24	43%	26.70
23	4.5	4.0	19.76	95	14	0.25	47%	27.50
24	4.4	3.9	21.29	95	15	0.25	50%	28.92
25	4.5	4.1	22.52	95	16	0.26	53%	30.68
26	4.3	3.9	23.92	95	17	0.26	56%	31.75
27	4.0	3.6	25.24	95	18	0.27	59%	32.53
28	4.4	4.1	25.84	95	19	0.27	61%	34.32
29	4.4	4.0	26.71	95	20	0.27	63%	34.91
30	4.1	3.6	28.09	95	21	0.27	66%	35.26
31	4.2	3.3	29.50	95	22	0.27	70%	35.86
32	3.3	2.9	31.02	95	23	0.27	73%	36.43
33	2.9	2.4	32.60	95		0.29	77%	37.13
34	2.4	2.0	34.16	95		0.31	81%	37.92
35	2.0	1.6	35.57	95		0.32	84%	38.32
36	1.6	1.3	37.01	95		0.33	87%	38.97
37	1.3	0.9	38.50	95		0.36	91%	39.44
38	0.9	0.6	39.88	95		0.37	94%	39.86
39	0.6	0.4	41.06	95		0.40	97%	40.42
40	0.4	0.1	42.44	95	24	0.43	100%	40.70

gas not analyzed; used 95% methane for draft calculations

HY02-19P-2b Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	8.9	8.9	0.00	85		0.00	0%	0.00
2	8.9	8.0	0.00	85		0.00	0%	0.23
3	8.0	6.9	0.00	85		0.01	0%	0.46
4	7.1	6.1	0.00	85		0.02	0%	0.68
5	6.2	5.1	0.06	85		0.07	1%	2.72
6	5.2	4.8	0.13	85		0.07	2%	2.86
7	5.1	4.7	0.46	85		0.10	7%	4.19
8	5.0	4.9	0.54	85		0.11	8%	4.68
9	5.0	4.9	0.64	85		0.11	10%	4.78
10	4.9	4.8	0.73	85		0.11	11%	4.84
11	4.9	4.8	0.84	85		0.11	13%	4.90
12	4.8	4.6	0.98	85		0.11	15%	4.89
13	4.6	4.5	1.11	85		0.11	17%	4.90
14	4.5	4.4	1.21	85		0.11	19%	4.90
15	4.4	4.3	1.36	85		0.11	21%	4.93
16	4.3	4.1	1.53	85		0.11	24%	4.94
17	4.1	4.0	1.70	85		0.11	26%	4.95
18	4.0	3.9	1.85	85		0.11	29%	4.98
19	3.9	3.7	2.03	85		0.11	31%	4.99
20	3.7	3.6	2.26	85		0.11	35%	5.03
21	3.6	3.4	2.47	85		0.11	38%	5.07
22	3.4	3.2	2.74	85		0.11	42%	5.10
23	3.2	2.9	3.15	85		0.11	49%	5.17
24	2.9	2.7	3.36	85		0.11	52%	5.20
25	2.7	2.5	3.59	85		0.11	55%	5.23
26	2.5	2.3	3.81	85		0.11	59%	5.26
27	2.4	2.1	4.06	85		0.11	63%	5.28
28	2.1	2.0	4.24	85		0.11	65%	5.29
29	2.0	1.7	4.52	85		0.11	70%	5.30
30	1.7	1.5	4.73	85		0.11	73%	5.31
31	1.5	1.2	5.04	85		0.11	78%	5.34
32	1.3	1.1	5.28	85		0.11	81%	5.39
33	1.1	0.8	5.56	85		0.11	86%	5.42
34	0.8	0.6	5.76	85		0.11	89%	5.45
35	0.7	0.5	5.97	85		0.11	92%	5.49
36	0.5	0.3	6.16	85		0.11	95%	5.53
37	0.3	0.1	6.48	85		0.16	100%	5.63
38	0.1	0.1	6.48	85		0.16	100%	5.63

no samples

HY02-19P-2d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.4	19.4	0.00	99		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.4	10.6	0.00	99		0.01	0%	0.17
3	10.6	4.7	0.00	99		0.02	0%	0.27
4	4.7	4.4	0.00	99		0.03	0%	0.67
5	4.4	4.1	0.00	99		0.04	0%	1.01
6	4.1	3.8	0.00	99		0.05	0%	1.29
7	3.8	3.4	0.00	99		0.06	0%	1.47
8	3.4	3.2	0.00	99		0.07	0%	1.68
9	3.2	3.1	0.00	99		0.08	0%	1.93
10	3.1	2.9	0.00	99		0.09	0%	2.08
11	2.9	2.8	0.00	99		0.10	0%	2.27
12	2.8	2.8	0.00	99		0.11	0%	2.54
13	2.8	2.6	0.00	99		0.12	0%	2.61
14	2.6	2.5	0.00	99		0.13	0%	2.75
15	2.8	2.1	0.00	99		0.18	0%	3.29
16	2.4	1.9	1.11	99	1	0.20	8%	4.41
17	2.5	1.7	2.67	99		0.21	19%	5.87
18	2.4	1.6	4.23	99		0.22	29%	7.29
19	2.3	1.6	5.82	100	2 + BAG	0.22	41%	8.98
20	2.6	1.8	7.37	100		0.24	51%	11.28
21	2.4	1.7	8.95	100	3	0.24	62%	12.65
22	2.1	1.3	10.49	100		0.25	73%	13.36
23	1.5	0.7	12.08	100	4 + BAG	0.25	84%	13.60
24	1.0	0.4	13.35	100	5	0.25	93%	14.22
25	0.5	0.1	13.95	99	6	0.26	97%	14.14
26	0.2	0.1	14.35	99	7	0.30	100%	14.56

HY02-20P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.6	17.6	0.00	92		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.6	13.2	0.00	92		0.01	0%	0.10
3	13.2	9.3	0.00	92		0.01	0%	0.09
4	9.3	6.4	0.00	92		0.01	0%	0.08
5	6.4	2.9	0.00	92		0.08	0%	1.61
6	3.8	3.2	0.00	92		0.10	0%	2.43
7	3.9	3.1	0.00	92		0.13	0%	3.16
8	3.6	2.6	0.00	92		0.19	0%	4.12
9	3.1	2.1	0.00	92		0.30	0%	5.28
10	2.4	1.7	0.03	92		0.42	0%	6.21
11	1.8	1.4	0.04	92		0.55	1%	6.68
12	1.4	1.1	0.06	92		0.67	1%	6.51
13	1.2	1.0	0.51	92	1	0.75	7%	7.07
14	1.0	1.0	0.99	92	+ BAG	0.76	13%	7.55
15	1.0	0.9	1.84	97	2	0.76	25%	8.06
16	0.9	0.7	2.86	97		0.77	39%	7.67
17	0.7	0.6	3.70	97		0.77	50%	7.80
18	0.6	0.5	4.71	97	3	0.77	64%	8.07
19	0.5	0.4	5.57	97		0.77	76%	8.21
20	0.4	0.3	6.44	97	4	0.77	88%	8.34
21	0.3	0.1	7.35	97	5 + BAG	0.78	100%	7.80

HY02-20P-1f Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	15.8	15.8	0.00	93		0.00	0%	0.00
2	15.8	11.5	0.00	93		0.01	0%	0.15
3	11.5	8.5	0.00	93		0.01	0%	0.20
4	8.5	5.9	0.00	93		0.02	0%	0.20
5	5.9	4.0	0.00	93		0.03	0%	0.57
6	5.2	4.3	0.00	93		0.06	0%	1.81
7	5.0	4.3	0.00	93		0.08	0%	2.42
8	5.4	4.4	0.00	93		0.12	0%	4.05
9	5.2	4.4	0.31	93	1	0.16	3%	5.98
10	4.6	4.2	0.97	96	2	0.16	10%	6.63
11	4.2	3.9	1.28	96	+ BAG	0.16	13%	6.59
12	4.0	3.5	1.82	97	3	0.16	18%	6.62
13	3.7	3.5	2.32	97		0.16	24%	7.13
14	3.3	2.9	3.76	97	4	0.18	38%	8.01
15	2.5	1.9	4.98	97		0.19	51%	7.95
16	1.8	1.2	6.25	97	5	0.21	63%	8.25
17	1.3	0.6	7.66	97		0.25	78%	8.69
18	0.7	0.3	8.76	97	6	0.26	89%	9.16
19	0.4	0.1	9.85	91	7 + BAG	0.33	100%	9.74

HY02-20P-3 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.0	19.0	0.00	86		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.0	13.2	0.00	86		0.01	0%	0.53
3	13.2	7.8	0.00	86		0.02	0%	0.65
4	7.8	5.9	0.00	86		0.03	0%	0.90
5	5.9	5.6	0.00	86		0.04	0%	1.31
6	5.6	5.2	0.00	86		0.05	0%	1.63
7	5.2	5.1	0.00	86		0.06	0%	2.02
8	5.1	4.9	0.00	86		0.07	0%	2.34
9	4.9	4.7	0.00	86		0.08	0%	2.63
10	4.7	4.6	0.00	86		0.09	0%	2.96
11	4.7	3.7	0.00	86		0.18	0%	5.20
12	3.9	3.2	1.55	86	1 + BAG	0.23	10%	7.05
13	3.8	3.3	2.97	99	2	0.23	20%	9.59
14	3.5	2.9	4.52	99	3	0.24	30%	10.46
15	3.2	2.6	6.08	99	4 + BAG	0.24	40%	11.55
16	2.9	2.3	7.63	99	5	0.25	50%	12.52
17	2.5	1.9	9.18	99	6	0.26	60%	13.35
18	2.0	1.4	10.73	99	7	0.27	70%	13.78
19	1.4	0.8	12.34	99	8	0.29	81%	14.09
20	0.9	0.4	13.93	99	9	0.33	91%	14.77
21	0.4	0.1	15.23	99	10 + BAG	0.33	100%	15.18

HY02-20P-4 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.5	18.5	0.00	90		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.5	15.2	0.00	90		0.01	0%	0.21
3	15.2	13.3	0.00	90		0.01	0%	0.27
4	13.3	10.1	0.00	90		0.01	0%	0.35
5	10.1	7.4	0.00	90		0.02	0%	0.31
6	7.4	5.8	0.00	90		0.02	0%	0.30
7	5.8	4.3	0.00	90		0.02	0%	0.30
8	5.5	4.3	0.00	90		0.06	0%	1.50
9	5.4	3.7	0.34	90	1	0.16	2%	4.98
10	5.1	4.0	2.13	95	2	0.18	11%	8.19
11	5.0	4.4	3.50	95		0.19	17%	10.44
12	5.2	4.2	4.94	97	3	0.20	24%	11.99
13	4.8	4.2	6.32	97		0.20	31%	13.31
14	4.3	3.5	7.81	98	4	0.20	39%	13.67
15	3.8	3.0	9.25	98	+ BAG	0.20	46%	14.18
16	3.2	2.1	10.84	98		0.25	54%	14.99
17	2.4	1.9	12.12	98	5	0.25	60%	15.90
18	2.0	1.4	13.56	96		0.28	67%	16.45
19	1.6	1.0	14.99	96		0.31	74%	17.16
20	1.2	0.7	16.40	96	6	0.36	81%	18.04
21	0.8	0.2	17.85	96		0.37	88%	17.88
22	0.5	0.2	18.94	96		0.38	94%	18.94
23	0.3	0.1	20.02	97	7 + BAG	0.38	99%	19.66
24	0.1	0.1	20.24	97	8	0.38	100%	19.87

HY02-21P-1a Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	14.8	14.8	0.00	98		0.00	0%	0.00
2	14.8	8.8	0.00	98		0.01	0%	0.40
3	8.8	4.3	0.00	98		0.02	0%	0.45
4	4.3	3.6	0.00	98		0.03	0%	0.70
5	3.9	2.9	0.00	98		0.05	0%	1.16
6	3.3	2.3	0.00	98		0.10	0%	2.02
7	2.5	1.8	1.56	98	1	0.16	20%	4.09
8	2.5	1.6	3.11	98	2	0.18	39%	5.64
9	2.0	1.2	4.59	97	3 + BAG	0.19	57%	6.49
10	1.4	0.6	6.01	97	4	0.20	75%	6.92
11	0.7	0.2	7.13	96	5 + BAG	0.24	89%	7.36
12	0.3	0.1	7.98	96	6	0.26	100%	7.98

HY02-21P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.5	19.5	0.00	97		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.5	9.6	0.00	97		0.01	0%	0.00
3	9.6	6.4	0.00	97		0.02	0%	0.00
4	6.4	4.1	0.00	97		0.05	0%	1.06
5	4.1	3.2	0.00	97		0.10	0%	2.60
6	4.7	3.6	0.00	97		0.16	0%	4.67
7	4.1	3.8	0.26	97		0.18	2%	6.13
8	4.5	4.0	1.11	97		0.19	9%	7.50
9	4.1	3.5	2.00	97		0.19	17%	7.64
10	3.6	2.6	3.46	97	1 + BAG	0.21	29%	7.92
11	2.8	2.0	4.83	97		0.22	41%	8.50
12	2.1	1.4	6.25	97	2	0.23	53%	8.87
13	1.6	0.9	7.80	97		0.25	66%	9.48
14	1.1	0.5	9.21	97	3	0.27	78%	10.12
15	0.6	0.2	10.68	97	4 + BAG	0.29	90%	10.87
16	0.3	0.1	11.83	96	5	0.31	100%	11.73

HY02-21P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.7	17.7	0.00	98		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.7	5.6	0.00	98		0.01	0%	0.09
3	6.4	5.1	0.00	98		0.01	0%	0.08
4	6.3	5.0	0.00	98		0.01	0%	0.11
5	6.0	4.9	0.00	98		0.01	0%	0.22
6	5.2	4.2	0.00	98		0.02	0%	0.36
7	4.3	3.2	0.00	98		0.02	0%	0.41
8	3.4	2.4	0.00	98		0.03	0%	0.48
9	2.6	1.5	0.00	98		0.05	0%	0.54
10	1.7	0.8	0.47	98	1 + BAG	0.10	33%	1.13
11	1.1	0.3	1.32	99	2 + BAG	0.15	95%	1.69
12	0.4	0.1	1.40	99	3 + BAG	0.19	100%	1.55

HY02-21P-3 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.3	19.3	0.00	11		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.3	16.2	0.00	11		0.01	0%	0.08
3	16.2	14.6	0.00	11		0.02	0%	0.17
4	14.6	12.9	0.00	11		0.03	0%	0.24
5	12.9	11.5	0.00	11		0.04	0%	0.32
6	11.5	10.3	0.00	11		0.05	0%	0.37
7	10.3	9.3	0.00	11		0.06	0%	0.42
8	9.3	8.5	0.00	11		0.07	0%	0.46
9	8.5	7.8	0.00	11		0.08	0%	0.52
10	7.8	7.2	0.00	11		0.09	0%	0.55
11	7.2	5.1	0.00	11		0.12	0%	0.54
12	6.1	4.1	0.01	11		0.19	0%	0.77
13	5.5	3.1	0.09	11	1	0.33	1%	1.04
14	4.0	3.0	0.09	11		0.45	1%	1.38
15	3.1	2.5	0.79	67	2	0.45	7%	7.45
16	2.9	2.1	2.19	94	3	0.46	18%	10.13
17	2.4	1.7	3.75	95	4	0.47	32%	10.28
18	2.0	1.3	5.08	95		0.48	43%	10.04
19	1.4	0.9	6.41	95		0.51	54%	9.80
20	0.9	0.6	7.84	95		0.57	66%	10.16
21	0.7	0.2	9.27	95	5	0.59	78%	9.57
22	0.4	0.1	11.06	95		0.59	93%	10.75
23	0.1	0.1	11.91	95	6 + BAG	0.59	100%	11.56
24	0.1	0.1	11.91	95		0.54	100%	11.50

HY02-22P-1d Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	17.4	17.4	0.00	95		0.00	0%	0.00
2	17.4	11.7	0.00	95		0.01	0%	0.44
3	11.7	5.2	0.00	95		0.02	0%	0.35
4	5.2	3.6	0.00	95		0.03	0%	0.52
5	3.6	2.8	0.00	95		0.04	0%	0.64
6	2.8	2.4	0.00	95		0.05	0%	0.76
7	2.4	2.3	0.00	95		0.06	0%	0.94
8	2.3	2.1	0.00	95		0.07	0%	1.05
9	2.1	1.9	0.00	95		0.08	0%	1.12
10	1.9	1.7	0.00	95		0.09	0%	1.16
11	1.7	1.6	0.00	95		0.10	0%	1.23
12	1.6	1.3	0.44	95	1	0.14	13%	1.94
13	1.4	0.8	1.30	95	2 + BAG	0.19	39%	2.49
14	0.8	0.3	2.15	95	3	0.29	65%	2.80
15	0.3	0.1	3.31	95	4 + BAG	0.39	100%	3.49

gas not analyzed; used 95% methane for draft calculations

HY02-22P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	20.7	20.7	0.00	93		0.00	0%	0.00
2	20.7	9.3	0.00	93		0.02	0%	0.19
3	9.3	5.6	0.00	93		0.02	0%	0.17
4	5.7	4.1	0.00	93		0.04	0%	0.62
5	5.3	4.0	0.00	93		0.05	0%	0.93
6	5.2	3.3	0.00	93		0.06	0%	1.18
7	3.8	2.3	0.00	93		0.09	0%	1.36
8	2.8	1.7	0.00	93		0.14	0%	1.69
9	2.0	0.9	1.20	93	1	0.17	24%	2.24
10	1.3	0.5	2.28	93	+ BAG	0.20	45%	2.88
11	0.8	0.3	3.56	93		0.25	71%	3.91
12	0.4	0.1	4.48	96	2 + BAG	0.29	89%	4.43
13	0.2	0.1	5.00	96	3	0.30	100%	4.95

HY02-23P-1a Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	20.5	20.5	0.00	88		0.00	0%	0.00
2	20.5	14.7	0.00	88		0.01	0%	0.43
3	14.7	9.2	0.00	88		0.02	0%	0.57
4	9.2	3.3	0.00	88		0.03	0%	0.30
5	3.3	0.5	0.00	88		0.04	0%	0.07
6	0.5	0.4	0.00	88		0.05	0%	0.09
7	0.4	0.4	0.00	88		0.06	0%	0.13
8	0.4	0.4	0.00	88		0.07	0%	0.16
9	0.4	0.4	0.00	88		0.08	0%	0.20
10	0.4	0.4	0.00	88		0.09	0%	0.23
11	0.4	0.4	0.00	88		0.10	0%	0.26
12	0.4	0.1	1.01	88	1 + BAG	0.26	100%	1.09

HY02-23P-1c Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	21.4	21.4	0.00	85		0.00	0%	0.00
2	21.4	15.6	0.00	85		0.01	0%	0.54
3	15.6	9.8	0.00	85		0.02	0%	0.68
4	9.8	4.1	0.00	85		0.03	0%	0.43
5	4.1	0.4	0.00	85		0.04	0%	0.06
6	0.4	0.4	0.00	85		0.05	0%	0.10
7	0.4	0.3	0.00	85		0.06	0%	0.10
8	0.5	0.1	0.53	85	1	0.22	100%	0.61

HY02-23P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.4	19.4	0.00	92		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.4	11.8	0.00	92		0.01	0%	0.00
3	11.8	6.8	0.00	92		0.02	0%	0.00
4	6.8	1.4	0.00	92		0.03	0%	0.01
5	1.4	0.8	0.00	92		0.04	0%	0.07
6	0.8	0.8	0.00	92		0.05	0%	0.14
7	0.8	0.1	1.03	92	1	0.40	55%	1.27
8	0.8	0.1	1.88	94	2 + BAG	0.42	100%	2.10

HY02-24P-1 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	19.6	19.6	0.00	92		0.00	0%	0.00
2	19.6	13.2	0.00	92		0.01	0%	0.39
3	13.2	8.6	0.00	92		0.02	0%	0.39
4	8.6	4.6	0.00	92		0.03	0%	0.39
5	4.6	3.6	0.00	92		0.04	0%	0.59
6	3.6	3.1	0.00	92		0.05	0%	0.81
7	3.6	2.3	0.00	92		0.07	0%	0.97
8	2.8	1.8	0.00	92		0.11	0%	1.34
9	2.1	1.0	0.51	92	1 + BAG	0.20	10%	2.02
10	1.3	0.7	1.61	98	2 + BAG	0.23	32%	2.88
11	0.9	0.3	3.02	97	3 + BAG	0.34	60%	3.79
12	0.4	0.1	4.30	98	4 + BAG	0.37	85%	4.49
13	0.2	0.1	4.86	98	5	0.42	96%	5.10
14	0.1	0.1	5.07	85	6	0.42	100%	5.22

HY02-24P-2 Quantitative Degassing Table

Stage	Start Pressure (MPa)	End Pressure (MPa)	Cumulative Volume Gas Expelled (liters @ STP)	Percent Hydrocarbon Gases (%)	Gas Sample	Cumulative Volume Liquid Expelled (liters)	Degassing Progress (%)	Estimated Hydrocarbon Gas in System (liters @ STP)
1	18.8	18.8	0.00	91		0.00	0%	0.00
2	18.8	12.1	0.00	91		0.01	0%	0.09
3	12.1	6.9	0.00	91		0.02	0%	0.23
4	6.9	4.5	0.00	91		0.03	0%	0.41
5	4.5	3.9	0.00	91		0.04	0%	0.67
6	3.9	3.6	0.00	91		0.05	0%	0.93
7	3.6	3.4	0.00	91		0.06	0%	1.17
8	3.4	3.0	0.00	91		0.07	0%	1.29
9	3.3	2.3	0.00	91		0.13	0%	2.23
10	2.5	1.4	0.94	91	1 + BAG	0.17	14%	2.61
11	1.9	1.2	1.94	98	2	0.18	28%	3.65
12	1.3	0.8	2.85	98	3 + BAG	0.20	42%	4.05
13	1.1	0.3	4.41	98	4	0.26	65%	4.93
14	0.5	0.1	5.93	99	5 + BAG	0.34	87%	6.07
15	0.3	0.1	6.81	99	6	0.35	100%	6.94

Appendix K: Q-Degas Pressure-Volume Plots

HY02-05P-4b&c

HY02-07P-1f

HY02-05P-2

HY02-07P-1c

HY02-07P-2b

HY02-07P-3

HY02-07P-1g

HY02-07P-2e

HY02-08P-1c

HY02-09P-1

HY02-08P-1b

HY02-08P-1d

HY02-09P-2e&f

HY02-10P-2

HY02-09P-2b

HY02-10P-1

HY02-13P-2

HY02-15P-1b

HY02-13P-1

HY02-13P-3

HY02-19P-2d

HY02-20P-1f

HY02-19P-2b

HY02-20P-1c

HY02-20P-4

HY02-21P-1C

HY02-20P-3

HY02-21P-1a

HY02-21P-3

HY02-22P-2

HY02-21P-2

HY02-22P-1d

HY02-24P-2

Appendix L: Gas Hydrate Saturation Tables

HY02-														
Parameter	Units	1P-1a	2P-1	2P-3f	4P-2d	5P-2	5P-4b&c	7P-1c	7P-1f	7P-1g	7P-2b	7P-2e	7P-3	8P-1b
Sediment length	cm	70.0	20.0	20.0	11.0	40.0*	38.0*	20.0	20.0	15.0	20.0	50.0	15.0	18.0
Sediment volume	liters	1.850	0.528	0.528	0.291	1.057	1.004	0.528	0.528	0.396	0.528	1.321	0.396	0.476
Sediment porosity	%	35.3	35.3	29.4	33.5	33.5	35.3	32.4	34.1	31.8	30.6	30.0	31.2	32.4
Pore volume	liters	0.653	0.187	0.155	0.097	0.354	0.354	0.171	0.180	0.126	0.162	0.396	0.124	0.154
Volume HC gas collected	liters	0.96	0.09	0.09	6.10	20.37	26.79	4.34	15.47	8.75	7.72	21.47	8.74	10.48
Total HC gas in core	mmol	42	4	4	269	898	1180	191	681	385	340	946	385	462
Methane saturation	mmol/kg	55	54	54	53	53	53	52	52	52	52	52	52	50
Maximum dissolved methane in pore fluids	mmol	36	10	8	3	12	10	8	5	4	6	14	4	5
Excess HC gas**	mmol	7	-6	-4	265	885	1170	184	677	381	334	932	382	457
Volume of gas hydrate**	ml	0.9	-0.9	-0.6	36.2	120.6	159.4	25.0	92.2	52.0	45.5	127.0	52.0	62.3
Gas hydrate, % of pore volume**	%	0.1	-0.5	-0.4	37.1	34.0	45.0	14.6	51.1	41.3	28.2	32.0	42.1	40.5
Gas hydrate, % of core volume**	%	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	12.4	11.4	15.9	4.7	17.5	13.1	8.6	9.6	13.1	13.1

HY02-														
Parameter	Units	8P-1c	8P-1d	9P-1	9P-2b	9P-2e&f	10P-1	10P-2	11P-1	11P-2	12P-1	12P-2	13P-1	13P-2
Sediment length	cm	40.0	20.0	115.0*	10.0	40.0	115.0	65.0	114.0*	97.0	106.0	99.0	79.0	88.0*
Sediment volume	liters	1.057	0.528	3.039	0.264	1.057	3.039	1.718	3.012	2.563	2.801	2.616	2.088	2.325
Sediment porosity	%	32.4	34.7	31.8	25.9	32.4	28.8	30.6	29.4	27.6	25.3	25.3	27.1	26.5
Pore volume	liters	0.342	0.183	0.965	0.068	0.342	0.876	0.525	0.886	0.709	0.708	0.662	0.565	0.616
Volume HC gas collected	liters	5.79	11.12	10.29	0.13	0.16	0.96	0.30	5.49	6.53	8.05	13.58	8.11	7.59
Total HC gas in core	mmol	255	490	453	6	7	42	13	242	288	355	598	357	335
Methane saturation	mmol/kg	50	50	52	52	51	51	51	51	51	44	44	44	44
Maximum dissolved methane in pore fluids	mmol	16	6	47	4	18	45	27	44	34	29	26	23	25
Excess HC gas**	mmol	240	484	406	2	-11	-3	-14	198	253	325	573	335	309
Volume of gas hydrate**	ml	32.6	65.9	55.4	0.3	-1.5	-0.4	-1.9	27.0	34.5	44.3	78.1	45.6	42.2
Gas hydrate, % of pore volume**	%	9.5	35.9	5.7	0.4	-0.4	0.0	-0.4	3.0	4.9	6.3	11.8	8.1	6.8
Gas hydrate, % of core volume**	%	3.1	12.5	1.8	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.9	1.3	1.6	3.0	2.2	1.8

* Sediment length not equal to curated length. Actual sediment length estimated from X-ray to remove gaps or account for extra material.
 ** Negative values indicate no gas hydrate present. Values are retained as they provide useful information about the extent of undersaturation.

HY02-

Parameter	Units	13P-3	15P-1b	15P-1d	16P-1d	16P-2	17P-3a&b	17P-4	17P-5c	18P-1c	18P-2c	19P-2b	19P-2d	20P-1c
Sediment length	cm	106.0*	20.0	20.0	11.0	30.0	33.5	26.0	11.0	20.0	45.0	11.0	20.0	20.0
Sediment volume	liters	2.801	0.528	0.528	0.291	0.793	0.885	0.687	0.291	0.528	1.189	0.291	0.528	0.528
Sediment porosity	%	26.5	26.5	26.5	36.5	37.1	37.1	36.8	37.1	33.5	31.8	32.4	31.8	30.6
Pore volume	liters	0.741	0.140	0.140	0.106	0.294	0.328	0.253	0.108	0.177	0.378	0.094	0.168	0.162
Volume HC gas collected	liters	12.17	0.61	1.82	4.35	31.90	28.06	23.35	9.79	17.69	40.70	5.63	14.56	7.80
Total HC gas in core	mmol	536	27	80	192	1406	1236	1029	432	779	1793	248	642	344
Methane saturation	mmol/kg	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44
Maximum dissolved methane in pore fluids	mmol	30	6	6	4	5	7	5	2	3	6	3	4	5
Excess HC gas**	mmol	506	21	74	188	1401	1229	1024	429	776	1787	245	638	339
Volume of gas hydrate**	ml	69.0	2.8	10.1	25.6	190.9	167.5	139.5	58.5	105.8	243.6	33.4	86.9	46.2
Gas hydrate, % of pore volume**	%	9.3	2.0	7.2	24.2	65.0	51.1	55.2	54.3	59.7	64.5	35.6	51.8	28.6
Gas hydrate, % of core volume**	%	2.5	0.5	1.9	8.8	24.1	18.9	20.3	20.1	20.0	20.5	11.5	16.5	8.7

HY02-

Parameter	Units	20P-1f	20P-3	20P-4	21P-1a	21P-1c	21P-2	21P-3	22P-1d	22P-2	23P-1a	23P-1c	23P-2	24P-1	24P-2
Sediment length	cm	43.0	35.0	81.0	30.0	58.0*	35.0	110.0	70.0	120.0	62.0*	40.0	100.0	120.0	120.0
Sediment volume	liters	1.136	0.925	2.140	0.793	1.533	0.925	2.907	1.850	3.171	1.638	1.057	2.642	3.171	3.171
Sediment porosity	%	28.2	28.2	26.5	29.4	25.3	25.9	25.9	25.3	24.7	27.6	25.9	25.9	23.5	24.1
Pore volume	liters	0.321	0.261	0.567	0.233	0.388	0.239	0.752	0.468	0.763	0.453	0.274	0.684	0.746	0.765
Volume HC gas collected	liters	9.74	15.18	19.87	7.98	11.73	1.55	11.56	3.49	4.95	1.09	0.61	2.10	5.22	6.94
Total HC gas in core	mmol	429	669	876	352	517	68	509	154	218	48	27	92	230	306
Methane saturation	mmol/kg	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44	44
Maximum dissolved methane in pore fluids	mmol	12	7	20	8	14	10	30	20	33	20	12	30	31	32
Excess HC gas**	mmol	418	661	856	344	503	58	479	134	185	28	15	63	199	274
Volume of gas hydrate**	ml	56.9	90.1	116.6	46.8	68.5	7.9	65.3	18.3	25.2	3.9	2.1	8.6	27.1	37.3
Gas hydrate, % of pore volume**	%	17.7	34.5	20.6	20.1	17.7	3.3	8.7	3.9	3.2	0.9	0.8	1.3	3.6	4.9
Gas hydrate, % of core volume**	%	5.0	9.7	5.4	5.9	4.5	0.9	2.2	1.0	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.9	1.2

* Sediment length not equal to curated length. Actual sediment length estimated from X-ray to remove gaps or account for extra material.
 ** Negative values indicate no gas hydrate present. Values are retained as they provide useful information about the extent of undersaturation.

Appendix M: Linescan Images

HY02-01P-1a Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-02P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-05P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-06P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-06P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-06P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P-1g Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P-2b Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-07P-2e Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P-1b Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-08P-1c Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-09P-2b Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

cm 125 cm

HY02-09P-4a Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-10P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-11P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-12P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-13P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-15P-1d Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-16P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P-1c Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-17P-4 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P-1d Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-18P-2c Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P-1f Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-20P-4 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P-1a Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P-1c Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-21P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P-1a Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P-1d Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-22P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P-1a Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P-1c Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-23P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P-1 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P-2 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

HY02-24P-3 Image

2x Horizontal Exaggeration

Appendix N: PCATS Triaxial Reports

PCATS Triaxial Sample ANS-HY02-04P-2d (2401.1ft MD)

Key parameters of the sample:

HY02-04P, 731.2m MD

Figure 1: Characteristics and X-ray images of Sample 04P in the interval around subsample -2d (box) selected for PCATS Triax. Radiographs densities and P-wave velocities obtained in PCATS.

Table 1: Test results of Sample 04P-2d. Gamma density and P-wave velocity determined in PCATS.

Bottom depth (m MD):	732.0				
In-situ effective stress (MPa):	4.6				
Average P-wave velocity (m/s):	2378				
Average gamma density (g/cm ³):	2.09				
Methane hydrate saturation (% pore volume):	37				
Effective stress tested (kPa):	200	400	800	1600	1600, degassed
Shear Modulus (MPa):	139	187	293	465	323
S-wave velocity (m/s):	257	297	372	468	391
Permeability (mD):	26.6	9.42	8.55	8.05	12.47

Sample transfer:

The sample was successfully extruded into the PCATS Triaxial cell with zero effective stress but otherwise in situ P - T -conditions of 9.6 MPa (total stress) and 5.5 C. Contact of the sample top with the top cap was verified by a lasting increase of the load cell reading (~ 20 kPa). A low positive load was maintained during extrusion of the sample into the rubber membrane, to maintain contact of the sample with the top cap. Full extrusion length was reached at full extension of the bottom manipulator (53.9 cm). This corresponded to an extruded sample length of 11.1 cm as indicated by the LVDT installed in the cell. This agrees with the reported length of the sample (11 cm) on reception.

Sample reconsolidation:

Sample reconsolidation was performed in four steps at effective stresses of 200 kPa, 400 kPa, 800 kPa and 1600 kPa. Note that the maximum effective stress was lower than the in-situ value (4600 kPa, J. Yoneda, personal communication, January 2023) due to instrument limitations. The effective stress was raised by pore pressure reduction. At each consolidation step the confining pressure was raised to the starting pressure, if necessary. Consolidation at each step was considered complete once the shrinkage of the sample as indicated by LVDT was less than 0.1 mm/h (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effective stress (ES) history (orange) and corresponding lengths (blue) of sample 04P-2d from time of full extrusion to final testing. Times of resonance column (RC) and permeability tests are indicated by grey and blue arrows, respectively. Axial loads and confining pressures were adjusted dynamically whilst the sample was reconsolidating. Motors were stopped at times of resonance column and permeability tests, to rule out effects of variations in effective stress on sample consolidation. The large variability of the ES curve starting on Day 7 is a result of sample depressurisation. The drop of ES thereafter, to 1213 kPa (Day 7.8) is due to a rise in the pore pressure whilst the sample was isolated, suggesting ongoing dissociation of gas hydrate remnants or methane exsolution from pore water.

Sample testing

Resonance column and permeability tests were performed once consolidation was complete at each step. Resonance tests were conducted by inducing a torsional vibration in the sample over a broad frequency range. Accelerometers delivered peak voltages at the resonance frequency of the sample. Permeability tests were conducted with flow directed from sample top to bottom, at a constant volumetric flow rate of $-10 \mu\text{L/s}$. After completing the tests at 1600 kPa the pore pressure was reduced to atmospheric pressure whilst maintaining the isotropic stress at 1600 kPa. The volume of the gas released during the depressurisation was measured to determine the gas hydrate saturation (S) of the pore space

of the sample. Once the sample was depressurised, the total pressure was reapplied to starting conditions and final resonance and permeability tests were carried out. The sample length was recorded throughout the test and until the system was depressurised for sample recovery. The results of the tests are summarised in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: Resonance column and permeability test results of sample 04P-2d. ' V_s '=Shear wave velocity, ' G_{max} '=Small Strain Shear Modulus, ' k '=Permeability. 'down' refers to the flow direction of water through the sample in constant flow permeability tests.

Elastic parameters G_{max} and V_s

Figure 5 shows the frequency response curves of the sample at the effective stresses tested. The resonance frequencies are clearly identifiable from the peak locations. G_{max} and V_s were calculated using the methodology described in ASTM 4015-07 and plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows that G_{max} and V_s follow a linear positive trend as the effective stress is increased. At maximum tested effective stress (1600 kPa) Extrapolation of the values to in-situ stress conditions (4.6 MPa) predict values of $G_{max} = 11.7$ GPa and $V_s = 922$ m/s for the sample with gas hydrate.

Permeability

Figure 4 shows differential pressures registered during constant flow tests. Permeabilities were calculated from differential pressures at steady state and are summarised in Table 1. Before reaching steady state conditions the differential pressure graphs at 400, 800 and 1600 kPa degassed show inflections, after which differential pressures increase at different rates for prolonged time periods. This suggests that control of permeability at the inflections changes from water to the higher viscosity oil-based drilling mud, the presence of which was later verified in the recovered sample (Figure 7). The graph for 1600 kPa degassed indicates that a steady state was reached before the inflection. Steady state differential pressures for the data sets at 400 and 800 kPa were obtained from extrapolating the data series before the inflections using functions of the form $\Delta P = a \cdot e^{tb} + c$, where $c = \Delta P$ at steady state, whilst a and b are other fit parameters. Although steady state ΔP determined in this manner seem plausible as they increase with the consolidation state of the sample, the derived permeabilities should be treated with caution as the effect of the drilling mud during the entire tests could not be quantified.

Figure 5: Frequency response curves for sample 04P-2d

Figure 4: Differential pressure (ΔP) change with testing time measured along the sample as fluid is directed upwards through the sample at $-10 \mu\text{L/s}$. The tests at 400 and 800 kPa did not reach steady state (see text for details). ΔP for these were determined from parameters of a fit (dashed lines). ΔP for the data set at 1600 kPa degassed was determined at $0.17 < t < 0.50$.

Degassing

Figure 6 shows the stepwise degassing of Sample 4P-2d through controlled fluid extraction. The total volume of methane in the system was determined to be 6.10 L (STP). Assuming full cage occupancy, this corresponds to a methane hydrate saturation of 37%.

Figure 7: Degassing of Sample 04P-2d. Depressurisation was achieved by incremental extraction of fluid from the sample. The cumulative volume of extracted gas is shown by the blue graph.

Figure 6: Recovered sample 04P-2d. Brown discolorations indicate oil-based drilling mud.

PCATS Triaxial Sample ANS-HY02-16P-1d (2914.2ft MD)

**Key parameters of the sample:
HY02-16P, 887.8m MD**

Figure 1: Characteristics and X-ray images of Sample 16P in the interval around subsample -1d (solid bordered box) selected for PCATS Triax. Radiographs, densities and P-wave velocities obtained in PCATS.

Table 1: Test results of Sample 16P-1d (P-wave velocity and shear modulus) and -c (hydrate saturation). Gamma density and P-wave velocity determined in PCATS.

Bottom depth (m MD):	887.8				
In-situ effective stress (MPa):	5.6				
Average P-wave velocity (m/s):	2198				
Average gamma density (g/cm ³):	2.08				
Methane hydrate saturation (% pore volume):	24				
Effective stress tested (kPa):	200	400	800	1600	1600, degassed
Shear Modulus (MPa):	n/a	896	1100	1348	1160
S-wave velocity (m/s):	n/a	655	726	801	743
Permeability (mD):			0.92		

Sample transfer:

The sample was successfully extruded into the PCATS Triaxial cell with zero effective stress but otherwise in situ P - T -conditions of 9.7 MPa (total stress) and 8.1 C. Contact of the sample top with the top cap was verified by a lasting increase of the load cell reading (~ 20 kPa). A low positive load was maintained during extrusion of the sample into the rubber membrane, to maintain contact of the sample with the top cap. Full extrusion length was reached at full extension of the bottom manipulator (53.4 cm). This corresponded to an extruded sample length of 10.6 cm as indicated by the LVDT installed in the cell. This agrees with the reported length of the sample (11 cm) on reception.

Sample reconsolidation:

Sample reconsolidation was performed in three steps at effective stresses of 400 kPa, 800 kPa and 1600 kPa. The effective stress was raised by pore pressure reduction. At each consolidation step the confining pressure was raised to the starting pressure, if necessary. Consolidation at each step was considered complete once the shrinkage of the sample indicated by LVDT was less than 0.1 mm/h (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effective stress history (orange) and corresponding lengths (blue) of sample 16P-1d from time of full extrusion to final testing. Times of resonance column (RC) and permeability tests are indicated by grey and blue arrows, respectively. Axial loads and confining pressures were adjusted dynamically whilst the sample was reconsolidating. Motors were stopped at times of resonance column and permeability tests and during depressurisation of the sample. The large excursions of ES between Days 1.8 and 2.1 are a result of sample depressurisation during quantitative degassing.

Sample testing

Resonance column and permeability tests were performed once consolidation was complete at each step. Resonance tests were conducted by inducing a torsional vibration in the sample over a broad frequency range. Accelerometers delivered peak voltages at the resonance frequency of the sample. Permeability tests were conducted with flow directed from sample bottom to top, at an absolute constant volumetric flow rate of 4 μ L/s. Hydrate saturation was determined by quantitative degassing. The results of the tests are summarised in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: Resonance column and permeability test results of sample 16P-1d. 'up' refers to flow direction of water through the sample in constant flow permeability tests.

Elastic parameters G_{max} and V_s

Figure 5 shows the frequency response curves of the sample at the effective stresses tested. The resonance frequencies are clearly identifiable from the peak locations. G_{max} and V_s were calculated using the methodology described in ASTM 4015-07 and plotted in Figure 3.

G_{max} and V_s increase with effective stress from 896 MPa and 655 m/s, respectively at 400 kPa to 1348 MPa and 801 m/s. Linear extrapolation of tested values to in-situ effective stress (5600 kPa, J. Yoneda, personal communication, January 2023) predict $G_{max} = 2828$ MPa and $V_s = 1277$ m/s. Removal of the gas hydrate through quantitative degassing of the sample yielded $G_{max} = 1160$ MPa and $V_s = 743$ m/s.

Permeability

Figure 6 shows differential pressures registered during constant flow tests carried out at 800 kPa effective stress. Permeabilities were calculated from differential pressures at steady state and are summarised in Table 1. Permeability tests at 400 kPa and 1600 kPa did not reach steady state, preventing calculation or even extrapolation of meaningful permeabilities. Likely cause for the inability of the system to reach steady state differential pressures was infrequent clogging and sudden release of fluid conduits by the viscous drilling mud at these effective stresses. This was evident from observing the flexible polyester conduit visible through the sight glass of the pressurised cell Figure 4.

Figure 4: Sample view through sight glass of pressurised cell. A quantity of viscous drilling mud is visible in the semi-opaque polyester fluid conduit, downstream of the sample.

Figure 5: Frequency response curves for sample 16P-1d

Figure 6: Differential pressure change measured along the sample as fluid is directed upwards at 4 $\mu\text{L/s}$. No meaningful data could be obtained for permeability tests at 400 kPa and 1600 kPa, most likely due to clogging of fluid conduits.

Degassing

Figure 7 shows the stepwise degassing of Sample 16P-1d through controlled fluid extraction. The total volume of methane in the system was determined to be 4.35 L (STP). Assuming full cage occupancy, this corresponds to a methane hydrate saturation of 24%.

Figure 7: Degassing of Sample 16P-1d. Depressurisation was achieved by incremental extraction of fluid from the sample. The cumulative volume of extracted gas is shown by the blue graph.

Sample Recovery

Figure 8: Recovered sample 16P-1d. Freckles of drilling mud (dark brown) can be seen to cover a large part of the surface of the sample.

PCATS Triaxial Sample ANS-HY02-17P-5b & c (2927.9ft MD)

Key parameters of the sample:

Figure 1: Characteristics and X-ray images of Sample 17P in the interval around subsamples -5b (solid bordered box) and -5c (dashed) selected for PCATS Triax. Radiographs, densities and P-wave velocities obtained in PCATS.

Table 1: Test results of Sample 17P-5b (P-wave velocity and shear modulus) and -c (hydrate saturation). Gamma density and P-wave velocity determined in PCATS.

Bottom depth (m MD):	892.4				
In-situ effective stress (MPa):	5.6				
Average P-wave velocity (m/s):	2947				
Average gamma density (g/cm ³):	2.08				
Methane hydrate saturation (% pore volume):	54				
Effective stress tested (kPa):	200	400	800	1600	1600, degassed
Shear Modulus (MPa):	n/a	4017	4380	n/a	n/a
S-wave velocity (m/s):	n/a	1391	1450	n/a	n/a
Permeability (mD):		3.74	6.75*		

Sample transfer:

Sample 17P-5b was successfully extruded into the PCATS Triaxial cell with zero effective stress but otherwise in situ *P-T*-conditions of 9.7 MPa (total stress) and 8.1 C. Contact of the sample top with the top cap was verified by a lasting increase of the load cell reading (~20k Pa). A low positive load was maintained during extrusion of the sample into the rubber membrane, to maintain contact of the sample with the top cap. Full extrusion length was reached at full extension of the bottom manipulator (53.4 cm). This corresponded to an extruded sample length of 11.2 cm as indicated by the LVDT installed in the cell. This agrees with the reported length of the sample (11 cm) on reception.

Sample reconsolidation:

Reconsolidation of 17P-5b was performed in two steps at effective stresses of 400 kPa and 800 kPa. The effective stress was raised by pore pressure reduction. At each consolidation step the confining pressure was raised to the starting pressure, if necessary. Consolidation at each step was considered complete once the shrinkage of the sample as indicated by LVDT was less than 0.1 mm/h (Figure 2). Consolidation times and overall sample shrinkage was lower than for other samples of this test series, indicating good retention of the matrix structure from core recovery until reconsolidation in PCATS Triax.

A puncture in the membrane during testing at 800 kPa resulted in a loss of effective stress and the termination of the test before sample 17P-5b was degassed quantitatively. The gas hydrate saturation stated in Table 1 was determined through quantitative degassing of the very similar sample 17P-5c, which was extruded into PCATS Triax exclusively for this purpose.

Figure 2: Effective stress history (orange) and corresponding lengths (blue) of sample 17P-5b from time of full extrusion to final testing. Times of resonance column (RC) and permeability tests are indicated by grey and blue arrows, respectively. Axial loads and confining pressures were adjusted dynamically whilst the sample was reconsolidating. Motors were stopped at times of resonance column and permeability tests and after Day 1.1. The sample membrane suffered a puncture during permeability testing at 800 kPa, resulting in the inability to maintain effective stress. The time the puncture occurred is clearly identified by the sharp drop of effective stress at Day 1.07. The drop of effective stress caused the sample to lengthen slightly. The spike in ES at Day 1.6 is a result of sample depressurisation.

Sample testing

Resonance column and permeability tests were performed once consolidation was complete at each step. Resonance tests were conducted by inducing a torsional vibration in the sample over a broad frequency range. Accelerometers delivered peak voltages at the resonance frequency of the sample. Permeability tests were conducted with flow directed from sample top to bottom, at an absolute constant volumetric flow rate of 10 $\mu\text{L/s}$. Due to the puncture of the membrane, the permeability test did not reach steady state. A steady state pressure was derived by extrapolation of the existing data using an exponential fit (Figure 4). After abandoning the test, the cell pressure was reduced to atmospheric pressure. Hydrate saturation was inferred from the adjacent and similar (Figure 1) sample 17P-5c, which was degassed quantitatively. The results of the tests are summarised in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: Resonance column and permeability test results of sample 17P-5b. 'down' refers to flow direction of water through the sample in constant flow permeability tests.

Elastic parameters G_{\max} and V_s

Figure 5 shows the frequency response curves of the sample at the effective stresses tested. The resonance frequencies are clearly identifiable from the peak locations. G_{\max} and V_s were calculated using the methodology described in ASTM 4015-07 and plotted in Figure 3.

G_{\max} and V_s are highest amongst all samples tested in PCATS Triax (4383 MPa and 1448 m/s, respectively at 800 kPa), and do not increase notably with effective stress. This indicates the good preservation of the matrix structure during storage at only hydrostatic pressure.

Permeability

Figure 4 shows differential pressures registered during constant flow tests carried out at 400 and 800 kPa effective stress. Permeabilities were calculated from differential pressures at steady state and are summarised in Table 1. Note that the higher permeability was determined at 400 kPa effective stress than at 800 kPa effective stress. This unexpected behaviour highlights the importance of extrinsic controls, such as the occasional clogging fluid conduits by viscous drilling mud, that was similarly observed in sample HY02-16P-1d, on permeability testing of sample 17P-05b.

Figure 5: Frequency response curves for sample 17P-5b.

Figure 4: Differential pressure change measured along the sample as fluid is directed upwards at 10 $\mu\text{L/s}$. The test at 800 kPa did not reach steady state before the sample membrane suffered a puncture. A function of the form $a \cdot \exp(b \cdot t) + c$ (dashed line), where $c = \Delta P$ at steady state, was fit to the existing data to yield $\Delta P = 91.5$ kPa.

Degassing

Figure 7 shows the stepwise degassing of Sample 17P-5c through controlled fluid extraction. The total volume of methane in the system was determined to be 9.79 L (STP). Assuming full cage occupancy, this corresponds to a methane hydrate saturation of 54%.

Figure 7: Degassing of Sample 17P-5c. Depressurisation was achieved by incremental extraction of fluid from the sample. The cumulative volume of extracted gas is shown by the blue graph.

Figure 6: Recovered sample 17P-5c. Dark brown areas on the surface indicate oil-based drilling mud.

PCATS Triaxial Sample ANS-HY02-19P-2b (2948.1ft MD)

Key parameters of the sample:

Figure 1: Characteristics and X-ray images of Sample 19P in the interval around subsample -2b (box) selected for testing in PCTAS Triax. Radiographs, densities and P-wave velocities obtained in PCATS.

Table 1: Test results of Sample 19P-2b. Gamma density and P-wave velocity determined in PCATS.

Bottom depth (m MD):	898.6				
In-situ effective stress (MPa):	5.6				
Average P-wave velocity (m/s):	2300				
Average gamma density (g/cm ³):	2.16				
Methane hydrate saturation (% pore volume):	30				
Effective stress tested (kPa):	200	400	800	1600	1600 degassed
Shear Modulus (MPa):	120	175	271	501	361
S-wave velocity (m/s):	233	282	350	475	403
Permeability (mD):	4.10	3.47	3.76	3.19	15.78

Sample transfer:

The sample was successfully extruded into the PCATS Triaxial cell with zero effective stress but otherwise in situ P - T -conditions of 9.5 MPa (total stress) and 8.1 C. Contact of the sample top with the top cap was verified by a lasting increase of the load cell reading (~ 20 kPa). A low positive load was maintained during extrusion of the sample into the rubber membrane, to maintain contact of the sample with the top cap. Full extrusion length was reached at full extension of the bottom manipulator (53.4 cm). This corresponded to an extruded sample length of 11.3 cm as indicated by the LVDT. This agrees with the reported length of the sample (11 cm) on reception.

Sample reconsolidation:

Sample reconsolidation was performed in four steps at effective stresses of 200 kPa, 400 kPa, 800 kPa, and 1600 kPa. Note that the maximum effective stress was lower than the in-situ value (5600 kPa, J. Yoneda, personal communication, January 2023) due to instrument limitations. The effective stress was raised by pore pressure reduction. At each consolidation step the confining pressure was raised to the starting pressure, if necessary. Consolidation at each step was considered complete once the shrinkage of the sample as indicated by LVDT was less than 0.1 mm/h (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effective stress (ES) history (orange) and corresponding lengths (blue) of sample 19P-2b from time of full extrusion to final testing. Times of resonance column (RC) and permeability tests are indicated by grey and blue arrows, respectively. Axial loads and confining pressures were adjusted dynamically whilst the sample was reconsolidating. Motors were stopped between Days 2.92 and 5.75, at times of resonance column and permeability tests, as well as during degassing (indicated by large variations of ES around Day 10). No data was recorded whilst the system equilibrated between Days 2.92 and 5.75.

Sample testing

Resonance column and permeability tests were performed once consolidation was complete at each step. Resonance tests were conducted by inducing a torsional vibration in the sample at frequencies over a broad frequency range. Accelerometers delivered peak voltages at the resonance frequency of the sample. Permeability tests were conducted in both flow directions, where possible and at an absolute constant volumetric flow rate of 10 $\mu\text{L/s}$. After completing the tests at 1600 kPa the pore pressure was

reduced to atmospheric pressure whilst maintaining the isotropic stress at 1600 kPa. The volume of the gas released during the depressurisation was measured to determine the gas hydrate saturation (S) of the pore space of the sample. Once the sample was depressurised, the total pressure was reapplied to starting conditions and final resonance and permeability tests were carried out. The sample length was recorded throughout the test and until the system was depressurised for sample recovery. The results of the tests are summarised in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: Resonance column and permeability test results of sample 19P-2b. 'Vs'=Shear wave velocity, 'G_{max}'=Small Strain Shear Modulus, 'k'=Permeability. 'up' and 'down' refer to flow direction of water through the sample in constant flow permeability tests.

Elastic parameters G_{max} and V_s

Figure 4 shows the frequency response curves of the sample at the effective stresses tested. The resonance frequencies are clearly identifiable from the peak locations. G_{max} and V_s were calculated using the methodology described in ASTM 4015-07 and plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows that G_{max} and V_s follow a linear trend upwards as the effective stress is increased. At maximum tested effective stress (1600 kPa) G_{max} and V_s reached respective 501 MPa and 475 m/s with gas hydrate and 361 MPa and 403 m/s without gas hydrate. Extrapolation of the values to in-situ stress conditions would indicate values of $G_{max} = 15.8$ GPa and $V_s = 1155$ m/s for the sample with gas hydrate.

Permeability

Figure 5 shows differential pressures registered during constant flow tests carried out at varying effective stress conditions. Permeabilities were calculated from differential pressures once these had reached steady state. Permeabilities ranged between 3.2 and 4.2 mD (Figure 3). Although the lowest permeability was measured at the highest tested effective stress, the correlation between the consolidation of the sample and extracted permeability was poor. After removal of the gas hydrate the permeability increased notably to 16.4 mD at 1600 kPa effective stress.

Figure 4: Frequency response curves for sample 19P-2b.

Figure 5: Differential pressure change measured along the sample as fluid is directed upwards at 10 $\mu\text{L/s}$.

Degassing

Figure 6 shows the stepwise degassing of Sample 19P-2b through controlled fluid extraction. A marked increase in gas production at 5.1 MPa indicates that the gas hydrate starts to dissociate at this pressure. The total volume of methane in the system was determined to be 5.63 L (STP). Assuming full cage occupancy this corresponds to a methane hydrate saturation of 36%.

Figure 7: Degassing of Sample 19P-2b. Depressurisation was achieved by incremental extraction of fluid from the sample. The cumulative volume of extracted gas is shown by the blue graph.

Figure 6: Recovered sample 19P-2b. Drilling mud is visible as dark brown freckles on the surface of the sample.